

University of the West of Scotland

**“The impact of social media on banking industry and banking consumer: Case
in Vietnam”**

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Abstract

In the era of Internet and social network, consumers tend to in to increasingly manage their daily lives digitally. They believe that social network supports them to engage in social interaction as well as being a tool to seeking products and services. Therefore, in the aspect of business, social media has been become a very convenient network which significantly contribute for the purpose of trading and promotion activities. Finance and banking industry did not stay beyond the social media trend. Applying of social media in banking industry indicates a movement in customer behaviour towards the mode of accessing banking products and services. This movement created valuable opportunities to obtain insight from customers by leveraging social media data. In order to approach their consumers, the majority of banks are investing in social media marketing that can effectively support them in satisfying consumers and also raising the brand awareness. In the fact, there was not many research focus on the impact of social media in specific industry as banking, especially in developing countries, particularly in Vietnam. Therefore, this research is conducted to identify and examine the impact of social media on banking industry and consumer behavior including key elements to create the viral contents as well as those factors to gather customers and banking services through applying social media.

Base on the literature review and conceptual framework, the study will also evaluate a significant role of social media which the traditional marketing such as magazines and advertising campaigns do not have the influence that they did in the past. This research

illustrates how the financial firms and banks use the social media as the tool to promote their products and raise the brand awareness. Based on that, this study deepens how results of social media interaction affect to consumer perception in relation with choosing the appropriate banking services.

Based on the research aim, the research will follow a pragmatism philosophy when conducting the methodology in the research. Because pragmatism in epistemology provides a practical meaning of knowledge in the particular contexts. On the other hand, it also emphasizes practical solutions and outcomes. The mixed method search will be applied in this research. This is combination of quantitative and qualitative methods which provides a deeper understanding of complex phenomena. Qualitative method will be conducted by interviews with managerial level in Vietnamese commercial banks. They provide comments towards social media and social media marketing strategy related to business growth. Through the interview, it has supported the researcher an insight towards how banks generate contents on social media which effortlessly build a loyal customer base. Moreover, the interview has provided in-depth about the development of brand awareness and building strategy for social media channels in banking industry. In another aspect, quantitative method has been conducted as taking a sample of 152 questionnaires. Self-selection sampling is used as the sampling method, the questionnaire has been distributed to customers and bank employees in Vietnam. As the result, interviews and questionnaires has been conducted to collect data which will illustrate the application of social media in banking industry.

In conclusion, based on the statistical results, the research also will be proved that by applying social media to enhance the engagement between consumers and banks has a positive and significant role in building banking brand awareness. Further discussion and recommendation were conducted for future research on investigating impacting factors that can potentially lead to higher level consumer satisfaction with banking services via social media.

Outline and structure of the thesis

➤ Chapter one: This chapter introduces the research and basically discusses the background and the importance of social media in general and in the banking sector. It also presents main points of motivation of the research, rationale for choosing Vietnam to involve in this research, research objectives, questions, and hypotheses.

➤ Chapter two: This chapter is to discuss about literature reviews which relate to social media establishment, social media in business and different industries. Based on that, chapter two developed social media concepts and it reviewed the impact of social media on banking industry and banking consumer through the previous studies.

➤ Chapter three: This chapter examines the methodology used in this research. Based on the provided knowledge, this chapter also explained the reason of the choice of research methods and research design. Data analysis techniques and data collection have been described in this chapter.

➤ Chapter four: This chapter examines the impact of social media on banking industry by using quantitative analysis techniques and through the analysis of questionnaires.

➤ Chapter five: This chapter examines the impact of social media on banking industry, the benefits and challenges of social media towards marketing strategy of banks based on participant's experiences through the analysis of interviews.

➤ Chapter six: A discussion of the findings of this research, limitation and recommendations for the future research are provided in this chapter.

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter outline a background of social media and its role in businesses in general as well as in the banking industry. It also introduces the importance of social media impacts on consumer behavior and discusses about the motivation of the research. Finally, the aim and objectives are stated in this chapter.

1.1. Background:

The concept of social media has been gradually developed from the human interaction and the communication of individuals. Social networking was generated to gather people and also has been become a popular activity in daily life. Therefore, in recent years, the influence of social media plays a vital role in many aspects of our life. It not only affects to human communication, also extremely impacts on business where the social media has been utilized to increase the business's value and expand the brand awareness.

Beginning of 21th century, the information system has been strongly developed with a very start of many social networking sites. Social media has played an important role to connect communications and businesses. It has been considered as the fastest way to reinforce marketing strategy of businesses when applying social media as effective tool in conjunction with traditional marketing. In the early 2000s, several networking sites were introduced as social media platform in order to facilitate human interaction on internet. People enable to effortlessly exchange, share and interact various information with each other on social media platform. The effectiveness of social networking sites opened a new vision for businesses to conduct their marketing strategy by using social media for

advertisement, spread their reputation and branding, maintain customer relationship and so on. The major social media platform has been introduced such as MySpace, Facebook, Yahoo360, YouTube, Twitter (Edosomwan et al., 2011).

Social media is a crucial communication channel that businesses use to reach a broader customer base. Its effectiveness in engaging customers significantly enhances brand awareness. Social media supports brand building, maintains brand reputation, and helps disseminate a strong brand name. Through interactive and viral content such as videos, images, and conversations, businesses leverage social media to create promotional campaigns that foster customer interaction. This interaction not only promotes products and services but also facilitates communication between businesses and their customer, providing insights into consumer behavior. Furthermore, social media helps attract potential customers, expanding the customer base and enhancing brand visibility. As a cost-effective marketing tool compared to traditional advertising, social media enables businesses to achieve their marketing objectives, receive immediate customer feedback, and address customer concerns. Consequently, many brand and businesses intergrate social media into their marketing strategies to maximize profits.

1.2. Social media in business and its impact on banking industry

The development of social media has created numerous opportunities and benefits for businesses across various industries. Companies and brands have leveraged social media as a sharp marketing tool to enhance their reputation and increase their value. In terms of customer relationship management (CRM), many businesses have utilized social media to support their CRM systems. These systems connect customer demands to products and services, manage customer relationship, maintain sustainability. Social media's role in CRM has generated an environment that not only maintains existing customers but also reaches potential customers. The strength of customer relationships has significantly improved by integrating social media marketing into business strategies. Social media platform enable faster customer interactions than other channels, allowing businesses to provide prompt responses and instant customer care to meet their demands. Platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram are essential for deploying CRM activities.

In the marketing sector, social media plays a vital role in promoting products and services. These platforms have become powerful tools that help businesses remain

competitive in the market. Social media offers various functions, such as likes, shares, reposts, and retweets, which support promotional content going viral and enable instant customer interaction. Additionally, social media analytic tools help businesses analyze customer databases, activities, and track the traffic and progress of promotional campaigns. This allows companies to understand customer preferences and behavior better.

Raising brand awareness is a primary goal of marketing strategies, making businesses more competitive. Brands and businesses expect social media to yield effective outcomes for their brand reputation. They believe that social media provides an environment where content marketing and product information are widely disseminated to customers. By utilizing social media features optimally, businesses aim to deliver impactful impressions of their product and services. This influences customer behavior and improves brand awareness through customer interactions on social media.

Despite the extensive research on the role of social media marketing strategies on corporate performance, there is a gap in understanding the specific mechanisms through which social media influences brand reputation and customer engagement. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how social media's unique features and functions contribute to building and maintaining strong customer relationships and enhancing brand awareness. The novelty of this study lies in its detailed examination of the interplay between social media activities and their direct impact on customer behavior and brand perception.

Currently, most businesses and brands across various industries leverage social media to enhance their marketing strategies and maintain customer relationships. From a strategic perspective, social media extends beyond marketing to include other vital aspects of company operations, such as recruiting and connecting with stakeholders or partners, known as business to business (B2B) interaction (Bernard, 2016). The financial services sector, in particular, has adopted this trend to build their reputation and bolster marketing efforts. Within this sector, banks utilize social media to address customer inquiries, understand their needs and complaints, and provide timely and effective responses. Some banks have been exploring the potential of social media for transactional banking. However, due to security concerns, transactional activities via social media remain limited, necessitating further investigation by banks (Paurusheva, 2019). Consequently, most banks currently focus on using social media as marketing tool, communication channel, and

customer service platform rather than for transactions. This strategic use of social media not only supports marketing objectives but also facilitates robust customer relationship management, reinforcing the bank's overall competitive position in the market.

1.2.1. Social media in banking sector

Social media created the essential social media marketing tool for banking sector. Indeed, brings advantages to banks in implementing their strategies through employing social media as the sharpen tools. Same as other business industries, social media has been employed by banks to provide online community for customer engagement Ahuja (2020). Banks have taken advantage of the increasing of social media accessing customer in the recent years, so that, they have built the online environment on social media to communicate with more customers including existing and new potential customers. In addition, due to the typical type products, banking products always are considered as boring finance information with many details, however, banks use social media to assist them to engage banking products to customers through online community. Banks believe that through the viral contents, customer interactions or social media influencers would affect to customer perception quicker than using only conventional marketing.

As the similarity with other industries, social media plays an important role in lowering cost and raising their presence on online environment. Hence, employing appropriate social media platforms has provided the engaging contents to connect customers with banks. It supports banks to enhance customer experience and create more business opportunities. The engaging on social media channels with creative contents and dealing with customer complaints on social media brought more benefits to banks. Therefore, banks enable to maintain the relationship between banks and customers and reach to customer expectation.

Additionally, since the digital bank has been developed, the young generation tends to prefer using social media to communicate with each other. They also like to update banking activities with a high technology and conveniences, therefore, social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn are prioritized to become places to update information as well as look for new trending banking products.

In another aspect, banking services is a typical product which need to provide trustfulness and financial knowledge to customers. Social media enable work as the online

environment to spread over the useful financial information and build the trust from banks and experiences from their existing loyal customers. Therefore, banks take advantage of social media to improve brand equity (Micti and Kapoulas, 2012).

Indeed, in comparison with other channels such as website, call center, email marketing, social media supports banks to understand their customer needs and figure out the solution in the fastest way. By applying social media, banks can analyze and understand customer's preferences, needs and even their emotion. As stated in that investigation, products and services will be designed to meet their customer needs and expectations (Rezayat, 2017).

Apart from benefits of social media in banking industry, there still remain some of challenges which banks has to face when using social media for their activities. In the open online environment, confidential and private information of customer such as account number, credit card number are easily leaked through social media via customer interaction. Therefore, bank reputation would be affected if customers were stolen money or indirectly impact on their personal life. Besides, the security and privacy of social media are also considered as the challenges for a typical industry as banking and finance, many customer queries are not able to instantly solve when banks use social media platform as another customer service. Banks need to protect their customers, hence, they do not allow customer make payment, bank transfer or balance checking on social media. Because social media compliance is still not enough to secure the confidential customer information.

1.2.2. Social media impacts on consumer behavior in banking industry

The advantages of social media application in banking sector brought the effective outcomes towards consumer behavior. Even though the common operation of online banking services such as Internet banking and mobile banking support customers to associate with banks to experience and utilize banking service in the convenient way, it still remains the limitation considering the interaction between customers and banks. In order to understand customer needs and their preferences, banks still need an another platform to obtain more interaction with customer. Moreover, customer retention are also one of the purposes for applying social media in bank's strategy. It is very important in banking operation, existing customers contribute more profit to compared with the new customers because of product cross selling.

In fact, understanding consumer behavior are always a background to develop many banking products strategy as well as reinforce customer retention. Therefore, social media has become a sharp weapon to support banks in observing them on social media. By utilizing social media, consumer will behave their satisfaction or dissatisfaction on social media towards banking products and also update trends on different social media platform. Especially, in the era of smartphones and smart devices, young generation tends to access social media platform to communicate with each other more than using other channels. Customers easily to express their experiences and preferences towards a specific banking product. Therefore, social media has become a focus channel for bank to expand to young generation customers as well as understand the current customer needs. On the other hand, using social media platforms assists banks to promptly interact with customers to improve their service.

The impact of social media on consumer behaviors in banking industry is not only customer reaction towards viral contents or customer interaction on social media, it also their attitude towards social media influencers. The effects of influencers on social media has a strong impact on customer decision making. Influencers supports bank to promote and spread their products information on social media. Many banks hire personal experts who have high follower on social media to express their experiences and financial knowledge to social media users. This is the most convenient way for fast sharing information and also build the trust to customer.

1.3. Motivation of the Research

Recently, despite the extensive integration of social media into daily life and its impact across various industries, there has been limited research on its influence within specific sectors like banking, particularly in developing countries. This study aims to fill that gap by examining the impact of social media on consumer behavior in the banking industry. It will identify key elements that create viral content and the factors that attract customers to banking services through social media. Additionally, the research will explore how banks use social media as a strategic tool to promote their products and enhance brand awareness. This study will focus on how social media interactions influence consumer perception and their decisions in selecting banking services.

The application of social media in the banking industry signifies a shift in customer

behavior towards digital access to banking products and services. This shift presents valuable opportunities for banks to gain insights from social media data, which can be leveraged to enhance their marketing strategies. By investigating the effectiveness of social media in these strategies, the research will demonstrate how social media contributes to increasing customer retention, enhancing customer loyalty, and driving competitive advantage.

The findings of this research will highlight how social media marketing supports banks in transitioning from merely a social engagement tool to a crucial solution for fostering strong customer relationships. The study will show the advantages of social media in helping banks achieve targeted marketing, effective advertising, regulatory compliance, superior customer service, and an improved user experience. The research will focus on the Vietnamese banking industry, where the rise of social media platform like Facebook, Instagram and YouTube has become instrumental in building relationships between banks and their potential customers. Many local banks utilize social media to update their services and products, as well as to promote brand awareness and engage with their audience.

1.4. Overview and social media influences in Vietnam banking industry

Since the social media has been emerged in over the world as well as the developing of smartphones and smart devices, social media has become more essential in the daily life of most Vietnamese people. The numbers of social media users in Vietnam has been reached into the top of countries with highest social media users. In 2021, with the social media around 72 million, Vietnam became the 2nd country of social media users in Southeast Asia. Especially, Facebook are the leading social media platform in Vietnam, YouTube and Instagram are the following popular platforms. Currently, social media platforms in Vietnam are not only for connecting people, these networks also provide knowledge, information, brand communication and marketplace for many brands. However, banking is a typical finance industry where customer information and financial products are considered to be more confidential, therefore, social media platforms in Vietnam mainly work with their original functions such as advertising, customer services and raising brand awareness.

Figure 1: Data of Internet users and social media users in Vietnam

Sourced by: WeAresocial and Hootsuite (2021)

Vietnamese banking system has been managed and controlled by State bank of Vietnam. Those activities such as issuing currency, managing money and creating monetary policies and laws on banking systems has been managed by State bank of Vietnam. There are 5 state owned commercial banks, 34 joints stock banks, and more than 35 branch offices of foreign banks and representative banks and they are working under Vietnamese banking law controlled by State bank of Vietnam. The leading banks of Vietnam are Vietcombank, Agribank, BIDV, Vietinbank and Techcombank. Besides, other foreign banks in Vietnam are HSCB, ANZ and Citibanks are also considered as the popular banks in Vietnam (vietnamonline, 2021).

Figure 2: Assets in Vietnam's banking sector

Sourced by: hanoitimes.vn (2022)

In the recent years, due to the development of digital banking and technological adaption, instead of branch based expansion, Vietnamese banks focus more on improving smart applications and enhancing online services like social media or mobile apps. As per the rate of people using social media, mobile and internet in Vietnam in 2021, Vietnamese banking has many potential conditions for developing social media to become functional marketing tool. Along with the current digital banking transformation, social media improvement will support Vietnam's banking sector to be more competitive and expand banking products/services to more people.

1.5. Rationale for the choice of Vietnam banking industry

In Vietnam, social media has not traditionally been a primary focus for the banking sector, resulting in limited research on its application within this industry. However, as social media has developed in Vietnam, many banks have started. To leverage it for their marketing strategies. Vietnam is an emerging market in Southeast Asia, largely due to its youthful demographic, which presents numerous opportunities for business investment. The younger population is particularly significant for the banking sector, as they are quick to adopt new technologies, making them potential customers for digital banking services.

In order to attract and retain these customers, Vietnamese banks are increasingly adopting digital marketing strategies, with social media marketing being a key component.

Despite its recent development, social media marketing is not yet widely applied in many commercial banks in Vietnam. However, with the ongoing digital transformation and the rise of digital payments, social media is expected to become an increasingly valuable tool for banks. Specifically, influencer marketing, which has been successfully utilized by many businesses and brands in Vietnam, is set to become a crucial strategy for banks using social media. Some Vietnamese banks have already started using influencers to introduce new banking products to consumers. There are numerous marketing activities that influencers can effectively perform on social media platforms to achieve more impactful outcomes for banks.

Overall, as social media continues to grow in Vietnam, it will play a critical role in helping banks create targeted promotion campaigns and deliver their products to a wider audience, ultimately enhancing their marketing strategies and customer engagement.

1.6. Aim of the research

The overall objective of this study is to emphasize the importance of social media marketing in the banking industry. Specifically, it aims to assess the extent of social media's impact on consumer behavior, both generally and within the banking sector. Literature indicates that the expansion of social media significantly contributes to a bank's marketing strategy by providing insights into consumer behavior. However, social media also presents challenges that can hinder the deployment of marketing strategies. This study anticipates that banks will successfully apply social media to analyze consumer behavior, thereby facilitating customer acquisition and retention. The research findings were obtained through quantitative analysis of data collected from Vietnamese social media users, complemented by thematic analysis to capture participants' views and experiences regarding the impact of social media on the banking industry. In order to reach the aim to examine the impact of social media on consumer behavior in the banking industry, the following research questions have been formulated for investigating and answering:

Research question:

1. How does social media contribute to the banking industry?
2. How do consumers behave towards banking services on social media?

3. What are benefits and challenges of social media for banks?

Research objective:

1. To explore the contribution of social media on banking industry in a developing country (Vietnam).
2. To examine the consumer attitudes towards the application of social media marketing.
3. To evaluate the opportunities and challenges of the viral marketing in social media toward consumer behavior in banking industry.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The purpose of this chapter is to describe and expand the theoretical framework for this research. The main developments of theoretical background and foundation of this research focus on the impacts of social media on consumer behavior. This chapter critically reviews previous studies concerning social media by different scholars. Therefore, this chapter will discuss all the factors which have significantly contributed to social media in marketing strategies in the banking sector.

Social media has been studied in many different pieces of research with various perspectives. Many industries utilized social media to create a new environment for their marketing strategy. The literature review of this chapter will provide an overview of the influence of social media in general. Following that, the literature on the issues of understanding how social media impacts consumer perception and decision-making in the

banking sector will be reviewed particularly in this research. Finally, the investigated conceptual framework will be introduced and followed by appropriate research hypotheses in this chapter.

2.1. Introduction

At the very beginning, social media was developed from communication technologies, and it involves in the Web 1.0 evolution. Significant developments of technologies have supported the online social community. The technologies contributed the potential change to the way people communicate with each other and the environment of people interaction (Feldmann, 2007). Based on the changing of technologies, the concept of social media has been introduced with a related term of Web 2.0 definition, which is considered as the platform for social media evolution. The evolution of Web 2.0 created social media technologies with various features that attract billions of Internet users to concern. Moreover, it generates a new online communication place to social connectivity (Page and Pitt, 2012). Along with the social media evolution and its development, many businesses take advantage of social media to engage with consumers. They acknowledge the importance of this emerging technology in their business strategy. Social media provides opportunities to maintain the relationship with their customers, and it also becomes the online social environment to support businesses to acquire potential customers. Therefore, in order to exploit the concept of social media in business strategy, this chapter will initially review the existing studies which relates to social media in business. The main factors that have led to the impacts of social media on businesses and consumer behavior will be discussed through the development of literature reviews. Furthermore, the adoption of social media in the banking sector in general and in the Vietnam banking sector in particular to approach and satisfy consumers and enhance their brand awareness will be the main focus of the research. This literature review will be started with the basic concepts of social media and the technologies development foundation to form the social media environment. It will be followed by the knowledge of social media that has been discussed and examined throughout the period of research. Additionally, the previous studies will review the application of social media in business strategy to reach out to consumers and meet consumer satisfaction. Especially, this chapter will focus on updating more informative research in terms of consumer behavior and expectation in purchasing products or services through social media. By adopting social media to create a

new channel for reaching out to consumers, the existing opportunities and challenges will be determined by discussions from different studies.

2.2. Web Evolution and social media establishment.

2.2.1. Web evolution

Beginning with the initial web 1.0 (world wide web), this is the first generation of the web, which is the foundation to evolve technologies. Based on the limitation of Web 1.0 interaction and web contribution, Web 2.0 has been released to open a new generation of technology (Aghaei et al., 2012). This is a new stage of evolution in terms of online social networks. The functionalities of the new Internet web base allow Internet users to create, share content and communicate with each other (Everson et al., 2013). This web 2.0 term was first released in 2004 as a platform in which the “World wide web” is used by end-users, and the content is created and shared by all users in a collaborative way (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). With the new era of online marketing using Web 2.0, O’Reilly (2005) stated that some principles are involved in business and their marketing strategy while applying Web 2.0 to enhance business activities. Businesses intended to create the applications and the networking where users are able to freely access, interact with business and friendly interface; moreover, this networking supports them to customize and deploy their promotion. The next principle is to create an online environment to support businesses in terms of engaging with users/consumers via their feedback and their interaction. On the other hand, businesses are able to respond to customers promptly regarding their needs and preferences. The last principle, according to Constantinides and Fountain (2008), businesses believe that the new online social environment would focus on improving customer databases, customizing promotions through an interactive online social communication channel. Based on these principles, Constantinides and Fountain (2008) claimed that the new online social environment had been developed under the term Web 2.0, and it created interactive online communication between businesses and their customers. In another research, many communication platforms or marketing tools were developed under Web 2.0 in which interactive environment and online content sharing based on user experiences have been significantly expanded to improve their online marketing (Cooke, 2008 and Pannunzio, 2008). From the enterprise’s perspective, according to Bernal (2010), web 2.0 is considered as an enabling technology that completely supports enterprises and brands to approach and provide services to consumers

in an exciting way. He also defines web 2.0 as a new model that enables users to participate, interact and contribute instead of web 1.0 that basically was used on delivering products to users. Based on web 2.0, users can create and edit contents, tags, and comments that provide other participants new information, experiences, and significant data in the community. Various tools and applications have been created to generate online social networking where users enable to share content or effortlessly spread information on social networks (Grant, 2009). As a consequence of the variety of tools developed under Web 2.0, social media has been incorporated with Web 2.0 which contributes to the marketing of a business as a new communication channel and platform. Using social media as an online social channel to expand marketing activities, businesses or brands provide supportive networking with interactive communication environments to users and their existing customers (Pannunzio, 2008). The main initial technologies of Web 2.0 have been released as also known as social media such as Blogs, Really Simple Syndication (RSS), Wikis, Online social networks and Forums. The main function of these technologies is to open a website where users enable to create the content by themselves in several ways. Blogs are where people contribute the content creation and their comments and discussions of any topics or posts. RSS is used to update any blogs and websites that users are concerning. Wikis are websites where users enable to edit and amend information based on the history and knowledge of contributors. Online social networks are introduced with many social media platforms such Facebook, LinkedIn, My Spaces and even later on YouTube can be considered as social media platforms where users enable to create their own personal pages for content creation, information sharing and spreading, videos and images creating, information exchange within networks. This is the background technology for social media development in business (Constantinides and Fountain, 2008). Following the evolution of Web 2.0, the development of technology since 2010 until now has mentioned Web 3.0 and Web 4.0, however, these kinds of technology evolutions mainly support social media innovation. For instance, with the development of Web 3.0, technologies based on Web 3.0 will target to link data set with more functionalities (Aghaei et al., 2012). Moreover, according to Garrigos-Simon et al., (2012), Web 3.0 refers to semantic web technologies which enhanced the development of social networks, created new tools and are more competitive for businesses. The most important innovation in Web 3.0 is to build a new environment of social networks. Businesses took advantage of this as an essential tool to

link their consumers with businesses. It plays an important role in the marketing of a business for creating, influencing and promoting products and services (Garrigos-Simon et al., 2012). Therefore, social media is basically based on Web 2.0 technologies which have been empowerment to develop further in the future.

2.2.2. Social media establishment

Social media has proven to be a powerful tool since its inception, allowing content creation on websites without relying on software experts or web managers. Social media enables users to compose, create, edit, comment, and publish content across networks (Kozinets, 2009; Pannunzio, 2008). It has created an online environment that meets people's needs and preferences without requiring knowledge of computer or software programming. Users can easily design their personal pages, aggregate online information, and share or create their own content independently (Cooke, 2008). This shift in the internet landscape allows individuals to control the information online rather than relying on web controllers (Hardey, 2009). Consequently, Web 2.0 and social media have established new values and factors for online communication, enhancing the variety of social interactions within the online environment (Comley & Beaumont, 2011).

Dynamic discussions and content contributions, such as news or information, are more prevalent on social media, creating a vibrant and dynamic virtual environment (Cooke, 2008). The evolution of Web 2.0 and social media technologies has not only impacted social interactions but also provided businesses with powerful tool to enhance their marketing strategies and satisfy customers in the digital era (Ewing et al., 2008). Businesses leverage this technology to build a social environment for their customers, facilitating the delivery of product or service information an understanding customer needs through social interaction. However, this shift has also posed challenges for businesses, as they must adapt to the rapid spread of information online and select appropriate social media channels to promote and deploy their products and services effectively (Hardey, 2009).

The evolution of Web 2.0 and social media has significantly transformed the marketing field for businesses. Interactions on social media occur in various forms, from customer – to – customer to customer – to business. Information about products and services is no longer solely controlled by businesses and brands; customers also contribute

by sharing and spreading content on social media (Pannunzio, 2008). According to Kozinets (2009), social media technology based on Web 2.0 development provides a convenient tool to change consumer behavior towards products or services. It opens channels for consumers to express their opinions, experiences, and attitudes about products, services, or brands in an online community. This encourages users to share personal information, needs, and preferences, helping businesses understand customer expectations and enhance their customer database.

The evolution of the web has created more opportunities for businesses and marketers to influence consumer decision – making. Social media builds relevant online communities where consumer opinions and experiences impact each other, significantly influencing purchasing decisions. Businesses and brands that effectively utilize social media gain powerful insights for targeted marketing purposes (Beer, 2008). Additionally, marketing factors such as online branding, brand awareness, and online consumer behavior are expanding on social media as new online channels emerge (Pannunzio, 2008).

Apart from the advantages of web evolution with social media, Kozinets (2009) argued that it has remained some ethical issues regarding transparency of the information on social media and Web 2.0. Social media or Web 2.0 has been constructed to obtain both contributions from consumers and businesses rather than one side. Therefore, posted products/services information on these platforms need to be driven the truthfulness. By using social media, consumers easily check and verify the product's information through content sharing and interacting within their online communities. Many businesses and brands have considered online information and campaign managing as additional challenges in their marketing communication with respect to social media (Cooke, 2008). Furthermore, the diversity of social media or web 2.0 technologies also give significant challenges for businesses in terms of maintaining both relevant positive and negative information from users about their products and services (Comley, 2008). However, at the very stage of establishing social media as a new convenient tool for marketing communication, social media has still brought positive outcomes and effectiveness for businesses. Many businesses have caught social media trends to adopt in their marketing strategy regardless of remaining issues which would be improved in applying process (Stone, 2009).

2.3. Social media

Establishing social media created an innovative tool which supports businesses and brands to improve the engagement to their customer and being more flexible in interaction activities (Wollan et al., 2011). Indeed, the relationship between businesses and their customers has been significantly enhanced through the interactivity of businesses on social media. Businesses have been beneficial social media to influence consumer purchasing behavior (Gao and Feng, 2016). In another study of Chang et al., (2015), social media platforms have been used basically to promote brand awareness, thus, it leads to improving consumer purchasing intentions. By utilizing social media marketing in promoting products or services, it naturally considers social media platforms as influential communication channels. For instance, in order to engage new potential customers to a positive purchase intention, businesses or brands can take advantage of existing customer's influences on social media. These existing customers intentionally encourage others by interaction activities or sharing their experiences in their online social media. Hence, the products/services information has been spread over in customer's friend base.

Social media provided a new online environment for users which has been changed the purchasing manner. Businesses utilize the emergence of social media to become online channels along with their main website, thus, it naturally transforms Internet users to become target customers (Napoli, 2011). The role of social media in recent years seriously change the approach of communication between businesses/marketers and customers. The innovation of social media evolved the acquiring of potential customers, retaining existing customers and diversifying the communication. Furthermore, the customer decision-making process and their products/service evaluation have been remarkably influenced by the information society. Therefore, the contribution of social media has been importantly examined in business strategy or marketing communication of businesses (Chu and Kim, 2011). Social media can be adopted by any type of business for a diversity of purposes. There are many potential opportunities for businesses in approaching their target customers and improving brand awareness by applying social media such as content marketing, customer support, social cross-selling (Strauss, 2016). In another context, according to Ioanas and Stoica (2014), in order to support businesses to enhance their communication and expand social networking, social media plays as a tool to transform consumers, their society and their interests into a virtual community. By this movement, social media

generate digital platforms where users have the same interests or purchasing purposes will be connected to each other and being gathered in the same online community. Indeed, those social networking sites as known as social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and other blogs are emerged to connect a huge amount of Internet users who have similar interests, hobbies, points of view or purchasing purposes. Businesses based on these platforms approach more customer base as well as improve their networking and communication. In the facts, there are three typical social media platforms that many businesses and users consider as a typical leading social media platform to facilitate customer connectivity and effortlessly enhance their communication. They are Facebook, YouTube and Twitter (Ioanas and Stoica, 2014), other platforms like Instagrams will be developed later on but also based on the sharing technologies as Facebook. Therefore, the literature review will be focused only on three main typical social media platforms.

Figure 3: Global social media users using social media platforms over 2 years (2011)

2.3.1. Facebook:

Facebook was launched in 2004 as the social networking site and become to dominant social media platform. Since recent years, Facebook focused on developing programmes to create the marketing solutions for businesses. According to Conlin (2020), with more than 2.7 billion Facebook users, Facebook is a largest social network where can bring more benefits for businesses and users. Hence, Facebook has created integration tools to businesses. With initial goal is to connect people, Facebook developed to allow businesses and brands build an online environment with a credible community where businesses

enable to determine their customer profiles. This subsequently led to the trustfulness of any social media page. According to Moth (2012), Facebook contributed analysis tool to support businesses can control their Facebook page including information of their follower demographic, their activity frequency and their intentions towards business Facebook page, thus, it significantly assists businesses to analyze these factors and match their business strategy. With the development of Facebook, many solutions have been provided to businesses from Facebook. For instance, Facebook ads is an effective solution that develop advanced campaign strategies (Newberry, 2021).

2.3.2. YouTube:

YouTube initially was an entertainment social media platform where YouTube users freely to share, post and watch videos. This platform was found in 2005, it facilitated businesses to diversify their media content in communication. The social relationships between users and YouTube channel's host has been maintained through subscription service, this is based on videos which has been watched on YouTube (Lange, 2007). In the business perspective, businesses were attracted by the diversity of YouTube platform where they enable to utilize this for advertising instead of traditional advertising media channels with the similar marketing cost (Senadherra et al., 2011). By following a specific business YouTube channel, users naturally become their potential customers and participate in a community. This created an opportunity for businesses to obtain customer feedback regarding the video content, this is the direct way to engage to customer audience (Senadheera et al., 2011). In recent years, due to ownership between Google and YouTube, businesses have more chances to improving their reputation on Google search by utilizing YouTube for their businesses. This is a particular tool to maximize business presence online. Furthermore, in order to expand customer base, YouTube ads is one of the inconvenient advertising tool. With a huge amount of audience watching YouTube videos every day, gaining more customers through YouTube is one of the effective strategy for any businesses (Salamader, 2020)

2.3.3. Twitter:

Twitter has been released in 2006 and plays a role as a micro blogging service. The term of "participatory or citizen journalism" has strongly involve to Twitter activities. Twitter has been considered as a place to connect people to pass information and based on

the important share information, it brings people closer (Twitter, 2012). It supports a quick information exchange within social (Bieller, 2009). Twitter was created with purpose of supporting people to share ideas and spread information without barriers. From the business perspective, every Tweets on Twitter are valuable sources from customer insight. On another hand, based on the quick information on Twitter, Twitter allows an instant conversation between businesses and their audience on every topics or business Tweets. The main advantage of Twitter has been taken in recent years is to deliver customer support and gather their feedback. It can say this platform easily to make customer reach out brands and brands enable to provide very quick customer care and market research medium (Zote, 2020).

2.4. Social media in business:

Hollensen (2015) stated that, regarding the customer relationship management (CRM), social media is convenient tool for any businesses which contributes important function to be more competitive in the market. In a business, CRM system plays a vital role to determine the strong relationship between customers and what business delivers to them. CRM has concentrated to connecting customer's need and preferences to products/services, therefore businesses will manage the relationship by providing appropriate products, privileges and ultimate services to customers (Safko, 2010). Based on that, social media supports businesses in acquiring more successful and valuable in relationship with customers. In other words, the role of social media in CRM is to assist businesses in maintaining existing customers and approaching more potential customers. In the same context, social media relating to customer relationship management has been attributed as the elemental approach to improve the customer relationship strengths. By utilizing social network site such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, businesses increase the customer relationship with prompt responses, instant customer care towards their queries on social media platform (Chou and Wang, 2014). Furthermore, improving customer relationship will gain more competitive advantage in the marketing, thus, businesses employ social media as a sharp weapon to strengthen their positions in the market.

In respect of marketing field in businesses and brands, the role of social media has been taken advantage of as the main concentrated tool. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram or even YouTube are practical social networks for promoting

products and services. These platforms generated analytic tools to support business to analyze customer data base, moreover, the engagement between customers and businesses are tracked in detail including tracking traffics of promotion campaigns, customer penetration, and progress of all campaigns (Strauss, 2016). Understanding the benefits of social media towards business activities in marketing as well as in order to expand the social networking and spread over products/services over, many businesses convey their partners including supplier, employees, customers and their associates though social media (Aeker et al., 2008). Social media marketing was operated depending on the business's marketing objectives and purposes. Every business has the own marketing strategies to reach the objective, therefore choosing appropriate social media platform and social media tools is crucial to meet their target. Although some of the function on social media such as share, like, repost, retweet always being beneficial for brands and businesses, obtaining the marketing objective and following the marketing strategic goal are more vital in every social media post and activities. In other words, brands always desire their social media content on all platforms need to be reached the brand awareness goal and improve consumer purchasing behavior (Balakrishnan et al. , 2014). Therefore, in another context regarding delivery content and activities of product information on social media, Cho (2014) claimed that the vital features of social media marketing have been provided to businesses which are the interaction between customer to business and customer to customer. Businesses utilize social media networking to deliver the product/service impression to customer and to create the influence on consumer purchasing behavior regardless of business size. At the same time, social media take into account the online social community, customer also access social networking sites for communicating, connecting, updating, searching and even purchasing. Therefore, it can be demonstrated that utilizing social media as marketing tools would bring the effective connection and outcome to businesses and this is the adequate marketing strategic tool (Chou and Wang, 2014). Along with the conventional marketing or even other digital marketing strategies, delivering traffic is one of important factors in social media marketing. This is the key factor to approach more potential customers and expand their networks. Products/services information has been updated, shared and spread over on social media, moreover it directly links to main websites (for instance, through landing pages). Hence, it has driven more traffic to the business and deliver more potential customers to the business. The more traffic

causes the more influences on consumer buying decision (Lamberton and Stephen, 2016).

In order to evaluate the important role of social media in marketing, the knowledge of the social media platform categories need to be considered. Additionally, the adoption of social media in customer personal use need to be investigated along with the engagement of businesses and social media marketing also has to be identified (Perdue, 2010). Social media marketing has increasingly developed to be one of the online marketing tools in business strategy. Social media marketing has become more common in online marketing field due to the advantage of social media platform also known as social network sites. It generated the rapid growth of social media marketing in businesses (Solis, 2010). The key factors for the development of social media marketing is the increase of social media platform user, it contributes more potential customer in any business marketing strategies. Furthermore, it promotes the high rate of communication between brands, businesses and customers. Businesses employs social media to implement social media marketing which also support their business structure (Dumitriu et al., 2019). Therefore, key factor of understanding how social media marketing play important role to success of online marketing activities need to be examined in business strategy (Marzuki et al., 2014). According to Eagleman (2013), the application of social media and utilizing social media platforms enhance the marketing communication technique. Businesses also use social media marketing as the extension of conventional marketing to achieve the strategic goals. Social media platforms have been employ by businesses to deploy marketing activities. In social media marketing, it supports to expand the product information and corporates with different parties on social media platforms to create the interactions. The social media users play the roles as business stakeholders and they assist businesses to intentionally or purposely share and discuss the contents about the product information (Kietzmann et al., 2011). By gathering the contents discussed and commented by customers on social media platforms, consumer purchasing behavior will be predicted and evaluated to meet customer needs and preferences, moreover it supports businesses to have an adequate insight towards creating marketing contents on social media and planning the effective marketing strategies in the future (Vries et al., 2012). Furthermore, in order to build the customer loyalty and gain more potential customers, improving social media marketing in any marketing strategy is core value to raise brand awareness (Michaelidou et al., 2011). In the aspect of approaching potential customers, businesses utilize social media marketing to build

friendly online environment, thus people can interact with each other and engage with products/services information. More marketing strategies need to be planned towards social media to reach out more potential customers and enhance business performance (Eltayib et al., 2018). Regarding to strategic social media marketing, a user centric strategic plan is developed, business investigate and identify customer needs and their interests via customer interaction on social media platforms. Based on that, businesses enable being more competitive in the market and more capable to approach more target customers (Coleman et al., 2012). Social media marketing also enhances marketing goals and sale targets of any business. Products and services are directly offered to customer on the virtual environment on social media platforms along with main websites (Eagleman, 2013). Pentina and Koh (2012) summarized that in order to have a success marketing plan and effective strategies, businesses must develop and improve social media marketing with strategic insight. Additionally, selecting appropriate social media platforms is vital marketing decision to expand business further.

Social media platforms play a crucial role to support businesses to reach their objective while implementing social media marketing. Social media platforms are considered as the marketing materials and marketing channels where facilitate businesses to raise their brand awareness and approach the target customers. Those social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter are particular equipment for business to provide product/service information by multiple approaches and thus customers enable to capture products to certain extent. Through social media platforms, businesses or brands are able to understand customer needs and interests without contacting directly to customer, they can observe their personal social media page, their interaction on business social media pages, hence, brands can identify customer need and their behavior (Pentina et al., 2012). In the recent study by Kuligowski (2021), each social media platform brings different fits to business objective, so by investing features of social media platform will support businesses to reach their goals. For instance, Facebook with high active user will provide business effective advertising tools and powerful analytics, whereas Instagram targets to businesses who desire to be more visuals in their marketing contents. Twitter is instant platform where business enable to impress customers by short updates. There are more leading businesses and companies in the world using Twitter to expand their network to compare with small business. YouTube is video sharing platform where business can easily

influence customers by creative videos and it is the key factor when YouTube is linked with Google, so business enable to improve their ranking on Google search and enhance their brand awareness everywhere. Furthermore, Tiktok and LinkedIn is also considered in the social media marketing of businesses, however, they are targeting in specific aspects such as landing job, recruitment in LinkedIn and still on the way to discover by Generation Z with Tiktok. Therefore, this context is to mention the purposes of each social media platforms affect to marketing decision in choosing the adequate social media platform.

2.5. Use of social media in different industries:

There many companies and businesses used social media to marketing strategy. According to Vasudevan and Kumar (2018), some technology companies as Canon and HP operated their activities on social media platform such as LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter. Promotion activities were posted and focus on product and brand centric. Number of shares was proved the effectiveness of social media platform. It was investigated that using social media improves customer relationships, pushes sales and raises brand awareness. Moreover, social media provided companies a recruiting tool (LinkedIn) and searching tool (Facebook and Twitter) to diversify business activities. Bernard (2016) investigated that many business activities can be enhanced by employing social media. For instance, IBM company provided customer service after sale, targeted to new potential customer to gain sales leads, improve company reputation on social media platform. In another industry, device companies normally focus on innovation factors of products. Social media can be used to connect to stakeholders or partners, it calls business to business (B2B). In this case, social media supports to gather businesses globally. Katona and Sarvary (2014) states the case study of a logistic company Maersk (one of the large shipping company), they launched integrating operation on social media for their marketing strategy. In the sale sectors, the advantage of social media has been investigated as a social selling tools, salespeople utilized social media as the relationship oriented applications for their selling purposes and after sale follow up. Salespeople enable to improve customer service after sale and keep contacting to maintain relationship with customers (Moore et al., 2015). In another context, Muller et al., (2013) stated that in the automotive market, social media has been operated between dealers and buyers, moreover, social media engagement were very popular to be used by manufactures and dealers. For instance, Facebook are the most online environment to update product information. One of the most common industry is fashion

which using social media the most in their marketing strategies. The main functions of social media in this industry is to increase customer loyalty and trust, enhance brand reputation, improve people engagement and facilitate product information updating (Vukanovic, 2013). Finally, banking sector is the most considered regarding social media application due to the main objective of this research. According to Parusheva (2019), banks utilize social media to facilitate the customer queries and investigate their needs and complaints in a prompt and effective way. Some of the bank even can use social media for transactional banking. Via social media personal page of customers, banks offered customer to make standard transactions. They claimed that it is quite convenient and quick way. However, Paurusheva (2019) also stated that still many banks refuse this transactional social media banking model due to security issues. Therefore, in banking perspective, by utilizing social media, they mainly concentrated on marketing tool, communication channel, customer services rather than transactional social media.

2.6. Links of social media and consumer behavior

2.6.1. Impacts of social media on consumer purchase intention:

In term of purchase intention, according to Sharma et al., (2021), it is the combination of customer preferences and purchase opportunities. Those factors such as consumer behavior, consumer perception and consumer attitudes will be crucial factors to impact on purchase intention. Moreover, it supports to evaluate the products that they want to purchase. On the other words, purchase intention of customer toward products has been measured by their attitudes and interests for a brand or a product. Therefore, if customer have the optimistic and positive attitude for a product, it will definitely push the purchase intention. Focusing on consumer attitude and their perception is the imperative for any business and brand, it supports to encourage the consumer intention and also affects to product/service evaluation in the future. In order to understand consumer attitude and improve their perception towards brands or products, businesses build the customer brand relationship in both sides communication through social media. A strong relationship has been created by a high interactivities between brand and customers. Hence, social media activities generated a heathy exchange with various contents on social media platforms/networks to attract customers and give a stable association to customers.

Basically, social media mechanism has been operated within businesses which as

classified into some different aspect such as entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization and spreading over (word of mouth). These aspects directly impact on business activities such as brand awareness, brand loyalty. Following by these, consumer purchase intention has been influenced by the social media contribution in business. In other words, for instance, existing customers become brand ambassador and influence to other potential customers by their experiences, their reviews on social media platform by interaction or spreading over activities. Thus, purchase intention completely are improved by these customer reviews. According to Pham and Gammoh (2015), Facebook, Twitter and YouTube has been recently become common social media platforms where businesses or brand can take advantage to strengthen relationship with customers and importantly contribute as two-way communication. Brands or businesses apply social media marketing on this kind of platforms to increase brand's value-added which relates to purchase intention. Many activities of businesses have been operated based on social media to boost purchases intention such as brand improvement, relationship management, promotion campaigns. Indeed, social media has positive impacts on purchase intention when application of social media platforms improve consumer attitude towards the brand. Jaring and Back (2017) pointed that the good communication between loyal customers and brand on social media enable to create the good attitude, thus it positively impacts on their purchasing intention. For instance, the good communication can be described through advertising contents or attracting promotion campaigns on social media. By the study of Sharma et al., (2021), the association of social media marketing activities and consumer purchasing intention was very strong when the activities on social media platforms like Facebook made customers feel the readiness to purchase products/services. Brands utilized social media in their practical implementation to enhance consumer purchase intention, based on that it will create leads by driving customer into actual purchases.

In another context, according to Suprpto et al., (2020), purchase intention has been increased by advertising contents social media. The more attractive of content will lead the higher consumer purchase intention. Social media platform such as Facebook, Instagram or YouTube provide a diversity of social advertising to brands and businesses. It can be attractive video and images with purposive contents to approach customers. Consumer purchase intentions has been stimulated by the power of social advertisements on social media platforms. The high visual advertisements influence on customer browsing activities

on social media and directly impress customer attention. It easily makes customer to be more considered to buy products, hence consumer purchase intention will be increased. In another aspect, because consumer perception is considered as one of influenced factors to consumer purchase intention, hence visual advertisement on social media can intentionally establish consumer perception everywhere. All the attracted advertisements can be intentionally shared or posted by social media users or they can be created by brands, it still enables to enhance consumer purchase intentions on specific products (Wang et al, 2017). Besides, with the supportive analytic programs of social media platforms, through the customer attention of advertisement and their interaction on that, brands enable to know customer preferences or their hobbies. Based on that analysis, brands or businesses will have other appropriate strategies to increase marketing activities so it leads to increase consumer purchase intention like a cycle. Therefore, consumer purchase intention was influenced by many aspects and activities of social media. It also depends on how brands and businesses adopt social media to trigger consumer purchase intention.

2.6.2. Impacts of social media on consumer decision making:

The rapid development of social media has driven the customer not only use social network to buy products or services but also to support their decision making. Therefore, beginning with Internet and social media environment, consumer decision making behaviour was significantly influenced by few factors such as supporting the considering behaviour of customer when they desire to purchase products or services, maximising the product information searching and evaluating process, enhancing activities of the after purchasing process.

Due to the digital and social media evolution and development of online communities, customer consideration process has been changed over the time. In conventional marketing, customer consideration towards any products/services based on brand's marketing materials. Product information has been actively updated and advertised from brands, hence, customer evaluation would be intentionally depended on what brands built on their marketing channels. However, in social media era, customers no longer to depend on the marketing information or marketing materials of brands to consider their needs and preferences. It totally changes customer manner to collect information from other sources such as collecting information from social networks, or interacting within social

media platforms. Therefore, instead of only considering, social media assist customers also enable to evaluate production information, brand information and even judge their reputation before deciding to purchase anything (Hudson et al., 2015).

Regarding to searching and evaluating in pre-purchasing in consumer decision making behaviour, customers access social media to look for products and information from many sources. Those sources can be acquaintances, friends on social networks, or can be useful opinions and experiences of existing customers about products/services, possibly being attracted by various social media contents, or can be reviews and experiences from social media influencers (Hudson et al., 2015). Therefore, customer evaluation of a specific product would be more flexible and have various perspectives based on social media, whereas, conventional marketing of brands can be less objective view. Understanding this influence, many businesses employs social media as the practical tools in sales and marketing strategies. Businesses desire to attract customers in every stage of customer decision making process. Regarding the stage of evaluation products while searching product information, businesses investigated customer interactions and conversations on social media to figure out what they prefer and their demand towards a particular product or service. (Maechler et al., 2016).

The after purchasing stage is also very important because it directly relates to customer services and influences to new potential customer approaching in the future. Social media platform is an online environment where customer might express their experiences and opinions towards purchased products/services. This information definitely impact on other consumer decision making, therefore it will affect to business marketing strategies and objectives. Hence, businesses tend to build strategies which can resolve consumer behaviour on social media based on post purchasing activities. Businesses can observe and analyse customer comments, shares on social media including positive and negative opinions. It led businesses to provide instant customer care services, improve about their products/services and even obtain insight about their customer demand and preferences. Having an in depth understanding about customer needs and their perspective toward a product will literately support a business/brand to enhance the quality of product/service, have better performance and also boost their competitive strengths in the market.

In comparison with traditional marketing, social media in digital marketing significantly contribute to change the consumer decision making process. Instead of passive receiving information from brand's marketing campaigns, customers are more proactive to search about product information from various sources on social media. Additionally, instead of limitation of expressing their experiences and opinions about purchased products/services, customers no longer just share it to only their friends and family around them or give feedback to brands, by using social media, customers enable to spread over and share experiences on social media. Therefore, it is reasonable to state that the emergence of social media creates more benefits and inconvenient online environment to customers, whereas it brings both opportunities and challenges to businesses (Cui and Wu, 2016).

2.6.3. Impacts of social media on consumer behaviour:

Regarding to consumer behaviour, social media has an ability to influence to their buying behaviour. Businesses and brands understand the importance of social media when implementing marketing strategies to stimulate consumer behavior. By taking social media as a communication tool, businesses utilised factors of social media to enhance consumer behaviour in the positive way. Those factors can influences to consumer behaviour are contents, visual, promotion campaigns and social media influencers. Additionally, social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagrams, Youtube plays main role to be online environment to affect to consumer behaviour. Many contents, product reviews, customer experiences and product services have been shared and indirectly connected customers and busiesses. Therefore, this shared information are becoming the influence source on consumer buying behaviour Gupta and Chopra (2020). In a previous study of Barhemmati et al., (2012), social media marketing plays an important role in the relationship of brand selling activities and consumer behaviour, thus social media can be employed to enhance the awareness of products and services and importantly become marketing tool in designing promotion campaigns to attract customers.

Beginning with the product awareness at the first step of consumer behaviours towards products/services, following with the attractive contents about a specific products and given promotion campaigns of products to offer customers, the last step to trigger their decision behaviour is to use social medi influencer to confirm and convince customers about

the product quality and reinforce the choice. Building product awareness in social media plays an important role to influence customers. With the purpose of improve consumer behaviours in positive way, product information will be spread over social media platforms to achieve more interaction from users. In additions, the brand awareness and their presence on social media has to be considered as the vital activities to support customer on their searching process. Therefore, in order to enhance product awareness, an attractive and informative social media content need to be created to influence consumer behaviour. Attractive contents posted by brands can impact on customer sentiment and stimulate them to pay attention to specific products and brands. Informative contents shared on social media can provide customer a lifetime value to acknowledge about brands or products. It also support to increase the engagement between customers and brands. An attractive contents can be created for entertaining purposes. Entertainment factor always attract customer attention and enhance customer attitude towards any specific products or services. Hence, creating entertaining contents and gathering it with the information of brands or products are the marketing strategy to influence customers. Based on that, the social media engagement of brands and customers will be significantly improved and trigger to customer behavior (Aydin et al., 2021). Apart from the attractive social media content about a specific product of businesses/brands, the social media content created by existing loyal customer will influence others including potential customers. A good experiences towards products from existing customers are shared, reviewed or comments on social media will stimulate customer behaviour. Furthermore, the brand trust would be built based on the customer shares and reviews on social media and also increase conversion rate. Through the reality of positive case studies, videos, pictures, comments and reviews of existing customers, social media supports businesses build the trustfulness, it leads more effective toward consumer behaviour Varghese and Agrawal (2020).

Promotion campaigns always attract customers in buying behaviour aspect. Discount or incentive programs influence consumer behaviour in the conventional marketing and social media marketing. However, with the convenience of social media, customers tend to join to many social media page or group to see the promotions of products, and also receive promotion information which were shared by brands or other social media users. Many businesses and brands utilise social media platforms to advertise or deploy promotion campaigns to reach more customers and to promote them to purchase products/services.

Promotion and exclusive campaigns are considered as attractive content which enable to bring more value to customers. It significantly supports to brands obtain more engagement between customers and products on social media. The more attractive of discount and promotions, the more number of shares, likes, comments and other interaction on social media. Hence, it will affect to consumer behaviour in positive way and encourage them to purchase products when products are on promotions (Wibowo et al., 2020).

One more factor of social media influences customers which many businesses applied to stimulate consumer behavior are social media influencers. Customers tend to purchase any product that they has been recommended from a person they are inspired. Social media influencers contributes significantly in consumer behaviours. Influencers have power to affect to consumer decisions and behaviour by their knowledge, reputation and topic on social media. Posts and shares of influencer on their social media pages enable to generate a huge of followers and easily to engage users with their topic in purpose. Understanding this core value of influencer factor in social media marketing, brands hire social media influencers to support them in creating trends and encourage customer to purchase products/services. Social media influencers are formed in many types such as celebrities with a large number of both offline and online followers, social media users with high number of followers, or those people who can influence others in specialised fields. Social media influencers can present a specific topic in various type of social media contents. Brand can requires influencers to express contents in blogging type, videos on YouTube, social posts on Facebook, Twitter, or even visual images on Instagram. Based on their reputation, the social media contents about a specific brand or products will build more trust to customers (Geysler, 2021). According to Clootrack (2020), there are 49% of cutomers look for social media influencer opinions to support them in their buying decisions. Customers will be enjoyed and encouraged by positive social media influencers. Influencer marketing is more popular for both brands and customers when social media platform are increasing and evolving with various features which enable supports to influencer performance and content creation.

2.7. Demographical factors:

According to Tran and Olafson (2021), Social media demographics are the crucial factors that significantly support business marketing strategy to approach appropriate

customers. Authors claimed that with the rapid development of social media in people's daily lives, social media marketers need to understand and deeply investigate social media demographics. Additionally, the variety of social media platforms today impacts choosing the appropriate social media platform of customers. The rapid upgrading of technology tends to grab more attraction from young generation. The attractive social media contents of specific products might attract a different group of genders. However, the research based on the figures of social media users using social media platforms by genders, there are different gender gap relating to social media users in other regions. For example, according to the research, only 24% of social media female users are compared with 76% of social media user males in Southern Asia. However, this percentage is changing in other Asia regions, there is 48% and 52% of social media users of female and male, respectively.

The most influencing demographical factor acknowledged in the research is age demographic. Age plays a vital role in impacting social media in generally using and particularly in business. For instance, according to the distribution of Facebook users worldwide of July 2021 (Statista, 2021), the majority of Facebook users are in the age group from 25-34 years old. Understanding how different age groups use social media is essential to optimize marketing campaigns, and it is crucial to make a strategic marketing plan for the long- term. As a study of Hruska and Maresova (2020), in comparison with old generation (Generation X), the young generation (Generation Y) seems to be influenced and depended on brand content on Facebook. They also engage more with promotion campaigns of brands and have more interaction on social media through electronic word – of – mouth (E-WOM). Moreover, the young people in the age group with range 18-29 years olds tends to spend more time on social media than older people, the average spending time is over 3 hours per day, which means the age increases, it leads the social media access reduces. Therefore, Generation Y mainly supports businesses and brands to obtain a wide vision towards consumer behaviors. This is a significant contribution to create a marketing strategy to target the largest group of customers and raising brand awareness Hruska and Maresova (2020). According to Yakobi (2016), his research about social media in banking showed that gender distribution of females is higher than males concerning social media using in banking. Regarding the banking activities and sharing opinions about social influence, the age group between 25-39 has more concern than older age groups.

2.8. Social media in banking sector

2.8.1. Importance of social media in banking

Banking sectors has always been considered as the specific field with typical products/services. According to American Bankers Association (ABA) (2019), by a rapid movement of technology, banking sector also has significant changed with the emergence of social media. There is the similarity with other industries, banks also realized the important of social media which could lower cost and raise their presence on online environment. Moreover, it supports them to expand their networks to target customer on social media. A research about the State of Social media in banking sector was conducted to examine the role of social media in banking sector towards customer engagement. The survey was conducted and data was collected from 430 banks in the latest version in the report 2019 by ABA, it indicated that 40% of the respondents said social media has been used in their bank for five years and more, 32% said social media has been used in their banks for three to four years. There was 3% said their banks do not use social media but they will consider to adopt it in the future. However, the importance of social media in banking sector has been agreed by 84% of respondents. They understood that the innovation of social media crucially affects to bank reputation. In the same context, the most employed social media platforms in banking sector are Facebook (97%), LinkedIn (76%), and following by Instagram, Twitter and YouTube with over 40%. This research of ABA also partly demonstrated that the importance of social media has been contributed to banks by various ways. For instance, social media platforms are used by banks to provide engaging contents to connect customers with banks. Those creative contents could be education of financial and banking products, entertainments or celebration. According to Schmidt (2021), since 2010s, there has been significant change in the way how banks apply social media in their marketing strategies. Social media platforms become more popular in banking activities. It supports banks to enhance customer experience and create more business opportunities. The engaging on social media channels with various and creative contents and dealing with customer complaints on social media brought more benefits to banks when approaching to their customers. Furthermore, with the development of many social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube, social media has played an important role in banking sector which enable to maintain the relationship between banks and customers and reach to customer expectation (Capgemini, 2014). By using social media platforms, banks enable to create the connection in the personal way to deal with

their issues or give more information about bank services in the friendly way. Although banking services is considered as a typical product which are bounded with many financial regulation, many banks demonstrated that they have been successful by adopting social media to implement financial content and engage financial products to customers. Toronto Dominion Bank (TD bank) – one of the leading financial institution in North America was very successful when implementing their marketing campaigns on social media to attract their customers. Beginning with the first campaign in 2014 with hashtag #TDthankyou, customers and employees were rewards gifts and surprises. During this campaign, a video has been created and went viral on YouTube and was shared wisely. This campaign has been continued until the pandemic in 2020. It can be said that this campaign enhances the bank reputation, bring more added value to customer, build brand loyalty and maintain the relationship with customers via social media channels. Through this kind of campaign, it demonstrated that social media plays a vital role in marketing strategies of banks. By using social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, financial services could be put in emotional context and meaningful contents to attract customers and went viral in the fastest way to compare with conventional marketing Schmidt (2021).

In another aspect, digital bank has been developed, the trend of using electronic wallet has been rising in the young generation, social media platforms are the effective tool to deploy marketing campaigns to enhance banks services. Because young generation usually spend more time on Internet and specially in social media for communicating with each other. Hence, young generation customers tend to reach out banks on social media to update information and look for new trending products/services (Cognizants, 2016).

According to thefinancialbrand (2021), Facebook is the most popular platform for banks with high volume of likes to compare with other platforms such as YouTube, Twitter and Instagram. Social media literally is considered as an essential tool for banks to stimulate brand awareness and their reputation (Jackowicz et al., 2020).

#	Bank	Facebook Likes	Twitter Followers	YouTube Views	Instagram Followers
1	State Bank of India	17,993,284	4,200,000	401,696,192	2,000,000
2	Axis	3,657,727	361,100	318,051,946	158,000
3	ICICI	5,372,471	631,500	280,709,084	212,000
4	Kotak Mahindra	1,527,181	272,400	265,805,265	115,000
5	Yes	6,953,702	1,600,000	144,095,307	491,000
6	TD Bank (Canada)	832,597	120,600	224,083,775	44,300
7	RBC	576,275	102,800	188,943,330	47,600
8	HDFC	2,836,445	456,200	144,281,484	234,000
9	Chase	3,939,746	387,200	112,984,201	189,000
10	Goldman Sachs	248,864	846,200	153,648,635	155,000
11	GT Bank	6,064,095	1,600,000	27,600,799	721,000
12	Zenith Bank	6,166,906	1,300,000	28,014,987	505,000
13	CIMB	1,626,931	141,300	116,696,535	69,600
14	BDO	3,720,927		88,500,906	
15	TD Bank (US)	832,598	54,800	107,606,051	27,500
16	Maybank	2,295,611	176,500	62,482,421	132,000
17	Wells Fargo	1,116,267	326,400	74,127,132	95,700
18	Citi	1,169,165	912,900	63,542,759	61,400
19	BBVA	5,755,922	13,300	8,531,051	8,005
20	CIBC	411,071	121,000	84,615,973	31,400

Figure 4: Top 20 Banks using Social media platform in the first quarter 2021

(source: thefinancialbrand, 2021)

Apart from traditional marketing channels which banks are using to implement their marketing strategy such as email marketing, online advertising, TVC, social media has been considered as a practical marketing tool for brand awareness, raise bank reputation and directly trigger customer behavior. Additionally, banking services is a typical product which need to provide trustfulness and financial knowledge to customers. Social media enable work as the online environment to spread over the useful financial information and build the trust from banks and experiences from their existing loyal customers. Therefore, banks take advantage of social media to improve brand equity (Micti and Kapoulas, 2012).

According to a study of Parusheva (2017), social media becomes one of communication channels to approach both existing and new potential customers. With a lot

of inquiries and customer issues about banking services, the role of social media will support banks along with other channels to solve problems. Banks can communicate with a huge number of customers on social media platform and gather the same inquiries to figure out and help their customer in the quick way to compare with call center services or walk in branch service (face to face). Through social media channel, banks instantly offer customer the needed information towards a specific banking services which many customers on social media are concerning and interested in. Banks enable to provide customers a fastest response to customer inquiries and issues. Moreover, by using social media channel, bank provide customers appropriate solutions which might fits with customer needs and preferences because by observing customer interaction on social media, the best solution will be provided to meet customer requirement. In this study, an example from Deutsche bank research was given that customers have more desires about financial information on social media rather than seeking the bank consultancy via branches or call center. Therefore, it demonstrated the benefits of social media when playing a role as communication channel to approach customers. Additionally, banks take advantage of social media in receiving the feedback and opinions of customers about banking products/services. This is very important to support banks to improve their product quality and provide the best customer experience to customers. In the facts, the feedback of customer on social media always has both side positive and negative comments. However, obtaining the negative feedback to figure out and provide the appropriate solution will enhance bank brand equity and their reputation. For instance, many banks in UK has suspended the function of depositing money in other people bank account. JP Morgan's implemented that policy in 2014 to prevent money laundry. Customers immediately commented negative feedback and complaints on Twitter about that issues. However, JP Morgan instantly announced on social media to offer them alternative solution and explain to them on social media about their situation. Therefore, in comparison with other channels such as website, call center, email marketing, social media supports banks to understand their customer needs and figure out the solution in the fastest way. One more role that some banks has used social media to reduce the work for other bank departments is for transactional social banking which has been mentioned earlier. Some banks believe that social media totally enable to make transactions like fund transfer as the convenient tool. This offers customers the functional way to make a standard payment. For instance, ICICI

Indian bank released banking services on Twitter in 2015, this service allows customer to make fund transfer and top up mobile. By providing the security authentication process and the limitation of transaction, customers easily to use social media to make any transaction.

In comparison with traditional marketing of banks such as direct email marketing, advertising on website and banners, branch marketing, call center to provide banking service to customer, now social media changed the bank's approaches to customers. By using social media, banks can analyze and understand customer's preferences, needs and even their emotion. Based on that, marketing promotion campaigns on social media will be deployed to reach customer expectation. Many banks take advantage of social media source as the big data to accurately investigate customer behavior and their desires. Based on that investigation, products and services will be designed to meet their customer needs and expectations (Rezayat, 2017).

2.8.2. Benefits of social media in banking

Many research has been investigated the advantages of social media application in banking sectors including many reports and example of success banks in social media. Even some research did not focus on social media but the outcome still has been brought the benefits of social media in case the research will be conducted in the future. Indeed, in the research of Heaney (2007), with the common operation of online banking services such as Internet banking, mobile banking, it supports customer to associate with banks to experience and utilize banking service in the convenient way. However, it is still limit the interaction between customers and banks. Banks still need another platform to obtain more interaction with customer, hence they would want to understand customer needs and preferences. Especially, young generation tends to access Internet to look for information more than using other channels. They prefer new technologies as social media to communicate each other. Therefore, social media has become a focus channel for bank to expand and approach to young generation.

Social media increased the customer awareness in banking sectors. Customers tend to reach on social media to express their need and preference towards specific thing in their life. Customer interaction and action on social media indirectly become the source of customer data. With the development of social media, more and more customers rely on social media to seek for their daily life supports by posts and shares on social media

platforms. Therefore, banks will take advantage of social media in this aspect to implement their business plan such as marketing campaigns, product development, accelerate sales and customer service (Micti and Kapoulas, 2012).

According to Ahuja (2020), social media created the practical social media marketing for banking sector. It brings advantages to banks in implementing their strategies through employing social media as the sharpen tools. As other business industries, social media has been utilized by banks to provide online community for customer engagement. Since customer access social media more than before, building online environment on social media will support banks to communicate with more customers including existing and new potential customers. Moreover, due to the typical type products, banks always consider to deploy promotion campaigns. Advertisings must be related to finance and banking information which always make people feel bored. However, banks use social media to assist them to engage banking products to customers through online community. It will also help the banks for their long-term profitability goal. Online community on social media is where customers enable to discuss, interact with each other and being updated financial information shares of banking products to compared with traditional advertising. Through the online environment, customer will receive prompt response towards their inquiries rather than bank websites. In this research, the author also stated the benefits of social media to banks will maintain relationship banking. Banks enable utilize social media to deploy social media campaigns which relate to financial products. These social media campaigns highlighted the financial content such as offer high interest rates for long term, the social media campaigns run for long time to make customer satisfy and raise the higher interaction on social media. Additionally, in order to approach new potential customers, social media contents attract customer with relevant differentiation information of banks and their competitors. Promotional contents definitely attract new customers to switch from their current bank to the new bank.

Social media contributes to brand awareness of banks. All the post and marketing contents on social media reflect the brand awareness and the trustfulness of banks to customers. Especially, banking products relates to money, fund and financial therefore, it is very important to build a trustful image to customers in long term objective. Utilizing the loyal customer base to express their experiences and opinions in all the posts and bank marketing contents will create the positive impacts and trusts to new potential customers.

Social media plays an important role in sharing financial and banking contents wisely. Banking information and product updates are shared in social media contents. It can be social campaigns to improve consumer finance knowledge before they want to reach out to banking products. These kind of sharing contents can be mainly mentioned to online banking, mobile banking information, loans, mortgages, credit cards which will provide more information about banking services to new potential customers, also it guides existing customers to have better experiences with banks. For instance, the information about credit cards will attract more customer by providing them the specific benefits of credit cards and the privileges along with that. This social media content normally attracts both new and existing customers when they can see the conveniences of banking products.

Social media has been used to target different group of customers in banking sector. Social media provided the analytic tool to assist banks can classify different groups of customers, therefore, banks can provide different products and strategies to approach customers. With this purpose, banks create social media content and social media ads to promote long-term investment products or lifetime savings for old generations. Besides, mortgage or loans will be banking products to target young customers on social media. By reaching out specific customer groups with specific contents will enhance the customer approaching ability of banks, so it leads the sales increasing.

Many banks use social media for purposes of customer interaction and retention. In order to understand customer behavior, social media support banks to observe them on social media. By using social media, consumer will behave their satisfaction or dissatisfaction on social media towards banking products and also update trends on social media. Based on that, banks can interact with them to improve their service. Additionally, customer retention is very important in banking operation, existing customers contribute more profit to compared with the new customers because of product cross selling would be effortless to those customers. For instance, an individual customer has bank account in a bank, they will easily offer them credit card, loans or mortgage. Therefore, social media is the quicker channel to approach them an offer them attractive services.

Social media influencer is one of power tool that banks and financial institution employ to expand their network. According to Cocheo (2020), influencer marketing is development in recent years, and become a noticeable trend on social media. Social media

community has many participants who have different preferences and been influenced by different field. Social media influencers can be celebrities or people who have high follower on their social media pages. They influence social media users in many industries such as finance, fashion, lifestyle, music and etc. Banks pick influencers to help them to promote and spread their products information on social media. Many banks hire personal experts who have high follower on social media to express their experiences and financial knowledge to social media users. This is the most convenient tool for fast sharing information and also build the trust to customer. Social media influencers are considered as the channel to provide honest information when they experienced products and has been trained to provide useful information to others.

2.8.3. Challenges of social media in banking

Apart from the benefits of social media in banking, banks are also facing to challenges when employ social media to apply in their strategies. Compliance is one of the issues has been discussed in many studies which is a challenge to banks when using social media. According to Senadheera (2015), compliance issues need to be aware when address the use of social media. Consumers easily share information about banking products that they experienced. The opinions can be bad comments and even bank has policies and procedures to monitor their social media activities however, the social media compliance is not enough to prevent these issues. Bank policies can manager their employees towards social media posting and give them the restriction when interacting on social media, however in order to monitoring the customer interaction is still a challenge for banks.

According to Sarigianni et al. (2015), reputation risk is considered in case customer information has been leaked. This is one of the typical challenges to financial institutions and banks. Social media is an open online environment, if confidential and private information of customer such as account number, credit card number has been posted and leaked through social media via customer interaction. It would affect to bank reputation if customers were stolen money or influenced to their personal life. Moreover, many negative comments on social media which could not controlled by banks might ruin the bank reputation. Although banks have social media monitoring tools and techniques to manage the risk from social media, social media is a big online environment, negative information easily to spread over very quick. In this study, the author stated that the communication

from employees via social media can help to reduce the compliance risk and reputation risk. By providing a good training for employees, they can contribute to spread and create content via their personal social media page to decrease the risk.

Security and privacy are remaining the challenges for banks why employing social media. According to Parusheva (2017), even some banks accept customer to implement transactional social media, it might bring more convenient for social media users, however due to the security and privacy, banks need to protect their customers, hence, they do not allow customer make payment, bank transfer or balance checking on social media. Because social media compliance is still not enough to secure the confidential customer information. Instead of that, banks provide to customer a landing page, thus customer can directly link to Mobile app or Internet banking to implement payments or bank transfers. Understanding this challenge, many banks are improving their IT system such as generating authentication process to support customers on social media in the futures. Additionally, some banking products are considered as sensitive products like personal loans, whereas social media is an open online environment. Interaction of customers are to exposed, therefore, many customers desire to interact to banks for looking for loans or mortgage, they probably avoid social media channel due to their privacy issues.

2.9. Social media in Vietnamese banking sector

Vietnamese banking system has been managed and controlled by State bank of Vietnam. Those activities such as issuing currency, managing money and creating monetary policies and laws on banking systems has been managed by State bank of Vietnam. There are 5 state owned commercial banks, 34 joints stock banks, and more than 35 branch offices of foreign banks and representative banks and they are working under Vietnamese banking law controlled by State bank of Vietnam. The leading banks of Vietnam are Vietcombank, Agribank, BIDV, Vietinbank and Techcombank. Besides, other foreign banks in Vietnam are HSCB, ANZ and Citibanks are also considered as the popular banks in Vietnam (vietnamonline, 2021).

Regarding to social media in Vietnamese banking, social media has not been considered as the focused channel in Vietnamese banking sector. Therefore, there were rarely research which studied about social media application in Vietnamese banking. However, with the development of social media in Vietnam, many banks took advantage

of social media to implement their marketing strategies.

Figure 5: Number of interactions and comments about banks on social media in the first 5 months of 2020.

According to Bao Trung (2020), Vietcombank is the leading banks for the top of the interaction and comments on social media in 2020. As the report on the Figure 3, Vietcombank has the most comments and interaction of social media users with 866,081 comments and interaction, it accounted for 37% in total comments on social media about banking. Other banks contributed less comments however in this report, it also indicated that the number of comments reflects both negative and positive sentiment. For instance, the positive comments about Vietcombank mainly regarding the customer services, however, many complaints on social media about confidential customer information and also the high service fee of Vietcombank services. Besides, Techcombank obtained the most positive comments on social media about their services with reasonable fee charge for using their banking services. Whereas, BIDV with the most negative comments on social media, majority of the negative comments raised about their customer services. Regarding the demographic of social media users who participated in social media community to interact about Vietnamese banking, the research indicated that the young generation in the age group of 18-25 mainly contributed with 83% and female tends to have more interaction and comment on social media to compared with male. Therefore, based on the result of social media interaction, the target customers for Vietnamese banking would be focused more on young generation as well as women. In order to create the appropriate and attractive social media contents, utilizing their influencers will increase the viral of banks on social media. Indeed, in another report from Vovworld (2021), with more

than 72 million social media users in Vietnam, equivalent to 73% population, Vietnamese banking are planning to consider social media to become the communication tools to expand their network larger. In the previous research of Pham (2013), digital marketing has developed many commercial banks in Vietnam. With the high Internet penetration in Vietnam, especially the young generation with high technology knowledge, many banks use digital marketing to support banks to approach more potential customers. Hence, social media marketing is one of the digital marketing tools and has a big customer database. By using social media, banking products and promotion campaigns of banks will be reached to more people in social network. But the fact that, not many commercial banks in Vietnam have practical social media marketing. However, with the development of social media and the high number of Vietnamese social media users, social media can become one of the functional communication for banks.

2.10. Conceptual framework:

From the review of the literature, a conceptual framework has been developed as below

Figure 6: Conceptual framework for the research.

As mentioned in the literature, social media provides businesses and brands essential factors to influence consumer behavior, improve marketing strategies, and expand brand awareness. This study aims to acknowledge the impact of social media based on key elements that contribute to business operations in general and the banking sector in particular. Banks leverage social media in their marketing strategies to significantly influence consumer behavior towards banking products and services. By utilizing social

media marketing activities, businesses can align with consumer purchasing intentions and instill confidence and reliability in their products or services. Social media marketing for businesses typically involves creating content, visual images, promotional campaigns, and engaging with social media influencers. These efforts are driven by social media activities such as entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on social media platforms (Gupta & Chopra, 2020).

When banks employ social media to implement marketing strategies and positively influence consumer behavior, they must consider both the benefits and challenges of social media. The advantages of social media can help achieve business goals such as product development, marketing campaigns, sale acceleration, and customer service (Micti & Kapoulas, 2012). Social media becomes an essential tool for banks to execute their marketing strategies and foster an online community for customer engagement with banking services (Ahuja, 2020). However, social media also presents risks such as compliance issues, reputation risks, and concerns about security and privacy, which can hinder consumer decision-making regarding product seeking and purchasing (Parusheva, 2017).

In order to build an effective marketing strategy on social media and accurately target customers, understanding social media demographics is crucial. Social media is evolving with advanced technology, making platforms increasingly popular, especially among the younger generation (Tran & Olafson, 2021). Based on the conceptual framework, the researcher formulates five research hypotheses, as mentioned in Chapter 1.

2.11. Hypotheses from which they were derived:

Hypothesis 1: Demographical factors are statistical significantly and positively related to social media in banking industry.

The rapid changing of technologies always have a strong affect to young generations. Social media, in particular, has become highly attractive to young people, offering engaging content, opportunities for connection in an open online environment, and a platform to express their opinions. Consequently, understanding social media demographics is crucial for businesses to effectively implement their marketing strategies. These demographics help in designing promotion campaigns that target the right customers. The integration of social media into daily life has altered people's habits and

perceptions. Social media marketers need to analyze these demographics to develop diverse marketing strategies aimed at different customer segments. Additionally, social media demographics influence customer's choice of platforms, as each platform offers unique features that can enhance various aspects of business operations. Different social media content can attract distinct groups based on gender and age (Tran and Olafson, 2021).

Despite the broad impact of social media, cultural and regional differences can lead to varying usage patterns. For example, in Southern Asia, only 24% of social media users are female compared to 76% male. The ratio differs in other parts of Asia, where the gender distribution is closer to 48% female and 52% male. One objective of this research is to explore the influence of social media on businesses and the banking industry. The most influential demographic factors identified in this study are not just gender but also age. Age demographics play a crucial role when businesses design marketing strategies to reach potential customers. According to Statista (2021), Facebook users are predominantly aged 25-34. Brands focus on creating content that appeals to younger generations, as they believe this group will help spread product information effectively to potential customers. Additionally, insights gained from the younger generation's experiences can help brands better understand consumer behavior. The amount of time spent on social media also varies by age group, with older individuals spending less time online. This hypothesis will be tested by surveying banking customers and using quantitative methods to demonstrate the significant contribution of demographic factors is essential for maximizing customer reach and enhancing brand awareness.

This hypothesis will support to achieve objective 1.

Hypothesis 2: Social media are statistical significantly related to consumer behaviour.

In term of consumer behaviour, social media has generated the effectiveness to customer's buying behaviour and their experiences about products. Businesses and brands has taken advantage of social media to stimulate the consumer behaviour in their marketing strategies. Brands employed social media as a communication tool to strengthen their marketing strategy and particularly investigate consumer behaviour. Factors such as contents, visual, promotion campaigns and social media influencer are operated on social media platforms to facilitate the consumer behaviour investigation. For instance, the

customer buying behaviour is always affected by promotion campaigns. Discount and incentive programs stimulate customer decision making towards a specific products or services. In the fact, even though these marketing activities has been implemented in traditional marketing, the benefit of social media would effortlessly approach to customers to support businesses understand consumer behaviour. Also, customers would easily take the initiative to look for product information instead of remaining passive to achieve promotions from brands. Customers enable to access to social media networks or fan page of brands to look for product information and promotions which were posted by brands or even by social media influencers. Promotion contents also easily go viral on social media to attract more potential customers and influence customer purchasing decision. Therefore, advertisement deployment and promotion campaigns tend to be posted on social media platforms as a main marketing channel. Consumer behaviour has been affected by seeing the number of shares, likes, comments and social media user's interaction of promotion. The higher reaction number of a social media content will influenced customer to purchase products. This will impact on consumer behaviours in a positive way and encourage them to spread information more viral. In additions, social media influencer are applied to stimulate consumer behaviour. Social media influencer enable to encourage customer in purchasing decision, furthermore, this also affect to consumer emotional or mental by inspiring them with their performance and creative content on social media Clootrack (2020). The researcher will apply quantitative method to analyse the collected data of participant's opinion based on questionnaire to test this hypothesis.

This hypothesis will support to achieve objective 1.

Hypothesis 3: Social media activities significantly contribute to marketing strategy in banking.

The banking industry is fundamentally a key sector within finance where the dissemination of product information must be trustworthy to gain customer confidence. Therefore, establishing a reliable and credible image is vital for long-term success. By leveraging social media, banks can significantly enhance customer awareness. Marketing content on social media platforms directly influences brand perception and trust among customers. The convenience of social media enables customers to easily express their demands and preferences regarding specific products or services. Simultaneously, social

media development. Allows customers to effortlessly seek product information. These customer interactions serve as valuable data sources, aiding banks in refining their marketing strategies.

Banks have harnessed social media to execute various marketing initiatives, including raising brand awareness, running promotional campaigns, accelerating sales, launching new products, and improving customer service (Micti and Kapoulas, 2012). A crucial aspect of social media utilization by banks is leveraging their loyal customer base. The experiences and views shared by loyal customers on social media generate positive impacts and build trust with potential customers. Shared experiences regarding digital banking, loans, mortgages, and credit cards can be particularly influential. For example, detailed information about credit card benefits and privilege packages can attract more customers. Furthermore, social media helps banks reduce marketing costs by providing an efficient channel to reach broad audience, thereby supporting cost-effective marketing strategies.

The researcher will employ both quantitative and qualitative methods to test the hypothesis by collecting and analyzing participants' experiences with implementing marketing strategies on social media platforms. This approach will provide comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of social media in enhancing customer engagement and trust in the banking sector.

This hypothesis will support to achieve objective 2.

Hypothesis 4: Practical factors of social media help to approach customer attention and satisfaction

The primary objective of many banks in integrating social media into their marketing strategies is to capture customer attention and meet customer demands. Customers often express their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with products on social media after using them, allowing banks to interact and refine their offerings based on this feedback. Additionally, social media is a hotbed for viral trends, which banks can monitor to inspire marketing ideas that attract more customer attention to their products.

Customer retention is a top priority in banking operations, and social media provides an effective channel to offer attractive products to existing customers. These customers are generally more profitable than new ones as they are familiar with browsing their bank's social media pages, enhancing cross-sell opportunities. For instance, offering additional

products like credit cards, loans, or mortgages to satisfied customers with personal bank accounts requires less effort than targeting new customers.

Social media is a powerful tool for rapidly disseminating attractive content within an online community. It serves not only as a promotional channel but also as a space where existing customers and potential new ones can interact. This creates an online environment rich in finance and banking information, fostering discussions and enhancing brand awareness, ultimately capturing more customer attention.

Moreover, social media offer analytic tools that help banks evaluate the performance of their content and understand customer responses. This data enables banks to improve their products and adjust marketing strategies accordingly. For example, social media analytics can help banks identify which products are more suitable for older customers versus younger ones. Banks can then create targeted social media ads, promoting long-term investment products and lifetime savings for older age groups while using trendy content to advertise mortgages or loans to younger customers. This capability enhances customer engagement and boosts sales.

A key factor contributing to the success of social media marketing strategies is the use of social media influencers. Many banks have embraced this trend, hiring influencers to support their marketing plans. Social media influencers, with their large followings, can effectively communicate honest and useful information about banking products, especially when they have financial knowledge (Cocheo, 2020).

In order to test this hypothesis, the researcher will gather data from participants' perspectives and use both quantitative and qualitative methods to analyze the collected data, aiming to achieve the research objectives.

This hypothesis will help to achieve objective 3.

Hypothesis 5: Risk factors of social media lead to a statistically significant change in choosing banking services of customers.

While social media offers many advantages, banks also face significant challenges and risks when incorporating it into their marketing strategies. One major concern is compliance. Social media platforms have terms and condition that users must agree to, but they cannot control all information posted, which can pose serious issues for banks. For

instance, negative comments about banking products can harm a bank's reputation (Das, 2015). Banks have implemented procedures to monitor their social media pages and mitigate these issues, but negative comments can still damage their reputation.

Reputation risk is another significant challenge, especially if customer information is leaked. In the banking sector, protecting customer information is critical due to the risk of scams. If confidential details such as account numbers or credit card information are posted or leaked through social media interactions, it can severely impact a bank's reputation.

Security and privacy also remain ongoing challenges. Many banks are enhancing their IT systems, including implementing robust authentication processes, to better support customers on social media in the future. However, certain banking products, such as personal loans, are considered sensitive. The open nature of social media makes some customers uncomfortable seeking information about loans or mortgages online, as they fear exposing their private lives.

In order to address these challenges, banks must continually update their security measures and privacy protocols. They need to ensure that their social media interactions are secure and that sensitive customer information is protected. Additionally, banks should educate their customers about the steps they are taking to protect their information and encourage safe social media practices. By doing so, banks can better navigate the complexities of social media marketing while maintaining customer trust and safeguarding their reputations.

This hypothesis will be tested by both qualitative method and quantitative method to achieve the research objective.

This hypothesis will help to achieve objective 3

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction:

The literature review in the previous chapter discussed the vital role of social media in banking services. This research focuses on the banking industry in Vietnam, a developing country in Southeast Asia. Like other developing countries, Vietnam's banking sector is increasingly adopting social media for customer service, customer perception, and banking advertisements to engage with their customer. This trend is particularly significant among younger generations, specifically Gen Y and Gen Z.

This chapter aims to build upon that discussion by detailing the research process and selecting the appropriate research method. The chosen methodology will be explored and justified as a tool for data analysis. According to Wilson (2013), research involves collecting, recording, analyzing, and interpreting information. In order to conduct effective and practical research, it is essential for researchers to have a thorough understanding of research methodology and methods. In general, to conduct research, methodology plays a role as the approach and strategy in the research process. In addition, data can be collected and analysed to demonstrate and solve all issues of any specific topic. Thus, in this research, the Honeycomb of research methodology model will be employed to outline and implement

the research methodology. This model offers a comprehensive strategic approach and an explanation of each stage of the research process. The model concepts developed in six steps: research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection, and data analysis techniques, respectively.

Each step of the Honeycomb model is crucial for developing a robust research framework. The research philosophy underpins the overall approach, guiding the choice of methods and techniques. The research approach outlines whether the study will be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed – method. The research strategy details the plan of action for how the study will be conducted. Research design involves the specific procedures and techniques used in the research. Data collection encompasses the methods used to gather information, while data analysis techniques refer to the tools and procedures used to interpret the collected data.

By employing this structured methodology, the research will effectively address the role of social media in the Vietnamese banking industry, providing insights into customer engagement and marketing strategies tailored to younger generations. The thorough application of the Honeycomb model will ensure a systematic and comprehensive approach to the study, leading to practical and actionable outcomes.

According to (Kruger & Welman, 2001), a scientific research method was utilized to develop knowledge in a specific field of any studies. Indeed, several models have been applied to research methodology such as Onion’s layers (Saunders, 2012). Saunders et al (2008) initially adapted research onion as one of the research methodology which contains six layers as the following Figure:

According to Sauder (2008) researcher understands that this research onion framework provides an ideal research procedures to conduct a practical research. The research onion has been claimed that the advantages of research onion devise a series of stages in which a methodological study would be described (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). However, this study needs to be addressed and focuses on the key issues and enhances the logical manner, so that the Honeycomb framework will be the best choice to conduct this study because of its preciseness while implementing the research. On the other hand, the Honeycomb model also supports in gathering the nature of the evidence with various types of research questions. In order to achieve to the best outcome of the research, the researcher always considers the appropriate option of research methods. Therefore, Honeycomb framework will contribute to creating the organized systematic and critical study due to its underpinning principle. It also will support the research to examine and explore each part of research method in effective pathway. Additionally, this model assists to effortlessly investigate specific issues of the study with diversified research philosophies, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection and data analysis and interpretation techniques to compare with others models. (Wilson, 2013). The Honeycomb of research methodology is showed as the following figure:

The benefit of this framework is all six elements might not need to be in the order because all the elements are combined to build up the research methodology. This research model always gathers all the elements as a strong relationship to compare with other models. Based on all the clarified reasons, this study adopts Honeycombs framework as a guide to deploy research methodology in this chapter.

3.2. Research Philosophy:

In any research field, the research philosophy has been adopted contains important assumptions which supported research strategy in the particular studies. The research philosophy usually will be influenced by practical considerations. On the other hand, research philosophy was described as the underlying of development with respect of knowledge and a system of beliefs (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). In order to be successful in a particular business research, the philosophical commitment needs to be clearly perceived throughout the choice of research strategy which means the research should be able to be reflected upon philosophical choices and be defended in term of the alternatives (Johnson and Clark, 2006). Basically, there are three major ways of describing research philosophy such as epistemology, ontology and axiology. Each of them certainly influences the way to drive researchers to understand research questions, the applied methods and data analysis process (Crotty, 1998). This chapter will explain the different theories that support for this research and also discuss the appropriate philosophy applied to this research.

3.2.1. Epistemology

Understanding of epistemology in research philosophy is the essential background to deploy a specific research. Hence, the research will start by explaining the concepts of epistemological assumptions. The study of knowledge and the acceptable valid knowledge are factors which refers to epistemology (Collis and Hussey, 2003). In other words, epistemology generally is concerned as the theory of knowledge and acceptable knowledge is constituted (Blaikie, 2004). According to study of Burrell and Morgan (1979), they also mentioned clearly epistemology refers to how the knowledge has been applying to gather with others. In another research, epistemology related to the kind of nature of knowledge. There are two types of researcher which are resource researchers and feelings researchers. Epistemology are concerned by resources researcher because the data collection and analysis tends to more natural and based in the fact (Wilson, 2014). For those kinds of researcher, reality is considered priority as objects, the data was involved in more authority and taken from statistical resources. Therefore, epistemology is more obvious where all knowledges refers to legitimate way. Epistemology has three main philosophical approaches such as positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism. These epistemological

views are taken in research, and for more detail of each assumptions will be extended in the following section.

Positivism:

Positivism has been seen in social science as the method which the combination of deductive logic with accurate empirical observation of individual behaviour, based on that it will be able to forecast general types of human activity (Neuman, 2003). The frame work of this assumptions relates to the acceptable knowledge is considered on direct observation or manipulation of natural circumstance through experience, experimental and means (Lincoln & Guba, 2005). In other words, researcher will implement with the observation towards the social reality, thus, the consequences of the research findings will tend to be more obviously in physical and natural mind set. Indeed, as mentioned in epistemology concept, the positivism assumption drives the research to be more credible. In the positivism assumption, the researcher is commonly separated with research participant which leads to the objective results. Because the implementation of any positivism assumption based research always refers to deductive approach, so the consequent research finding would be more deployed in the whole population. Positivists prefer to facts rather than opinion to evaluate the outcomes. Hence, the observation of positivism assumption should be considered as high reliability. In summary, positivism is suitable for those researchers who tend to implement their research with natural science process. (Bryman and Bell, 2011 and Wilson, 2014).

Interpretivism:

The principle of interpretivism refers to measurement field and reality of the research, it supports researcher to understand research participant's social world. In other words, researchers are able to observe research participants in interconnection way during the data collection process, however it remains subjective factors in the research (Wilson, 2014). Indeed, based on the interpretivist's view, interpretivism assumption truly relates to collaborative and participatory, hence, inductive approach is commonly used if researcher choose interpretivism. In another research, according to Bryman and Bell (2011), interpretivism is described as the relationship of researcher and the research is based in the interdependence way. In another aspect, the particular research is used epistemological assumptions based on interpretivism which usually tend to acknowledge the social reality

and the social environment within the conducted research (Blaikie, 2010, and Scotland, 2012). Eventually, in order to make the research to be subjective as the interpretivist perspective, researcher must equip themselves to understand the social world in which they are investigating. Also, the participants will play the role to influence the researcher by their values, agreement (Fisher, 2004).

Pragmatism:

According to Wilson (2014), pragmatism is a philosophy to be used while both qualitative and quantitative approaches will be implemented because positivism and interpretivism are not able to help to conduct both methods individually. In another aspect, pragmatism is concerned as the chain between knowledge and action (Goldkuhl, 2012). In the research field, pragmatism commonly focused on both physical and social term (Belk, 2006). In facts, qualitative and quantitative data are collected and analysed or interpreted in which the data integration through both qualitative and quantitative will be produced the final outcomes (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Furthermore, almost pragmatic researchers believe that applying pragmatism in this research will make research more practical and reliable. Researcher would implement both interviews and conduct the questionnaire survey at the same time in the research. Based on the, the best outcomes will be brought out (Wilson, 2014). Therefore, by using this philosophy, the research will dig more deeply into the world rather than observing.

3.2.2. Ontology:

Ontology is concerned with the nature of existence in social structures, cultural norms and all the reality of society. (Crotty, 1998; Snape & Spencer, 2003). In another research, Ontology is considered as the acceptance of reality or understanding knowledge of reality (Scotland, 2012 and Wilson, 2014). Social reality has not been influenced by human conception, on other words, in ontological views, researcher will concern about the nature of social reality as well as the nature of the existed world. It is separated with social actors or any social perceptions. (Bryman, 2008). In the ontological perspective, there are two main types of assumptions such as objectivism and subjectivism. Both objectivism and subjectivism refers to the social existence together with human perception and actions.

Objectivism:

Objectivism is considered as the assumptions of natural society and social reality is external. On other words, social reality stay out of control of researchers (Velde et al, 2004). During the data collections and data interpretations, the natural science will be related to more objective rather than the interaction between researcher and research participant or respondents (Kumar, 2014 and Saunders, 2009).

Subjectivism:

Subjectivism related to interpretivism in which the social reality will be evaluated by human perception and actions. In facts, subjectivism refers to understanding subjective beliefs and perceptions with respect of social individual actions. Subjectivity is considered as the relationship between the researcher and respondents. By using this philosophy, research must have to examine their research participant's observation during research process (Wilson, 2014).

3.2.3. Axiology:

According to Wilson (2014), axiology is considered as the nature of value. Axiology refers to researcher perspective and perception towards their research. It also emphasizes their own value which relates data collection and interpretation. Researcher's own values play a vital role in the research process when the research outcomes are credible. All human action is based on the own values. Axiological skill is concerned when researchers are clearer with their own values. On other words, by using their value, researchers will make judgements toward what their research are conducted and how the data will be collected and interpreted. Therefore, personal values are very important to support researcher realise the value of decisions making to conclude their data, it also assists researcher enable to explain their judgement towards the study (Saunders, 2009).

In conclusion, as the study aim to examine the impact of social media on banking industry in Vietnam, the researcher desires to investigate from the marketer views such as how banks utilize social media to create strong relationship with customers and take advantages of social media in their marketing strategies. In addition, in order to achieve the customer perspective in term of social media in their daily life and their banking activities, researcher will employ pragmatism philosophy to study the research issues. Due to the important of research question, pragmatism drives the researcher to gain subjectivity on the research and objectivity in data collection and analysis (Morgan, 2017). Especially,

by employing pragmatism, mixed method will be used as the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches (Barker, 2016). According to Creswell (2003), the benefit of the pragmatism paradigm for this research is the best connection between quantitative and qualitative methods, it will bring the best result to answer the research questions.

In order to achieve the research aims, the researcher arranged 9 interviews with key participants in Vietnamese banks through online interview due to the restriction of traveling during pandemic (Covid-19). 152 questionnaires were distributed to those people who mainly work in banks and financial institution to collect their opinion and views about social media. In summary, the mixed method which is suggested by pragmatist approach is used in this research to support identify the role of social media in banking sector and customer behaviour towards social media.

3.3. Research Approach:

Following the Honey Comb model, the second stage is research approach. There are two main approaches that are suggested to researcher such as inductive and deductive (Wilson, 2014). Moreover, in order to support researcher more while conducting study, apart from inductive and deductive, there are retroductive and abductive approaches (Blaikie, 2019). Deductive approach is started with an existing theory or known statement relevant to the research; then following with the constructing of a hypothesis mentioned in literature or existing theories; finally, the hypothesis will be tested in the research strategies (Saunders, 2009). Indeed, the researcher use a deductive approach to expand the literature to collect data and the theory will be developed based on the implementation of data analysis. The deductive approach is the connection of existing theory and hypothesis, hence, the research strategies are advanced to test the hypothesis (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In contrast, the inductive approach begins the observations of specific issues and then generalise the phenomenon. On other words, the inductive approach is based on theory building process in which the observation of the research will be started initially, the data collection will be conducted, and finally, the building process of theory will be developed from data interpretation. However, in another aspect, while using inductive approach, it also involves to collected data from closed-ended questionnaires in quantitative method (Wilson, 2014). Additionally, carrying out one method in this research might causes the limitation of the search. Hence, the selecting both research approach to conduct in the

research will help the researcher more proficient (Creswell and Clark, 2011). In conclusion, the researcher will choose a deductive approach and also adopt some inductive approach in the research process.

Besides, other two research approaches were introduced as retroductive and abductive. Retroductive is considered as a knowledge advancement approach, it involves to the building of constructing models, and the real structure and mechanisms might lead the outcomes the observed effects (Blaikie, 2004). In the meanwhile, the abductive approach is considered as knowledge advancement in social science research, it refers to interpretivism by generating an explanatory hypothesis, concepts and meanings which used by social actors and activities. (Blaikie, 2004 and Ibrahim, 2014). However, this researcher does not select these approach to conduct the research.

3.4. Research strategy:

The next stage of honeycomb model is the research strategy. Choosing the research strategy contribute a vital role in the research process which assists the researcher to have answers for research questions and gain the research aims and objectives. There are three main methods which enable to employ in the research. They are qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods (Saunders et al. 2012). Researcher will select an appropriate method depend on how to achieve the required data to conduct the research. Quantitative research is related to numerical analysis with the data collection methods refers to questionnaires, and it follows by the application of the theoretical framework. The quantitative method tends to understand the view of social life and the data interpretation is statistical analysis. Quantitative methodology is considered as deductive (Wilson, 2014). In contrast, Qualitative research is regarding data collection which can be focus group and interviews, and it is concerned as subjective views. (Dawson, 2009; Creswell, 2013). In another aspect, qualitative method supports the research have a deep insight so that the outcome will able to generate a theoretical framework. Achieving the understanding of social circumstances is one of the main factors while applying qualitative method and the data interpretation would be words rather than numbers (Brikci and Green, 2007).

Mixed method:

Regarding mixed method, it means the research will employ both quantitative method and qualitative method. The observation from interviews and the data from closed-ended

questionnaire will be conducted to generate the best perspective for this research. Therefore, a research is used quantitative and qualitative in combination generate a better understanding of the research issues rather than using one approach separately (Creswell, 2013). According to Venkatesh et al. (2013), mixed method generates deep insights towards diverse phenomena and improve the theoretical views. In other words, the advantage of mixed method research is to support researcher to obtain in – depth understanding and have a sufficient explain concerning organisational and social phenomena. Moreover, applying mixed methods will provide more depth and ranged to the research (Wilson, 2013). Meanwhile, although quantitative method is an effective method to obtain the conclusion with efficient data analysis technique which collected data has come from the huge number of respondents, it still drives the findings with the limited context of the study as the study requires more perspectives and experiences towards both sides customer attitude and bank’s views. Therefore, adding qualitative methods will provide more understanding from research participant’s experiences, it will help the research to maximise the research’s scope. Indeed, qualitative researchers understand that the relationship between researcher and research participants are able to bring the informative outcome through the process of data collection and analysis. Also, the results of the research are interdependent activities between researcher and participants. In the meanwhile, the quantitative study is objective. The research using quantitative method does not depend on the participant activities or relationship between researcher and research’s participants. Based on that, the research strategy of this research basically is concerned both types of research strategy that are quantitative and qualitative methods. Due to the diversity of perspectives of the mixed methods, it will lead to enhance the strength of discussion (Bryman, 2006). Additionally, the study aims to examine how banks utilise social media and social media impact on customer behaviours. Researcher desired to explore both sides banks and customers which will support the research have in-depth perspectives. Therefore, mixed methods will be an appropriate research strategy to implement this study.

3.5. Research design:

Following the Honeycomb model, this chapter will discuss about the research design. In order to achieve the effective research objectives as well as to have a constructive research process, research design is set as a plan to support researcher to conduct the research in particular way. (Wilson, 2014). In facts, the research design built frameworks

or plans which are deployed by researcher throughout the research process. Those aspects such as study plans, study design, data and information collection procedures including interviews, questionnaires, observations or secondary sources will be concerned in research design. According to Yin (2014), case study using in the research design has been described as an in-depth investigation towards topic or it is a phenomenon in its real-life context. On the other hands, the research questions of this study relate to how social media impacts on Vietnam banking sector, thus the case study strategy in research design will be appropriate. There is an in-depth analysis from a particular individual and organisation in banking sector which are offered by case study design (Wilson, 2014). The relevance of data collection from Vietnam are sufficient to conduct the research and moreover it enhances the quality of research outcomes. In other words, the research design of this study using case study will bring the valid and reliable outcome.

3.6. Data collection:

Data collection is the next stage in Honeycomb model. According to Wilson (2014), there are four techniques which has been considered to collect data in the research.

Interviews: This technique refers to the communication between two people or a group in which people will interact to each other through in person meeting, telephone or any kind of online tools and the purpose of the interview has to be prepared and clear. The interviews occur when researcher will ask the respondents or research's participants predetermined questions, those questions and answers were created in open ended types (Kumar, 2014).

Observations: This technique usually refers to qualitative collected data. It is different with interview technique due to researcher's perspective towards events or objects. This data collection method involves the presence or action of researchers; hence the researchers have to systematically and selectively observe, watch, listen and record the subjects or events with their oriented purpose. (Kumar, 2014).

Questionnaires: This technique contains a process of composing a list of questions, sending out or reaching to research's participants/ respondents, collecting the answers via posts, face to face, telephone or online media. Questionnaires can be created by tools on internet and automatically send answers to researchers. This data technique mainly refers

to primary data collection (Kumar, 2014 and Saunders, 2009). Researcher will use this data and gather them to be relevant with the current study.

Secondary data: This data collection technique basically refers to previous sources or collected data for different purposes. On other words, secondary data has been collected and gathered by other researchers for their study. The main sources of secondary data can be studies, statistics, reports, academic books, journals, magazines, newspapers...etc.

For this research, which aims to identify and analyze the impact of social media on customer behaviour in the banking sector, particularly in Vietnam, secondary data will be supplemented with primary data. Social media is an emerging channel in Vietnam's digital banking sector, making it essential of researcher to primarily focus on collecting primary data. Primary data will gathered using closed-ended questionnaires from customers, most of whom are employees of banks or financial institutions. These participants will provide valuable perspectives and experiences regarding banking products and services. Additionally, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with individuals in management positions within banks. These interviews will offer in-depth insights and specific experiences related to the role and potential of social media in Vietnam's financial sector. The collected data are analysed and discussed in the chapter 4 and chapter 5.

3.7. Data analysis techniques:

Follow the Honeycomb model, the data analysis techniques is the final stage to be discussed and to be used to conduct the research. According to Wilson (2014), there are several data techniques which considered to use to analyse the data such as:

Descriptive statistics: This technique involves to statistical procedures which has been used to gather, organise and clarify the data (Beins and McCarthy, 2012). In another aspect, this data technique concerned to the statistical characteristics of the data that used to describe the study in a structured manner. For instance, descriptive statistic technique has been used to measure features of a phenomenon such as mean, mode, medians, min, max, ranges and standard deviations. Hence, it supports the research to obtain more information on particular of data set (Hair et al. 2007 and Kumar, 2014). In the research, the descriptive statistic will be used to summarise all the data collected in which means and standard deviations relates to each other, frequency distributions are used to determine the data into group and indicate the scores in each group. However, the descriptive statistic was

not provided to determine variations as well as do not examine how the variables depend to each other or correlation of variables (Kumar, 2014). Understanding the applications of this technique, the researcher will use it to analyse some part of the primary data which will be present in next chapter for more details.

Inferential statistics: This technique basically supports the researcher to examine the relationships between variables from the population sample. It allows us to make inferences regarding a population based on data that has taken from a sample. The result of single sample will definitely determine the entire population by using inferential statistics. In the other words, this analysis technique involves to the entire population prediction or draw inferences by using a sample of a population, finally gather them to population to indicate how the correlation in between variables (Creswell, 2009). This study used sample collected from primary data (questionnaires) to explain the correlation of variables.

Thematic analysis: This is the method which suitable for qualitative research. By using this analysis technique, the researcher is able to identify, analyse, organise the key themes and explore the empirical data emerging from a data set (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2015). The thematic analysis allows researchers to be more flexible during the analysis process, this is one of the benefits of thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is considered as a research tool which can support researchers in approaching a rich, detailed and complex data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The researcher will apply code based on the collected data which will effortlessly identify key themes. The key themes have been captured the emerged data which are relevant with research aim and objectives. Moreover, this thematic technique brings the trustworthy and in depth sight for the research findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Therefore, this method will be useful for interpreting the collected data from interviews of this research, it drives the research to obtain a rich understanding of each interviews and also develop the key themes which contribute appropriate knowledges and answers towards this study.

3.8. Ethical Considerations:

Ethical extent is one of consideration in conducting the research and data collection. In order to carry out the research, the research followed the research ethics guidelines of University of West of Scotlands (UWS) who approved the data collection process in April 2021 (Appendix A). Basically, a researcher must conduct the research under ethical

principles with an accurate and honest actions. Therefore, the ethical form allowed to figure out any potential risks for participants as well as the risk issues might happen regarding the research. There are certain principles which usually are considered during data collection process such as harmless, make positive thing, respects and justice. Hence, with the ethical form approval, the researcher will need to provide some documents in advance such as participant consent form, participant information sheet. Those documents will secure participants towards confidential data, participant protection during the data collection as well as guarantee their rights at any point of research data collection.

3.9. Data collection and an overview of analysis techniques used in this study:

3.9.1. Questionnaire data collection:

This section will give more details about the data collection strategy and analysis technique to be used to analyse the primary data.

Questionnaire justification:

As the mentioned in the research strategy, the mixed method will be applied in this research, hence, questionnaires are used for data collection in this research as the primary approaches. The research participants will be received the questionnaires and the answers and information will be provided by the respondents (research's participants) (Brikci and Green, 2007). Questionnaire is concerned as a functional tool in the quantitative approach and also offered as the practical data collection technique. By using questionnaire for the data collection, the research can use the relevant information and knowledge to demonstrate the research aim and objective. According to Wilson (2014), questionnaire is considered as the measurement in which researchers identify the questions or questionnaires to bring out the data. These data collected from questionnaire will be appropriate information to answer to the research questions and obtain the research aims and objectives.

This study tends to use online survey questionnaire which is similar to one of the research of Senadheera (2015). The research of Senadheera (2015) also studied about social media in Australian banks. In this research, the researcher designed online survey questionnaires to achieve the data in order to examine the research objectives which relates to influence the social media in Australian banks. The questions were designed based on the factors managing the social media's impacts for communication. Senadheera (2015) employed this survey questionnaire for the research quantitative data to collect data from a

cross-section of a large population and utilise the collected data to examine the behaviour of participants towards social media. For example, Senadheera (2015) distributed 261 questionnaires, and it provided high number of appropriate responses to achieve the data for analysis. However, the difference between this research and the research of Senadheera (2015) is to mainly focus on the customers also known as the bank employees to give their opinions based on both customer views and bank's perspectives. Therefore, the questionnaire in this research aimed to examine the role of social media influences consumer decision on choosing and experiencing the products and services in banking sector and specific in Vietnam. Furthermore, the questionnaires will support researcher to gather informative answers to cover the part of the study about the advantages of social media towards bank's employee views. By employing questionnaires, the data collection and data analysis will develop research objective 1 (to explore the contribution of social media in Vietnamese banking sector) and also expand the research objective 2 (to examine the customer attitudes towards the application of social media marketing).

The type of questionnaire is structured by closed questions which is completely adequate to conduct for the online surveys in this research (Ekinci, 2015 and Jankowicz,2005). Those closed questions will be distributed to those people living in Vietnam and majority of them currently working in banks or financial institutions in Vietnam. Basically, these research's participants are experiencing as social media users and banking customers. In additions, the participants are also bank's employees. Hence, they have a multi perspective concerning the role of social media in the banking sector. As a whole, this study will adopt the closed questionnaire as the method of data collection to justify the research objectives. As a consequence of employing closed questionnaire, the researcher will use the numbers 1-5 to code all the responses of the research's participants, thus, the collected data will be analysed by statistical tools and it will refer to quantitative research.

Questionnaire design:

The design of a questionnaire is formulated specific, rational, logical and based on the research aim, research objectives and also answer the research questions. In this research, the questionnaire was designed based on the factors with respect to social media and customer behaviour towards social media in banking sector. Thus, according to

Oppenheim (2000), in order to structure a questionnaire, there are five typical categories to be concerned:

- Data collection technique plays a vital role in the research, which should be suitable for both researcher and participants. The type of data collection technique can be interview questionnaire, self-completion/postal questionnaire or online. The questionnaire must be distributed in the convenient way. In this research, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher will use online survey to distribute the questionnaire to the participants in Vietnam and in Vietnamese language.
- The way to approach participants to get their acceptance and meet the time requirement are the stage which relates to sending informed consent forms and getting the respondents' acceptance to the survey, and also get the confirmation whether or not the participants are willing to participate in the survey.
- Questionnaire must have a specific and logical layout and structures which will make the participant easy to understand and complete the questionnaire in the willingness.
- Question sequence must be relevant and more particular from the beginning to the last. In other words, the questionnaire must be specified from the general to particular questions.
- Closed questions must be stated with predetermined responses.

Following these stages, the process of the questionnaire designing will be formulated to obtain the study aim and objectives as well as it will be matched with the time, finances, circumstances and location. Therefore, in order to adapt all the factors to conduct the research, researcher decided to use online survey questionnaire via online media to distribute to research's participants.

Design and contents of the study questionnaire:

Questionnaire content design of the research are considered as the important part of set up adequate questions. Questionnaire contents need to be relevant and appropriate to the main structure of the research. In order to be more clarified, the distributed questions must support the study to obtain the research objectives as well as the outcome data will be able to answer the research questions. Based on that, in this study, the questionnaire was

designed to explore how social media play a vital role and contribute generally in business and particularly in banking industry, especially in Vietnamese banking sector. Additionally, the questionnaires were designed to examine the customer behaviour towards social media while they are using banking products and how social media attracts social media users to reach out the banking products and services. Hence, the questionnaire of this research will focus to target to current banking customers in Vietnam.

In order to compose the questionnaires contents, the researcher need to realise some factors which can impact to respondent during the process such as respondent's time, knowledge of the topic (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Moreover, the questionnaires must be designed to meet participatory requirement. The knowledge of the topic must be relevant with the questionnaire in some basic aspects such as language, participant age, and the location of questionnaire distribution. All of these considerations are inevitable for the research in desiring to achieve quality answers from the respondents. In particular, this study all the questions will target to Vietnamese people who tend to use social media and internet for purchasing and looking for product/service information. Also, the questionnaire contents were composed to approach banking employees to gain more information and experience from them. Because, social media in banking sector is not yet covered in a large population in Vietnam at the moment.

The closed questions are designed in this research, this is the adequate questionnaire which will support to reach to research aim and research objective 1, objective 2 and objective 3 of the research questions 1, 2 and 3 (how does the social media contribute in banking sector, especially in Vietnam, how do consumer behave towards banking services and product on social media/social media platforms and what is benefits and challenges of social media in banking industry?). Therefore, in this study, the research questionnaire was appropriately adjusted to make participant easy to answer and help researcher to achieve the data in a proper way.

Following the design of the questionnaire in this research, the questions commonly classified in different section based on the main objectives of the research. In this study, the researcher will investigate the relationship between banking customer and social media power in their daily life. Therefore, the justification of questionnaire below will be backgrounds to compose all the distributed questions.

The demographic information was initially identified in a general questionnaire such as gender, age group, occupation. As the almost of researches, demographic statistics mentioned in any social media are an essential part of data. The brand based on that to create the marketing strategy to approach customer and promote their products and services. Moreover, demographic information has been use as a vital data to determine what social media platform to target customers in researching, advertising and marketing decisions. Therefore, demographics help any brand to understand their audience to more detail (Chen, 2020). For instance, in another research, Park and Lee (2014) stated that women are using smartphones to express themselves more via the social networks rather than males. Female are spending more time with friends to develop deeper and intimate friendship and relationship on Facebook compared to males (Thompson and Loughheed, 2012). Therefore, the gender statistic in questionnaire plays a significant in targeting customers for a particular business. Besides, age group is also considered in this study questionnaire. Furthermore, in order to plan a marketing campaign and selecting a specific social media platform for deploying a promotion campaign, a business need to figure out which platforms are current trend towards different age group, for instance Facebook for all type of customers, Instagram for young customers and who concern about attractive images. In this study, the occupation yvis important, because the research intended to achieve a perspective not only from banking customers, it is also from the banking employees. Hence, one of the question was designed to concern whether or not the participant works in a bank or financial institutions. Those people currently work in banks or financial institutions will have an insight view regarding social media in banking rather than a normal customer. Basically, a beta version of any marketing channels in general and social media in particular has been launched by banks, employees usually are experienced and investigate the effectiveness of that. Therefore, the occupation in this study will be considered as the main question to be more adequate in data (Farook and Abeysekara, 2016).

Time spending on social media: Basically, the researcher intended to composed this question with the purpose to explore how people concern about social media while purchasing or researching products and services on internet. For instance, Facebook is currently one of the popular platform which are chose to deploy many marketing campaigns by brands. Base on US Facebook user statistic by Pew Research, approximately three

quarter of Facebook users visit the site on a daily basis in which 51% users visit several times per day (Sproutsocial, 2020). Based on that, the research composes this question to determine the concern of customer towards social media in purchasing.

Type of social platforms: In order to maximize a brand awareness on social media including engaging potential customers and obtaining social media marketing goals, which suitable platform will be highly considered by business (Lua, 2018). Currently, Facebook and YouTube are two biggest social media site where businesses are expanding their presence with diversity content formats such as video sharing, stories, images...etc. Therefore, in term of asking participants which social media sites are one of important element to determine the specific strategy in choosing a particular social media platform.

The next section of the questionnaire in this research, the researcher will design as to cover the contribution of social media on daily basis:

Elements of questionnaire	Justification of questionnaire design
Social media creates communities that can be influenced human interactions.	This questionnaire element is to investigate the role of social media towards the community in general. Every day billions of people are engaged with social media, creating huge numbers of connections, thus the human interaction essentially has been developed more by social media. In other words, social media has built an online community so people can communicate and be influenced by each other (Hansen, Shneiderman, & Smith, 2011).
People based on social media to make a decision	This element of questionnaire refers to social media users to be affected while making a decision. Social media has expanded the Internet not only to be a source of information, but also a source of influence (Smith, 2015).
Social media inspired people to have a better life.	This element of questionnaire is designed to figure out the beneficial aspects social media. Social media is not only support people find the convenient way to connect and communicate to each other, on the other hand, it also provided many people a place to sort out their own

	problem by getting advices and obtain positive information from social media communities.
Social media provide more information and useful knowledge	This element of questionnaire is to investigate the role of social media in some sort of useful technologies, knowledge, sources towards social media users or internet user in general. Social media is an obvious tool to generate new opportunities and capture interdisciplinary knowledge, with variety of information to users. Many reliable information are sharing on the social media by different methods.
Social media platforms where people enable express experiences and opinions freely.	This element of the questionnaire refers to the large scope of social media. It allows people to express their opinion freely and, there is less restriction on social media. Social media create an environment for people to freely interact and express their attitude.
Social media is addictive	This element of the questionnaire is concerned social media drive users being so addictive. Social media is becoming very popular on internet with many interesting features and play as an instant channel to update and spread information in fastest way, therefore, the fear of missing out is one of the leading factors of social media addiction. Moreover, other people daily life and attractive contents also creates the addiction to people.

Questionnaire was designed regarding social media contributions on purchasing behavior:

Element of questionnaire	Justification of questionnaire design
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<p>Social media is a tool that significant contributes to communication effectiveness.</p>	<p>This element of the questionnaire is concerning whether or not social media contribute to communication. Social media is considered as a tool to bring more benefits for both customers and businesses. A major advantage of social media is to help businesses reach out and communicate to customer directly through social media platforms. In another aspect, by using social media as a communication channel, customers enable to contact brands or businesses with timely responses.</p>
<p>Social media is a tool which improves the performance of marketing campaigns to attract users</p>	<p>This element refers to the benefits of social media in marketing and campaign deployment. Using social media to place marketing campaigns and to reinforce information about products and services is one of the effective choice of many brands. It supports brands/businesses to improve their marketing performance to achieve a specific goal in a set period of time, moreover the outcomes can be tracked and measured (Cyca, 2020).</p>
<p>Social media platforms enhance information spreading.</p>	<p>This questionnaire element refers to the social media ability of information spreading. Brands or businesses use social media with the main purpose is to reach out as many customer as possible. Social media platform is a place where brands' messages linked to customer in both direct and indirect way, because social media platform is a personal channel of each user where they connect to their friends and followers. This is the best way for brands to utilize to expand customer data base through spreading ability. For instance, in micro blogs such as Twitter, by a simple retweet, messages spread to a numerous people on that platforms or even share to many other social networks.</p>
<p>Social media build the value and trust between users and brands.</p>	<p>This element of the questionnaire is concerned more about the people reliability towards brands through social media. Businesses or brands utilize social media platform not only as a channel to promote products or services, it also to create a deeper relationship with their customers and build a community around. Interactions between people on social media help to build the brand trust. Indeed, people is</p>

	more likely to rely on each other to seek for help on social media. Therefore, businesses or brand enable to take advantage of this ability to build the trust between them and their customers.
Social media creates opportunities to reach to different brands while considering to purchases good and services.	This element of the questionnaire is more about expanding the customer purchasing on social media. Basically, there are many factor such as social influencers, social ads, even friends on social media play a significant role on choosing a specific product. Hence, social media creates many opportunities to reach out many various ideas regarding products or services selection. For instance, social media influencer is an effective tool to support customer in purchasing, this helps customer easier and more familiar with brands, thus, they will have more options to purchase products or services.
Advertising strategy of brands on social media affects people in considering a specific product/service.	This questionnaire element is concerned more about the trend of various advertising on social media. Especially, social media is evolving day by day with new social media platform and new updated trends. Therefore, the different kind of advertisement on social media drives customer to be more attracted towards products or services. In additions, it make brands more stand out in their market.

Questionnaire was designed regarding the role of social media in banking industry:

Element of questionnaire	Justification of questionnaire design
The frequency of using social media for banking activities is one of important factor towards the advantage of social media in banking industry	This questionnaire element has been created to initially investigate how participants concern banking services on social media. As the development of social media in all over the world, most of Vietnamese banks or financial institutions take advantage of social media as one of the main marketing channel to deploy marketing campaign as well as expand their social network. Furthermore, banking products is quite typical to compare

	<p>with others, using social media to look for banking information or promotion campaigns is not too familiar with Vietnamese social media users. Therefore, this questionnaire is designed to explore the important of social media toward banking customers.</p>
<p>Banking activities on social media</p>	<p>This element of the questionnaire basically investigate which banking activities has the most concern on social media. Banks or financial institutions use social media not only for marketing strategy, they also tend to improve other field such as customer service, financial or banking knowledge updating and training. Banks desire to be more flexible their strategy to obtain more customer interaction on social media. Based on that, meeting customer expectation and maintaining relationship between banks and customers will be more effortlessly. Additionally, Hence, understanding which banking activity has been concerned the most on social media will support bank to deeply reach out the demands of customer.</p>
<p>(1) Main purposes are applied in social media by banks: (2) Raising brand awareness (3) Expanding a relationship with existing and potential customers (4) Reducing marketing and advertising costs (5) Attracting customers with interesting contents.</p>	<p>This element of the questionnaire refers to the multiple-choice questions supports the researcher to mainly explore the understanding of participants who are working in banking industry, how their bank take advantages toward social media marketing strategy and how the bank utilized social media to achieve the best outcomes. According to Goodman (2021) social media marketing created solutions for many banks during marketing plan designing process. Many banking criteria is being beneficial by applying social media such as raising brand awareness, reducing marketing cost and retaining customers.</p>

<p>As a banking or financial institutions employee, the interviewer would be asked which factor banks should take it as the successful social media tactics to attract their customers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (6) Being visual on social media (7) Focusing on customer service (8) Inviting Influencers/Celebrities (9) Educating and providing financial advice to their customers/followers on social media (10) Educating and providing financial advice to their customers/followers on social media (11) Engaging with Interactive contents 	<p>This element of the questionnaire is designed to achieve the opinions on how their bank has been successful in applying social media to approach customers. As per, the researcher is able to analyze deeply in customer perspectives toward social media in banking industry. Additionally, many updated factors of social media which have been using to obtain more effective. Therefore, bank can use it to examine requirements customers more accurate.</p>
<p>Rating customer satisfaction with benefits from social media toward banking services</p>	<p>This questionnaire element is concerned in almost questionnaire in general. It is very important to listen customer opinions and experience. The rating of customer satisfaction explains the trust with the banks. Also, it affects</p>

	to the research while analyzing how the bank strengthen relationships between customer and banks. Especially, during the pandemic, social media plays a vital role in maintaining relationships because people spend more time on using internet as well as social media. Therefore, this opens more opportunities to banks to understand customer demands and reach their satisfaction.
What kind of risks can be occurred once using social media for banking activities	This element concerns about risks while using social media to look for banking information or seek for banking products. As a banker, participants tend to understand the risks occur while implementing social media marketing in their bank. For instance, a security issue can be shared quickly by consumers and the bank’s reputation can easily be damaged. As per, building and keeping the position of the bank’s brand as a safe and secure provider of financial services is key.

3.9.2. Questionnaire structure:

The closed ended questionnaire has been using in this study and will be completed by almost banking customers in Vietnam. As the mentioned in the previous section above. Questionnaire of this study are divided into 3 section. All these sections will support the research to cover objectives and the research questions. The first section of the questionnaire concerned about demographic factors and the further questions on social media application of participant’s daily life which was introduce to collect additional information for the first stage of social media role in people life. The second section are mainly designed as Likert scale questions by using 5 points ranging from 1 = strongly disagreed to 5 = strongly agreed. This section mostly focus on the role of social media as well as the factors of social media affect to participant’s life in general. The Likert scale type questionnaire is usually applied in social sciences to assess people attitude (Gliem and Gliem, 2003). In this research, the Likert scale considered the respondent time pressures and reasonable reliability and validity. The last section of the questionnaire was designed to measure the impact of social media on banking sector and also evaluate the customer

satisfaction towards social media in banking. The Likert scale questions also are applied to determine the participant's opinions. Therefore, the validity and reliability are enhanced the use of the questionnaire and these factors will be discussed in the next part.

3.9.3. Reliability and Validity of questionnaire:

The questionnaire of this research will be tested the reliability and validity. The need of reliability and validity test of questionnaire are very important due to desiring a good research. Reliability concerns about the stability of the findings and validity considers to the trustfulness (Altheide and Johnson, 1994). According to Saunder et al (2009), the data collection method has been assessed by the reliability and validity. Additionally, reliability and validity has been applied to improve the accuracy of assessment and the research outcomes.

Reliability: Reliability concerns about the consistency and stability of outcome which is provided by a measurement (Blumberg et al., 2005). The reliability is high will make the result is more accurate, therefore, it will enhance the decision making for a good research. In this research, Cronbach's Alpha correlation coefficients were used to measure the reliability of the research instrument (Saunder et al., 2009). The research instrument should not be used if the reliability is low. According to Oluwatayo (2012) the Cronbach's Alpha correlation coefficient (α) of the research instrument has been measured, and (α) should be in the range from 0.7 to 0.9. The higher value of (α) will reflect the high reliability of the factors or instrument (Robbins, 2009). Especially, when the Cronbach's Alpha correlation coefficient close to 1.0, the consistency of the measured factor is very high, however because (α) is too high which means that factor is redundant. Whereas, measured factor has lower value of (α) (less than 0.6), it indicates that this factor should be removed and not valid.

Validity: It plays an important role during research process. Validity is considered as a measurement to assess the research instrument whether is trustful or not. Hence, the validity is applied to determine that questionnaire (research instrument) measure what is intended to measure in a research study.

3.9.4. Sample techniques:

In order to bring out a best representation of population during the selecting the research sample, it is very vital in choosing an appropriate sampling to ensure the

effectiveness, cost and ethical issue for a research (Creswell, 2015). There are two types of sampling to be used to conduct sample selection which call probability and non-probability sampling. In this study, non- probability sampling was used to select sample. It is also considered as purposive and quota sampling strategies that is used to determine the appropriate respondents. The purposive sampling or quota sampling was the adequate sampling design which enable to handle a limited population to provide informative results for the research regardless of the time and cost restriction during the data collection process. Additionally, the outcome will appropriately represent for the whole population (Sekeran and Bougie, 2013). By using non- probability sampling technique, all the characteristics of selected population will be represented by sample (Saunders, 2012). Therefore, the researcher chose this sample technique which will support the research select a sample not randomly, it is purposive. In this research, the banking environment is quite specific in a developing country like Vietnam where people has tended to prefer face to face while reaching out any banking products and services. Social media in banking is emerging since few years, therefore in order to have appropriate statistics and knowledges about social media in financial in general or banking in particular. Almost selected participants of this research were financial institution or banking employees. These participants will present for those people have an insight knowledge or experiences towards social media in banking. The sample size was determined by the respondents of the questionnaire. Based on that, employees who currently work in top leading banks in Vietnam such as Vietcombank, Vietinbank, BIDV, Agribank, HSBC, VPbank were approached to distribute the questionnaire. The researcher reached out to leading bank in Vietnam because their marketing system has been operated wider on social media than other small banks. The questionnaire was sent to the respondents via their personal social media page. The questionnaire was created by Google online survey tool to obtain the responses in the fastest way during the Covid 19 pandemic and due to the travel restriction. The sample size of the study was 180 respondents and results of the response were quite positive with 85% of respondent completed the survey. The data was collected in the first two weeks of May 2021.

3.9.5. Data Description:

This section describes the variable used in the data analysis by using descriptive statistics and inferential statistic.

Social media influences human behaviour: There are 5 variables which were symbolised as SM1 to SM5 (as described in detail in Table 1 of Chapter IV). These variables will be used in descriptive statistic to measure the human behaviour towards social media with five item scale using Likert-scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagreed to 5 = Strongly agreed. The findings of this data would tell the impacts of social media towards the participant's daily life in different aspects as well as the influential components of social media drive the human behaviour.

Social media in customer purchasing: Five variables were symbolised as SMP1 to SMP5 (as described in Table 1 of chapter IV). These variables also will be used in descriptive statistic to measure the customer purchasing behaviour on social media with Likert Scale. The data findings would tell how social media contributes to purchasing behaviour of participants and which influential factors would be more effective choice towards decision making of customer purchasing.

Purposes of Social media in banking: There are 4 variables which were symbolised as SMBK1 to SMBK4 (as described in Table 1 of chapter IV). As the same as two constructs above. These variables will be used in descriptive statistic to measure how banks utilise social media to drive their strategy to approach customer as well as improve their marketing strategy. The findings of this data will tell which particular factors impacts more than others, based on the it supports researcher to have an insight perspective to explain the research objective.

Social media risks in banking: In this construct, there are 3 variables which were symbolized as RSM1 to RSM3 (as describe in Table 1 of chapter IV). These variables will be used in descriptive statistic to measure the potential risks of social media in banking sectors. The findings will indicate how the risks has been concerned while using social media to reach out banking products and services from the participants.

Customer satisfactions: There are 4 variables which were symbolized as CS1 to CS4 (as described in Table 1 of chapter IV). These variables will be used in descriptive statistic with four item scale using Likert Scale again range from 1 = strongly dissatisfied to 5 = strongly satisfied. The findings of this data play significantly to measure the trust of customers to their bank when bank use social media to approach and meet customer requirement.

Demographic variables such as Age group, Gender, Spending time on social media, advertisement on social media, social media platforms, banking activities, social media tactics in banking will be used in inferential statistic to measure the correlation of variables. By carrying out the inferential statistic, the significance of (p) value will be determined to test the relationship between those variables in ANOVA (Analysis of variance). ANOVA is considered to determine whether the relationship is relevant or not in two or more than two variables. Therefore, in this study, ANOVA test will be used to identify the relationship different demographic towards other variables of social media or banking. In another aspect, in order to analyse the correlation of data, Spearman's correlation coefficient is also used as nonparametric measure of the association between two variables. According to Sedgwick (2016), the Spearman correlation coefficient with values ranging from -1 through 0 to +1. If the correlation coefficient close to -1 or +1 which indicates the great association of variables, whereas if the correlation coefficient is -1 or +1 which indicate a monotonic relationship. If the correlation coefficient is exactly 0 which means there is no association between variables. Additionally, if the correlation is positive which indicate that increasing or decreasing of one variable would have been associated with the increasing or decreasing of other variables, while on the contrary, if the correlation is negative, the relationship would be negative.

3.10. Analysis technique of interview:

3.10.1. Thematic Analysis:

In order to analyse the collected data from interviews, the researcher will apply qualitative thematic analysis to analyse the data in the chapter 5. Qualitative thematic analysis will support the research to reach the objective 3 of the research which will mainly evaluate the opportunities and the challenges of applied social media in Vietnam banking sector. In addition, it investigates the research participants' experience and perspective of social media in banking because those participants are working in high position in Vietnamese banks. According to Braun and Clarke (2006) thematic analysis is a technique which supports the researcher to identify, analyse and report themes towards collected data. Researcher will use this method to sort out and describe the data in rich information. Indeed, thematic analysis is very practical tool to assist the researcher enable to analyse the huge

amount data that collected from many participants. All the collected data will be systematically combine into the adequate account. Furthermore, the thematic analysis has been utilised as a designed methodology to generate the key themes within a dataset and it is quite flexible. There is some suggestion has been provided while applying the thematic analysis. It is vital to identify the emerging theme to reflect the content of the entire data set. This thematic analysis probably support as a particular method to create a rich description of the data set. Additionally, a particular theme within the data will be provided more detailed and shaped by using thematic analysis. In another context, Boyatzis (1998) argued that thematic analysis was considered to be used along with various other approaches. In order to implement this analysis, all the text would be broken down and narrow at the first stage. Following that, transcript coding, themes identification and thematic construction would be implemented to reduce the texts.

Therefore, based on the suggestion of Braun and Clarke (2006), in this research inductive thematic analysis was conducted to achieve informative outcomes. In order to develop the emerging themes, the analysis would start from the interview transcripts. Furthermore, in order not to involve biases, by using inductive approach, the researcher concentrated to the experiences and perspective of research's participants to explain and develop the research objectives instead of confirmation of the existing literature.

3.10.2. Interview protocol:

Following the design of the interview protocol will be began with the background of the research and research aim which the researcher would like to conduct. By providing this detail of the study background, the interview will facilitate to reach out the participants in the comfort ways. In other words, the brief of the study was outlined to participants to understand the interview purposes. The researcher investigates the overview and perspective of 9 participants who are based on the high position in Vietnam banks and have experience towards banking marketing. Participant expressed their experiences and perspective of the development of social media in marketing strategies. The key information is to understand the advantages and disadvantages that banks have experienced during implementing social media marketing in different aspects. By using semi structured interview protocol, the participants were asked to sign the content form to give the permission to the interview as well as to use the data subsequently. According to the privacy

and confidential information, all the personal information of the participant for the interview was disclosed. Due to Covid19 pandemic, all the interviews took place via telephone and virtual meetings.

In summary, the thematic analysis will be applied to explore the semi structured data from the interviews, it will bring the outcomes to evaluate the opportunities and challenges of social media in banking sectors which meet the requirement to reach out the research objective.

Summary:

In conclusion, this research methodology chapter has discussed in detail the methodological approach and research analysis technique to be adopted in this research. By using the main Honey comb model of Wilson (2014) for research methodology, each stage of the model including research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection and data analysis have been explained how to apply in the study. Furthermore, it demonstrates to enhance the structure of the research topic by mentioning the detail of the data technique to be used to analyse the data. The research approach and mixed method strategy were appropriately adopted to implement as well as support to generate a good outcome of the research. The following chapter will be explored the empirical data to enhance the research objectives.

Chapter 4. Analysis/Interpretation of questionnaires:

4.1. Variables used data analysis:

Regarding Likert Scale questionnaires, in order to understand the analyzed data easier, all statements in the questionnaire have been symbolized simply. The below table shows the details. In additions, as the mentioned data analysis techniques, the researcher will show the descriptive statistics and inferential statistic of the presented variables in the next section of this chapter. Based on the data analysis, the further discussion of hypothesis of will be followed by this section.

Constructs	Symbols	Statements used in the questionnaire
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Social media influences human behaviour	SM1	Degree of agreement towards “Social media creates communities that can influence human interactions”
	SM2	Degree of agreement towards “People rely on social media to make a decision”
	SM3	Degree of agreement towards “Social media inspires people to have a better life”
	SM4	Degree of agreement towards “Social media provides more information and useful knowledge”
	SM5	Degree of agreement towards “Social media platforms are where people enable express their experiences and opinions freely”
	SM6	Degree of agreement towards “Social media is addictive and an engaging tool that exists in the user's lives”
Social media in customer purchasing	SMP1	Degree of agreement towards “Social media is a tool that significantly contributes to communication effectiveness”
	SMP2	Degree of agreement towards “Social media is a tool to improve the performance of marketing campaigns to attract users”
	SMP3	Degree of agreement towards “Social media platforms enhance information spreading”
	SMP4	Degree of agreement towards “Social media builds value and trust between users and brands”
	SMP5	Degree of agreement towards “Social media creates opportunities for users to approach various brands while considering to purchase goods and services”

Purposes of Social media in banking	SMBK1	Degree of agreement towards “Raising brand awareness”
	SMBK2	Degree of agreement towards “Expanding relationship with existing and potential customers”
	SMBK3	Degree of agreement towards “Reducing marketing and advertising costs”
	SMBK4	Degree of agreement towards “Attracting customers with diversified content”
Social media risks in banking	RSM1	Degree of agreement towards “Social media platform of banks is less trustworthy”
	RSM2	Degree of agreement towards “Social media is not secure once customers provide information to get support”
	RSM3	Degree of agreement towards “Social media might influence customer negatively in choosing banking service or being loyal”
	CS1	Degree of satisfaction towards “High quality in interactive support”
	CS2	Degree of satisfaction towards “Customer expectations gained towards banking service”
		Degree of satisfaction towards “Information provided on social media platforms of the bank are supportive”
	CS4	Degree of satisfaction towards “Better and faster responses to compare with branch banking service”

Table 1: Variables used in data analysis.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics:

All data was collected from people who currently live and work in Vietnam, almost of them work in banks in Vietnam. The survey has a sample 152 participants out of 180 questionnaires sent out, which accounts for approximately 85%. As per the result of participants, this is quite a high level of participation, thus, the responses are very reliable and can be representative for the majority.

4.2.1. Reliability Statistic:

In order to examine the reliability of the responses, researcher use a Cronbach's alpha coefficient to test the data collected by all questions using multiple item scales. All the social media influences human behaviour, social media in purchasing, purposes of social media in banking, social media risks in banking and customer satisfaction. All the data of these questions will be analysed by SPSS software to generate Cronbach's alpha coefficient. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), reliability refers to consistency, internal consistency is measured to investigate the correlation of the responses to each question in the questionnaire. Although there are different methods to test the internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha is the most frequently method to indicate the reliability of the data. An acceptable of reliability is indicated by value of Cronbach's alpha range between 0.7 to 0.8, while a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.8 indicates a very good level of reliability.

According to figures from table 2, Cronbach's alpha value of social media influences human behaviour is 0.793 which is acceptable. Besides, the Corrected Item-Total Correlation column tells the correlations of each question (r), in which r value of all greater than 0.3 indicates all questions do not need to remove. This questionnaire is reliable.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.793	.805	6

Item–Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item–Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SM influences human behaviour	20.99	5.901	.618	.446	.755
SM2	21.12	4.873	.669	.509	.729
SM3	21.62	4.728	.575	.349	.762
SM4	21.24	5.629	.500	.261	.772
SM5	20.68	6.151	.517	.290	.773
SM6	21.12	5.615	.491	.269	.774

Table 2: Cronbach’s alpha value of questionnaire scale on Social media influences human behaviour

As can be seen in Table 3, Cronbach’s alpha value of social media in purchasing is 0.744 which is greater than 0.7 for high internal consistency. Besides, the Corrected Item–Total Correlation column shows all the value of the correlations (r) of each question are greater than 0.3. It means the questionnaire of social media in purchasing is reliable and questions do not need to delete out of this questionnaire.

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.744	.761	5

Item–Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item–Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SM influences purchasing	16.76	2.517	.643	.513	.656
SMP2	16.68	2.498	.608	.544	.665
SMP3	16.58	2.629	.471	.328	.712
SMP4	17.37	2.459	.378	.216	.764
SMP5	16.86	2.535	.508	.277	.698

Table 3: Cronbach's alpha of questionnaire scale on Social media influences customer purchasing

Cronbach's alpha coefficient of social media influences banking activities in Table 4 is 0.716 which is not really high internal consistency but still greater than 0.7. This questionnaire is still considered reliable. The Corrected Item-Total Correlation column shows the correlations (r) of one question is less than 0.3 which is 0.278. It means this question SMBK 3 is considered to remove to make the Cronbach's alpha value higher as 0.828 which is high consistency, however the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of this questionnaire is still reliable with 0.716. Therefore, researcher will retain all the questions.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.716	.749	4

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Purposes of SM in banking	12.57	1.703	.647	.579	.576
SMBK2	12.43	1.690	.640	.594	.578
SMBK3	13.13	1.797	.278	.081	.828
SMBK4	12.49	1.801	.561	.362	.625

Table 4: Cronbach's alpha of questionnaire scale on Social media influences banking activities

Table 5 describe Cronbach's alpha coefficient of questionnaire scale on social media risks is 0.818 and Table 6 demonstrates the Cronbach's alpha value is 0.828 for questionnaire of Customer satisfaction. These figures are both greater than 0.8 so that can be considered good reliability. Additionally, the correlation (r) value in both questionnaires are higher than 0.3 therefore all the items will be retained.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.818	.823	3

Item–Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item–Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Risks of SM	5.97	1.483	.745	.714	.684
RSM2	5.88	1.271	.784	.736	.625
RSM3	5.47	1.562	.512	.272	.912

Table 5: Cronbach’s alpha of questionnaire scale on Risk in SM

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.828	.839	4

Item–Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item–Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Customer Satisfaction	10.77	1.940	.787	.734	.727
CS2	10.75	1.964	.777	.752	.733
CS3	10.78	1.866	.720	.578	.753
CS4	10.88	2.238	.402	.171	.903

Table 6: Cronbach’s alpha of questionnaire scale on Customer satisfaction

Overall, all the questionnaire scale of the research has high internal consistency which indicates all likert scale questionnaire has reliability statistic. Thus, research will carry on measure the normality of distribution in the next part.

According to Cohen and Holliday (1996), the normality of the distribution of collected data is concerns vitally in quantitative research. Therefore, in order to measure the data normality of distribution, there are two values called Skewness and kurtosis will be used to indicate the normal distribution of the questionnaire. Researcher continues to use SPSS to measure the value for Skewness and Kurtosis in which Skewness basically measures the relative size of the two tails, while the Kurtosis measures the combined size of two tails. The acceptable range for skewness is from -2 to +2 and the idea value for kurtosis is from -7 to +7 which to demonstrates normal distribution (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Those figures in Table 7 below shows values of skewness and kurtosis of all scales for social media influences human behaviour (SM), social media in purchasing (SMP), social media influences banking activities (SMBK), social media risks (RSM), and customer satisfactions (CS) are indicated acceptable values in the ideal range. Hence, as per the statistic of both skewness and kurtosis of questionnaire scales, the collected data is normally distributed.

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SM	152	4.2259	-.057	.197	-.296	.391
SMP	152	4.2118	.596	.197	-.562	.391
SMBK	152	4.2187	.115	.197	-.126	.391
RSM	152	2.8882	.131	.197	-.678	.391
CS	152	3.5987	-.612	.197	-.809	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152					

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics indicating normality of questionnaire scales

4.2.2. Descriptive statistics for demographics:

The demographic statistic has a significant effect to social media marketing of any industry which is used to analysed human behaviour towards product or services. In this

research, the distribution of gender with the sample size of the population in this survey is displayed in the Table 8 as below. The contribution of participants is female with 77% (117 female participants) which accounts for the majority of participant. The remaining of participant are male which accounts for 23% (35 male participants). This statistic indicates that there is a significant higher number of female participants contribute into this survey compared to male, therefore the figures tells the social media concerns of women is more than men. However, the role of gender participants toward other factors will be explained more detail in the next section.

Following by the table 9 as below, the majority of participant contribution for this survey belongs to young and middle generations which accounts for 55.3% and 40.8% from age group (18-29) and (30-39) respectively. In can be concluded that social media influences and plays a vital role to Gen Y and Gen Z compare with old generation (over 40 in age group). There is very small number of participant in old generation with only more than 4% of the contribution in this survey.

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	117	77.0	77.0	77.0
	Male	35	23.0	23.0	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics for Gender

		Age group			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 to 29	84	55.3	55.3	55.3
	30 to 39	62	40.8	40.8	96.1
	40 to 49	5	3.3	3.3	99.3
	50 and older	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics for Age group

As can be seen in the table 10 below, the vast majority of participant is currently working in finance environment, particularly in banks. The statistic in the table shows nearly 90% of the participant works in the banks which demonstrates the distribution mostly concentrate in the bank environment, thus, it can help the research more effective due to the research concerns social media in banking.

Working in finance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	15	9.9	9.9	9.9
	Prefer not to say	1	.7	.7	10.5
	Yes	136	89.5	89.5	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics for finance workplace.

In conclusion, the discussion of the demographics of the participants in the sample size has presented in this section which describes the contribution of the demographics to social media. The descriptive statistic various variables will be continued to present in the subsequent section in this research.

4.2.3. Descriptive statistics for social media in general:

As per the table 11 below, almost of the participants use social media for daily basis with 99% of the participant using social media every day in browsing internet. Indeed, it is not surprising that the majority of participant use social media, it is due to the fact that social media dramatically play an important role in people like such as entertainment, information searching, purchasing and getting support from society in very fast way. In another aspect, it is quite common for joining online society through social media. Therefore, the figure indicates the reality of using social media in young generation and even in educated people because base on the statistic of the previous section, the majority of participant has a job in banks.

Using social media

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	1	.7	.7	.7
	Yes	151	99.3	99.3	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 11: Descriptive Statistics for using social media

As can be observed from table 12, more than a half of participant spends 1 to 3 hours per day on social media with different purposes which accounts for 64.5%. With this number of the percentage towards the spending time on social media, which indicates that there would be many activities on social media to attract internet users. These participants who spend more than 3 hours per day on social media contributing a minority with 8%, however these participants can be considered to do jobs relates to social media, and generate more value for society via social media.

Time to spend on SM					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-3 hours	98	64.5	64.5	64.5
	3-5 hours	11	7.2	7.2	71.7
	Less than an hour	42	27.6	27.6	99.3
	More than 5 hours (Your job probably relates to social media)	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 12: Descriptive Statistics for time to spend on social media.

As per the table 13 below, social media platforms are considered as tools for user to access social media. Although the variety of social media platforms operate widely in Vietnam as well as approach to social media users recently, Facebook is still the most chosen platform for using social media, which accounts for 53.9% participants. It is effortlessly to understand due to high interaction and coverage of Facebook. As the consequence, the figure shows that both parties including sellers, brands and customers have an attraction with Facebook for purchasing intention and reaching customer. However, with the improvement of Instagram and Youtube, there is still nearly a half of participant chose these two platforms for their purchasing which contributes 28.9% and

15.8% respectively. It demonstrates the social media marketing strategy of brands on Instagram and Youtube currently approach customers in pretty particular way to compare with Facebook.

SM platform for purchasing

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Facebook	82	53.9	53.9	53.9
	Instagram	44	28.9	28.9	82.9
	Other platforms (Tiktok, Twitter,...)	2	1.3	1.3	84.2
	YouTube	24	15.8	15.8	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics for social media platform.

Table 14 below demonstrates the typical advertisement types on social media which attract social media users. As can be seen in the table 14, people use social media mainly to interact and communicate each other, therefore the reviews and recommendation of other people about a specific products or services contribute higher concerns to compare with other factors which accounts for more than 30% participants. However, in order to attract more customers, social media marketing strategy of brands recently hire celebrities or famous people who has significantly influence to people on social media to spread their reviews. The figure presents for this factor also contributes 27% concerns of participants. Additionally, another social media marketing strategy is to create an attractive contents, images and videos to attract customers, this type of advertisement accounts for quarter of participants with 25%. The last factors for advertisement on social media is social ads which displays frequently on customer’s social media as a new feed or pop up ads. Although the figure of this factor is not as high as other factors (with 17.8%), social ads are still considered as a common strategy on social media.

Advertisement on social media

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Reviews from users on the brand's social media	46	30.3	30.3	30.3
	Reviews of social media influencers	41	27.0	27.0	57.2
	Shared posts of attractive contents and images of the product/service on social media	38	25.0	25.0	82.2
	Social Ads	27	17.8	17.8	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics for advertisement on social media.

4.2.4. Descriptive statistics for social media in banking industry:

Having a discussed above about social media in general, in this section we can see figures which describe how social media influences banking industry in Vietnam throughout participants in the survey. As can be seen in table 15, also based on the demographic statistic, social media plays a vital role with participants, the majority of participants use social media to search for banking information which accounts for 93.4%. It demonstrates that the social media is not only a purchasing tool for retail industries such as fashion, it also generates benefits for those who concerns about finance and banking services. Regarding what kind of banking activities has been searched the most on social media, the table 16 indicates that customer service is a factor to be searched the most with more than one third of the participants (40%) while information of banking services accounts less with 33.6% and followed by promotions factor with 24.3%. As per these statistics, we can understand that the interaction between banks and customer is literally important on social media. Moreover, due to Covid 19 pandemic, seeking supports from the bank through social media page is more convenient rather than call centre or branch walk-in. In additions, as the discussions in the previous section about daily spending time on social media, with the majority of participant spends appropriately 3 hours on social media, therefore the searching towards banking services and promotion campaigns is adequate. Instead of spending more time to seek these information in different channels, users apparently prefer looking for needed information on social media.

SM for banking activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	10	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Yes	142	93.4	93.4	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 15: Descriptive Statistics for banking activities.

		Banking activity			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Customer service	61	40.1	40.1	40.1
	Marketing/Promotions	37	24.3	24.3	64.5
	Products/services researching	51	33.6	33.6	98.0
	Recruitment	3	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 16: Descriptive Statistics for banking activities in social media.

For the purpose of attracting customers, as can be seen in table 17 below, also as the participant experiences and predictions, social media tactics which banks consider to attract customer in a particular way are being more visual on social media and to enhance engaging with interactive contents. These two factors account for a half of participants with 25.7% for both factors. Hence, these figures demonstrate that banks would have to invest more in their brand awareness on social as well as focus more on creating contents to attract more interactive from customers. Additionally, the tactic relates to educating and providing financial advice also contributes significantly to a successful strategy of banks (with 21% of participants chose this factor). It means they have a concern with banks advice and desires to get more knowledge about bank service on social media, therefore they prefer banks provide particular information relating to banking on bank's social media page. The last two tactic factors are focusing on customer service and inviting influencers to attract more customers which account for 12.5% and 13.2% respectively. As a consequence, this

statistic explained social media strategies which are considered more appropriate with the banks to approach customers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Being visual on social media	39	25.7	25.7	25.7
	Educating and providing financial advice to their customers/followers on social media	32	21.1	21.1	46.7
	Engaging with interactive contents	39	25.7	25.7	72.4
	Focusing on customer service	19	12.5	12.5	84.9
	Inviting Influencers/Celebrities	20	13.2	13.2	98.0
	Not applicable (if you are not working in the banking industry)	3	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

Table 17: Descriptive Statistics for social media tactics towards banking.

4.3. Descriptive statistic (Likert Scale):

4.3.1. Descriptive statistic for Social media influences human behavior:

Table 11 below presents the descriptive statistics for social media influences human behaviour (SM1-SM6) of 152 participants who take part in the survey of this research. As per the statistics, in general it can be concluded that the majority of participants agreed that the social media have affected to human behaviour in their life. The figures show the mean value range from 3.75 to 4.67 and the range of a standard deviation is from 0.471 to 0.851 in all researched factors. As can be seen the mean values of this questionnaire, the values are fairly close to rating 5 = “Strongly Agreed” to the studied factors. Therefore, in order to demonstrate how main aspects of social media influence human behaviour in different level, researcher based on the mean values of all statements to arrange the level of social media impacts which will score from highest to lowest mean value. The statement SM5 has known as “social media creates communities that can influence human interactions” which has highest mean value with 4.76. Following by the second highest mean value is factor

SM 1 (“Social media creates communities that can influence human interactions”) with mean value is 4.36

Both factors SM2 “People rely on social media to make a decision” and “Social media is addictive and an engaging tool that exists in the user's lives” have the same mean value with 4.24. The next factor has mean value with 4.11 is SM4 “Social media provides more information and useful knowledge”. Finally, the lowest mean value is statement SM3 “Social media inspires people to have a better life” with only 3.74. As a consequence, looking at the statistics of these factors, there are none of participants choosing lowest 1 = ‘Strongly disagreed’, and just a few participants rated disagreed towards statements. In other word, we can conclude that those factors have positive impacts towards customers in all aspects.

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SM1	152	4	5	4.36	.482	.581	.197	-1.685	.391
SM2	152	2	5	4.24	.735	-1.014	.197	1.457	.391
SM3	152	2	5	3.74	.851	-.183	.197	-.595	.391
SM4	152	2	5	4.11	.646	-.258	.197	-.026	.391
SM5	152	4	5	4.67	.471	-.735	.197	-1.479	.391
SM6	152	2	5	4.24	.658	-.859	.197	1.855	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152								

Table 18: Descriptive Statistics for Social media influences human behavior.

4.3.2. Descriptive statistic for Social media influences customer purchasing:

Regarding the customer purchasing, participants were asked for selecting factors to examine the contribution of social media to purchasing behaviour. According to table 19, we can see the mean value range from 3.69 to 4.48 with a standard deviation start from 0.475 to 0.673 which completely can tell all participants tend to have in general agreed that factors of this questionnaire have a relatively impact on their purchasing behaviour. As the statement SMP3 “Social media platforms enhance information spreading”, the mean value is highest with 4.48 which explains that people understand the important of social media in spreading and making information become viral on social media. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, Twitter is becoming a sharpen weapon of brands to bring information faster to customers. Other factors such as SMP1 “Social media is a tool that

significantly contributes to communication effectiveness’, SMP2 “Social media is a tool to improve the performance of marketing campaigns to attract users”, SMP5 “Social media creates opportunities for users to approach various brands while considering to purchase goods and services” have mean values which is all over 4 = “Agree”, it demonstrates that the relationship between brands and social media is extremely strong in which the role of social media is to create attraction and added value of products/services to customer, . In additional it builds a strong relationship between brands and customers. The lowest mean value is a statement SMP4 “Social media builds value and trust between users and brands” with 3.69. There are a few participants rate 2 = disagreed which mean they still do not think purchasing products/services on social media give them any values to trust brands. In overall, it concludes that this survey demonstrates social media factors impact on customer purchasing in particular way, also have beneficial effects towards consumer behaviour in choosing products or services via social media.

Descriptive Statistics									
	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SMP1	152	3	5	4.30	.475	.679	.197	-1.049	.391
SMP2	152	3	5	4.38	.501	.332	.197	-1.502	.391
SMP3	152	3	5	4.48	.527	-.196	.197	-1.358	.391
SMP4	152	2	5	3.69	.673	.198	.197	-.464	.391
SMP5	152	3	5	4.20	.544	.099	.197	-.097	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152								

Table 19: Descriptive Statistics for Social media influences purchasing.

4.3.3. Descriptive statistic for social media in banking:

In order to demonstrate impacts of social media in banking, the table 20 below illustrates the statistic to expose that the majority of factors in the questionnaire has been agreed by participants. As can be seen in the table 20, the mean value range from 3.74 to 4.45 and a standard deviation range from 0.515 to 0.714 which means there only one factor has mean lower that 4 = agreed. The lowest mean value is 3.74 and belongs to SMBK3 “Social media help to reduce marketing and advertising costs”. It can be quite appropriate because in order to get a successfull campaign in social media, banks have to invest to marketing fund to manage and maintain advertisement on social media. However, it also depends on how banks want to target to approach customer, the marketing cost will be based on different marketing strategies. Therefore, instead of investing to all channels

including traditional marketing, banks might focus on social media to promote their services to reduce marketing costs. Indeed, there are still many participant agreed with this statement to generate the mean value still over 3.

Regarding other statements, mean values are greater than 4 which are 4.30, 4.45 and 4.38. The statistic demonstrates that raising brand awareness, expanding relationship with existing and potential customers and attracting customers with diversified contents are all the effectiveness social media factors which contribute important roles to marketing strategy in banking industry.

Descriptive Statistics									
	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SMBK1	152	3	5	4.30	.515	.265	.197	-.697	.391
SMBK2	152	3	5	4.45	.525	-.066	.197	-1.378	.391
SMBK3	152	2	5	3.74	.714	-.353	.197	.127	.391
SMBK4	152	3	5	4.38	.514	.194	.197	-1.284	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152								

Table 20: Descriptive Statistics for Social media in banking.

4.3.4. Descriptive statistic for risks in social media:

Table 21 below show the record of risk factor of social media with participant judgment. The mean value range is quite low from 2.78 to 3.19 with a standard deviation from 0.612 to 0.707. In general, it indicates that the participants tend to disagree with risks while using social media for banking activities. The highest mean value pointed at RSM3 “Social media might influence customer negatively in choosing banking service or being loyal” with mean value 3.19. It demonstrates that somehow social media creates negative environment which impact on customer on choosing banking service. It commonly happened with negative reviews from people on social media. However, there are some participants who still believe it does not affect to their decision. Both remaining factors relating to “less trustworthy” and “insecure platforms once customers provide information” have low mean value with 2.69 and 2.78 in respectively. These figures simply illustrate that participants disagree with statements, because they trust the social media platforms of banks where they always get supports in quicker way and have been protected with confidential guarantee. In conclusion, this questionnaire statistic demonstrates that risks of using social media for banking activities do not have highly impact to customer decision.

Descriptive Statistics									
	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
RSM1	152	2	4	2.69	.612	.290	.197	-.625	.391
RSM2	152	2	4	2.78	.690	.314	.197	-.878	.391
RSM3	152	2	5	3.19	.707	-.062	.197	-.556	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152								

Table 21: Descriptive Statistics for Risks in Social media.

4.3.5. Descriptive statistic for customer satisfaction:

From table 22 below, the statistics implied that participants of the research are in general quite satisfied with their bank’s social media. The mean values of variables range from 3.51 to 3.64 with standard deviations range from 0.525 to 0.620. These figures describe that the mean values in some aspects of participant satisfaction are close to 4 which is “satisfied”. In order to achieve a better understanding of how participants rate the researched factors of customer satisfaction, the variables are arranged in a sequence from highest to lowest mean scores as follow: CS2 (“Customer expectations gained towards banking service”) with 3.64, CS1(“High quality in interactive support”) with 3.62, CS3 (“Provided information on social media platforms of the bank are supportive”) with 3.61, and the lowest mean value CS4(“Better and faster responses to compare with branch banking service”) with 3.51. It can be explained that participants are more satisfied with banking service and quality of interaction on bank social media as well as the service information provided by the bank. However, it is quite understandable as many Vietnam banks still have a big branch base to compare with other support channels, and also people sometime prefer to get face to face support or call centre support, so the prompt support on social media might not satisfy customers, especially when banks have not fully focused to arrange more staffs to manage social media channel.

Descriptive Statistics									
	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
CS1	152	2	4	3.62	.525	-.935	.197	-.282	.391
CS2	152	2	5	3.64	.520	-.462	.197	-.711	.391
CS3	152	2	5	3.61	.587	-.445	.197	-.075	.391
CS4	152	2	4	3.51	.620	-.897	.197	-.204	.391
Valid N (listwise)	152								

Table 22: Descriptive Statistics for Customer satisfaction.

4.4. Inferential Statistic:

4.4.1. Correlation among demographics and other social media factors:

In this section, the correlation of different factors in the survey will be investigated by analysing the data on SPSS. In order to examine the correlation of variables, research will use regression technique to analyse the correlations of variables.

As can be seen in table 23 below, the statistic describes the information about gender variable relate to spending time on social media variable. The value in the R column represents the correlation between these two variables. In this case $r = 0.277$, which indicate not strong relationship between the variables. In addition, by looking at ANOVA table, Sig value = p value, we can determine the significance between two variables by the p value. The p value has to lower than 0.05 to get significance model (Berman Brown and Saunders, 2008). As per the table 23, the p value = 0.001 which is lower than the benchmark 0.05. Hence, it is clear that there is significant between two variables which predicts the spending time on social media.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.277 ^a	.077	.071	.563	.077	12.486	1	150	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.955	1	3.955	12.486	.001 ^b
	Residual	47.512	150	.317		
	Total	51.467	151			

a. Dependent Variable: Time to spend on SM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Gender

Table 23: Gender and time spend on social media.

Table 24 below indicates that $r = 0.430$ which means the relationship between age groups and spending time on social media strong enough. In another aspect, sig value (p) is less than 0.05 which demonstrates that the model with age group variables and spending time on social media is significant model. In other word, it can be said that there is an evidence for a significant different between age group and spending time factor. It is understandable due to young generation tends to spend more time on social media to compare with older generation.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.430 ^a	.185	.180	.529	.185	34.112	1	150	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Age group

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.536	1	9.536	34.112	.000 ^b
	Residual	41.931	150	.280		
	Total	51.467	151			

a. Dependent Variable: Time to spend on SM
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Age group

Table 24: Age and time spend on social media

With the purpose of examining the correlation and whether different gender and age groups impact on social media advertisement, the table 25 below illustrates that there is not strong relationship between two variables (genders and age groups) and one other variable (advertisements on social media) because r value = 0.115 which is low for a relationship between these variables. Besides, sig value (p value) = 0.163 which is greater than a benchmark 0.05, hence, it is considered that there is no evidence for significant difference between two variables genders and age with respect to advertisements on social media. It concluded that the advertisements on social media might attract all type of customers.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.155 ^a	.024	.011	1.161	.024	1.836	2	149	.163

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender, Age group

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.951	2	2.475	1.836	.163 ^b
	Residual	200.885	149	1.348		
	Total	205.836	151			

a. Dependent Variable: Advertisement on social media

b. Predictors: (Constant), Gender, Age group

Table 25: Gender, age group and advertisements on social media

As been observed in table 26, R value is 0.282 which has relationship between demographics factor and social media platform factor, however it is not enough strong. The p value (sig) = 0.002 which is lower than 0.05, there is significant difference in this model between variables. It can be probably explained that recently new generation in Vietnam tend to use Instagram more than other platforms like Facebook. Therefore, by observing demographics factors, we can predict the social media platform factors which slightly depends on genders and age groups.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.282 ^a	.080	.067	.765	.080	6.439	2	149	.002

a. Predictors: (Constant), Age group, Gender

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.543	2	3.771	6.439	.002 ^b
	Residual	87.273	149	.586		
	Total	94.816	151			

a. Dependent Variable: SM platform for purchasing

b. Predictors: (Constant), Age group, Gender

Table 26: Gender, Age and social media platforms

As can be seen from table 27, the p-value of social media in banking is 0.001 which is less than the standard 0.05. Hence, it can be determined that there is a significant difference here between participants from different demographics towards social media in

banking. However, the p-values of banking activities on social media and tactics to attract customers on social media are both higher than 0.05 (0.139 and 0.177) which show no significant difference between age group and these two factors in the company.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
SM for banking activities	Between Groups	.985	3	.328	5.814	.001
	Within Groups	8.357	148	.056		
	Total	9.342	151			
Banking activity	Between Groups	4.498	3	1.499	1.859	.139
	Within Groups	119.397	148	.807		
	Total	123.895	151			
social media tactics to attract their customers	Between Groups	12.636	3	4.212	1.666	.177
	Within Groups	374.180	148	2.528		
	Total	386.816	151			

Table 27: Age groups between Social media in banking.

In conclusion, it is recognised from the tests that demographical factors in general do not make any significant difference towards influencing factors of banking activities on social media as well as factors of tactics to help banks approach more customer in effectiveness way. Nonetheless, there are two interesting variables here that have been confirmed to have significant differences here which are genders towards choosing social media platforms and social media marketing for banking sector.

4.4.2. Correlation between Risks of social media and customer satisfaction:

		Correlations		
			RSM	CS
Spearman's rho	RSM	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.225**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.005
		N	152	152
	CS	Correlation Coefficient	-.225**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.
		N	152	152

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 28: Correlations between Risks of social media and customer satisfaction in continuing with their bank.

In this section, the Spearman's Correlation test was used to test the statistical relationships between risks of social media and customer satisfaction. According to Saunders et. al (2012), Spearman Correlation coefficient is a positive figure, it shows the positive relationship. if it shows negative figure which illustrates a negative relationship. As can be witnessed from table 28 above, risks on social media and customer satisfaction show a negative and significant correlation with correlation coefficient value $r = -0.225$ and p-value is 0.005 and lower than 0.01. It is complete understandable because it demonstrates that one of the variable goes up, the other variable will go down. In this case, the more risk of social media will cause the less customer satisfaction.

4.5. Summary:

The data analysis in this chapter supports the research to figure out the significant contribution of social media in the Vietnamese banking sector and deeply understand consumer behaviour towards banking services on social media. The findings of this chapter show that almost the Vietnamese people consider social media to support their daily lives in many aspects such as entertainment, purchasing, communication, and seeking specific information. They also are attracted by advertisements on social media in many types but are mainly influenced by other social media users and social media influencers. Regarding the purchasing products and services, the findings indicated that Vietnamese people prefer to spend more time looking for product information and purchasing on Facebook and Instagram. Hence, it demonstrated that the social media interaction reflects the customer purchasing intention. Banking services are typical products, so the findings indicate the importance of social media in banking customer services when banking consumers tend to use social media to seek customer services and research products before purchasing. Moreover, based on the data analysis, the findings showed that customers have been attracted by social media tactics, social media impacts can positively change their buying behaviour. As being bank's employees, participants have indicated that social media plays a vital role in raising bank reputation and expanding relationships with existing and potential customers via various social media tactics such as visual, interactive contents, and providing financial knowledge.

The findings also indicated consumer satisfaction towards bank's social media. Due to the emergence of social media in the Vietnamese banking sector, banks currently focus on improving their social media and banking activities on social media to attract and satisfy their customers. Therefore, although customers are not completely satisfied with the bank's services on social media, their expectation towards banking services and supportive information are met sufficiently. Aside from the convenience of using social media for banking services. The results showed that the risk of social media might affect in choosing banking service of customers. However, surprisingly, customers relatively believe in the bank's social media because their personal information is protected on social media during the interaction. Finally, the findings also indicated that demographical factors just affect spending time on social media because it is pretty understandable that the young generation tends to spend more time browsing on social media to compare with the older age group. However, the impacts of social media and advertising types still affect all types of customers choosing and experiencing banking services.

Chapter 5: Analysis/Interpretation of interviews.

5.1. Introduction:

The discussion of this chapter based on the analysis of interview data was able to determine key themes that drive the impacts of social media on banking industry in Vietnam, mainly focus on how banks evaluate the opportunity and challenges of social media towards banking sectors.

The collected interview data will be analysed using thematic analysis, researcher sets out the Table 1 below which are the themes guided by research objectives and interview questions. All the codes are represented for the themes, while broad themes were expected to explore the collected data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015). According to Braun and Clarke (2006), a theme emerges to acquire the important information from collected data which relates to research questions and represents different level of the patterned meaning within data set. The judgement of researcher is fundamental factor which determines a particular information. Based upon that, a theme will be considered to set from the retained information. Moreover, the coding process was implemented with the aim of a set of themes. (Tuckett,2005).

Themes and sub-themes:

Red circles: Themes

Yellow circles: Sub-themes

These themes below are discussed in the subsequent sections:

Themes	Codes	Evidence	Discussed in Section
Social media platforms	➤ Facebook and YouTube are main social media platform	<p><i>“Vietcombank has 2 official social media platforms. There are two main platforms for customer services and marketing communications which are Facebook and YouTube. LinkedIn is managed by Human resource department and support for recruitment. We mainly focus on Facebook page due to high traffic and easily approach to Vietnamese customers”</i></p> <p><i>“Techcombank has 3 social media platforms including Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn because the majority population in Vietnam use Facebook as their personal blog and entertain themselves with YouTube videos”</i></p> <p><i>“BIDV has 3 social media platforms which is Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn, however the Facebook is the main communication channel because there is more than 70% population using Facebook for their personal social media”</i></p> <p><i>“Vietinbank has Facebook and YouTube and LinkedIn as social media platforms”</i></p>	5.2

		<p><i>“CitiBank Vietnam has only Facebook as social media platform which is managed by Citibank Vietnam in Vietnam”</i></p>	
<p>Impacts of social media on customer behaviour</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Customer experiences. ➤ Customer expectation. ➤ Customer satisfaction. ➤ Customer engagement. 	<p><i>“Social media created speed of engagement and community for customers. Customers can freely interact to each other, get information from different sources, and the important thing is to reach to various promotions from our banks. We are working to provide not only attractive promotions, also launch new bank services on social media, therefore customers are able to update information in fastest way as well as gain good experiences in a convenient way”</i></p> <p><i>“With the purposes of satisfying in all customer groups, especially young generation, we are developing widely in social media marketing channel, then we understand that social media plays a significant role in customer services. Nowadays, customers spend quite a lot of time on social media, so their expectation is to gain useful and many attractive information not only from our banks, also from other customers who are interacting on our social media platforms. Our bank currently prioritises all new services and promotion campaigns on social media rather than other channels. We believe that</i></p>	<p>5.3</p>

		<p><i>it effectively works to approach our online customer expectation”</i></p> <p><i>“The development of social media is speedy. In the first stage of expanding our social media platform, we have used Facebook and YouTube platform to deploy our new products and services as well as marketing campaigns to attract customer. However, customer interaction on social media is very high, so now we focus more on customer services on social media. We guarantee that our bank service will meet customer expectation not only on introduce promotions and new products/services, also on customer service. Customer will have satisfaction towards our prompt service on social media platform”.</i></p> <p><i>“Different social media advertising attracts customers and meet their expectation to compare with other communication channels. On the other hand, customers easily have influences from others on social media. We think understanding customer behaviour on social media and having a social media marketing strategy are core values to be more successful and increase our social visibility”</i></p> <p><i>“We invite influencers, celebrities to promote our products/services, create attractive posts on our social media</i></p>	
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		<p><i>platforms including video, images and contest. We received a very positive feedback and concerns from customers. Moreover, the feedback and customer's interaction from social media are higher than other traditional channels. All information is effortlessly reached to our customers rather than sending marketing email or telephone supports"</i></p>	
Strength of social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Enhance customer relationship ➤ Customer behaviour analysing tool ➤ Young generation channel ➤ Prompt customer service support. ➤ SEO strategy Booster ➤ Social media Influencer 	<p><i>"We are aware of the power of social media, it is no longer just a place for communication between our bank and customers, it offers us to create a profitable relationship with customers. We use social media platforms, particularly Facebook to approach more customers for example opening new account online, guiding customer making transaction online, offering promotions and new products/services"</i></p> <p><i>"Customer data shares on social media creates more possibilities to support us to have deep insights in customer behaviour. We use social media as a tool to analyse customer behaviour, we have an insight into our customer's personal, spending preferences and even their life events. We will offer convenient services which meet their need. For example, according to their online searching about</i></p>	5.4

		<p><i>property and house price, we might offer them house mortgages”</i></p> <p><i>We are reaching to young generation who use social media to look for information and communicate each other. This customer group prefer to have almost their activities online rather than go to the branch. We retain customer by attractive images, video content and social advertisement on social media.”</i></p> <p><i>“Customer supports on social media are quite prompt. We realised that our customers always get supports not only from our bank, also from other customers, communities on social media. It avoids customer dissatisfaction while waiting responses from our customer service centre.”</i></p> <p><i>“We are using social media as a competitive weapon. Our bank focus to create interesting content and meaningful video about our products, social media helps us to spread it virally. Moreover, social media contributes as a significant traffic source for SEO (search engine optimization) on Google which push our bank to be on top of others”</i></p> <p><i>“Inviting social media influencers is one of tactics to create successful engagement from customers towards our products/services”</i></p>	
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<p>Challenges of social media</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lack of human resource ➤ Security and privacy ➤ Negative information spreading. ➤ Limitation of approaching all customer groups 	<p><i>“Negative information has been viral on social media very fast. It affects to all businesses, not only banks. Social media is a place where users freely comment, give their opinions, therefore, it is hard to control. Although social media platforms have policies to manage and report relating to inappropriate contents, negative information of customer experience towards products/services are still able to be viral by users”</i></p> <p><i>“Security and privacy are important issue for banks when we want to improve our service more convenient on social. We do not allow customer to implement any banking activities on social media. Basically, a landing page would help us to direct customer from social media platform to our website”</i></p> <p><i>“With a huge amount of customer interaction on social media. We are planning to educate more employee to manage our social media page, provide prompt responses and quality customer services. Moreover, we have a plan to approach customer on social media for sell crossing. We believe that lack of human resource is not a big challenge with us in the future”</i></p> <p><i>“Social media is always known as a useful network and entertainment for young</i></p>	<p>5.5</p>
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		<p><i>generation. Majority of our customer on social media is young age group (20-40 years old). Older age group still prefer to be approached by phone consultancy, advices from branches. So that, it not easy for our banks to expand social media to be a main communication channel with all age groups”</i></p>	
<p>Future plans for social media in banking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Expanding other platforms. ➤ Diversifying social media advertisings. ➤ Improving customer service responses. 	<p><i>“With the purpose of approaching more customers with different segments, we are intending to deploy our marketing communication on other social media platforms such as Instagram and Tiktok in the near future. We understand that the more channels, the more coverage.”</i></p> <p><i>“For our future plans, we will focus on creating various social marketing campaigns to engage customers. We want to provide positive campaigns to customer. It not only brings profit to us, also for our community such as charity programs”</i></p> <p><i>“We would like to provide fresh content on social media continuously. Therefore, we will work to diversify our social marketing contents which will make us to be more competitive with other banks on the market. Because attractive contents will be the best way to capture the attention of target customers”</i></p> <p><i>“Improving our customer service is the main action that we concern to</i></p>	<p>5.6</p>

		<i>implement. For us, customer retention is very important, especially young generation use social media as the main channels to look for supports and information”</i>	
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Table 29: Table of Themes

5.2. Social media platforms:

This theme emerged from the interview question involves to what social media platform has been deployed by banks in Vietnam. According to collected data, all the banks has reasons to deploy their marketing communication, promotion campaigns and customer services on specific social media platforms. Banks understand that social media is no longer just a personal blog. Indeed, this was based upon on collected data, all banks have developed their social media page on Facebook or YouTube where is instantly connect people with the banks. Banks is active on Facebook as the business tool which stay engage with their customers and boost sales. With 70% population in Vietnam accounts for Facebook users, it will be a very potential channel to reach high traffic for bank’s website. It is understandable that Facebook is not only a social media platform with biggest user in Vietnam, but also it is the most influential platform to approach customers. By providing particular ads program with effective targeting abilities, Facebook become a main social media tool for business to increase customer data base, for example Facebook lead ads supports banks to approach more customer to open new accounts, sign up for new services. Moreover, sharing content function on Facebook is one of the instant way to reach out and spread posts to people. It avoids showing posts on bank’s Facebook frequently, it might cause customer dissatisfaction. On the other hands, banks also expand on YouTube channel to enhance to special products or services. While many global brands focus on YouTube to create attractive videos, banks in Vietnam do not stay beyond that. Getting attention of customers through videos also is a marketing strategy for branding and self- promotion. Attractive and meaningful content videos are the best way to advertise bank’s products. Moreover, with advantages of lengthy videos on YouTube, for instance, many banks create interesting stories as a movie to bring more messages to customers. Currently, Community tab on YouTube is one of the tool which many brands including banks use it to market their

products and advertisement, even create a landing page on Community tab on YouTube. This tool is considered to work as Facebook posts and to encourage subscribers to engage to YouTube videos. Furthermore, as per the collected data from the interviews, a few banks also are active on LinkedIn social network, however, because Vietnamese social network users on LinkedIn is not big enough, therefore, building content on LinkedIn is mostly for recruitment. In the near future, with the variety of social media platforms, Vietnam banks probably explore their strategy widely to approach customer and for branding purposes.

According to literature review, Facebook is a large social network that can help businesses bring more benefits to their users (Conlin, 2020). Through its integration tools, businesses can easily create a community and manage their customer profiles. Indeed, the evidence from the interview demonstrated that the majority of Vietnamese banks are using Facebook to connect people with banks. It has developed a set of tools that allow banks to build an online environment. Almost Vietnamese banks such as Vietcombank, Techcombank, BIDV... , they utilise Facebook analysis tool to control their page's activities and demographic information. This will allow them to improve their efficiency and align their business strategy with their goals. This is significantly associated with a study of Moth (2012) which conducted that social media platform can help businesses to analyse their audience and determine their ideal business model. Since the development of Facebook, various solutions have been offered to banks, especially the use of Facebook ads can help them develop effective campaigns.

In the business perspective of banks, it is significantly parallel with the literature review when YouTube channel supports to bank to approach many potential customers. Based on the creating video contents for marketing campaigns, YouTube is a main platform to develop marketing strategy for banks as well as engaging customer audience in the direct way. However, utilising Google to improve bank reputations through the relationship between Google and YouTube has not mentioned. Basically, banks mainly use Facebook ads and YouTube ads to maximise their presence online and expand customer base which is demonstrated as the study of about inconvenience of social media platform in literature review.

However, Vietnamese banks has not focused on Twitter as many global banks. Although Twitter is one of the efficient platform which will spread information very fast.

The main benefit of Twitter is to gather conversation of businesses and customer instantly as well as customer feedback are always sorted out in the fastest way (Zote, 2020).

5.3. Impacts of social media on customer behaviour:

This theme emerged during the questionnaire relating to customer's view and customer's experience from the social media in banking sector. The important of customer experience towards making a convenient social media community is a necessary factor by the participant observation. Participant was knowledgeable to understand how social media created an extremely engagement between customers and banks. Indeed, on participant business view, to provide customer good experiences and achieve the effective engagement, banks realize that marketing and product launching deployment on social media is a vital channel to compare with traditional advertising. Because the fundamental of business success is effective customer engagement. Base on their point of view, participants identified how customers experience their products on social media. They observed that in order to look for a specific product or bank service, social media is a place to interact with each other, gain information from various sources, especially to search for many special offered deals. Thus, to demonstrate their customer expectations understanding, participant revealed that their bank has been worked to diversify their social media contents, not only focusing on posting attractive promotions or special deals of their products, but also use social media as a tool to introduce new products. It is one of the key benefit to engage with customers, the more diversified posts, the more positive reaction from the customers. This is appropriate with the study of literature reviews where revealed that all the contents, product review, customer experiences and product services are able to gather customers and banks on social media. It became the influence source on customer buying behavior (Gupta and Chopra, 2020). On the other hand, it is associated with the study of Barhemmati et al., (2012), Vietnamese banks employed social media to enhance the brand awareness in order to create promotion campaigns to attract customers together with traditional marketing channels.

Moreover, participants pointed that more and more customers access to social media rather than other channels to look for their desired information, especial young generation. Their bank currently takes social media as their strategic marketing channel to build up their customer satisfaction and expectation. Banks understand that interesting posts on

social media are not only enough to approach all customer groups, it also has to be shared and spread by their social media followers. In order to spread their products and promotion campaigns widely, participants highlighted that they prioritized to focus their marketing strategy on social media channel rather than other channels. Banks believe that with a strong communication channel has been built via social media, approaching the group of young generations as well as achieving customer expectation is completely reached out. Indeed, based on the study in the literature review, young generation always have been attracted by the entertained contents of specific products. It can trigger their decision behavior through social media influencer. Vietnamese banks prioritize attractive contents which can impact on customer sentiment and encourage them to pay attention to their products and brands. Moreover, studies in literature review stated that the informative contents shared on social media will bring the valuable knowledge to customers in the long term. It is paralleled with the intention of banks when they are applying social media to create more attractive and provide informative content to customer with the purpose of customer engagement. Vietnamese banks understand the entertainment factor significantly affect to customer attention and reinforce customer attitude towards bank services. It play an important role in marketing strategy to trigger to customer behavior as the mentioned study in literature review (Aydin et al., 2021).

One of the very important key to value a bank success is customer service. In responses to the question in relation with customer's view on social media, participants expressed that banks are not only expand marketing strategy on social media, they also provide instant responses to customer on their social media platform together with their customer service center. With extremely high customer interaction on social media, and also high number of social media accessing, a poor customer service probably ruins bank reputation. Prompt responses on social media shows a responsive customer service. It supports banks reach out their potential customers and maintain a good relationship with existing customers. On the other hand, social customer service is a convenient place where banks can collect and direct customer needs to call center or create the social contents to support to those customers have same concerns. Hence, based upon the important role of social customer service, participants pointed that banks always improve their social media customer service to meet their customer needs and resolve customer concerns. This is a

vital factor which has significantly contributed to a social media marketing strategy of banks.

Banks tend to use various type of social media advertising to achieve effective result. Participant indicated that to meet customer expectation, banks has created many type of advertising on social media. Facebook is the most social media platform which is used by Vietnamese, therefore, Facebook ads is the favorite choice of banks which effortlessly build brand awareness, increase engagement to customers, and direct customers to main websites. On the other words, diversity of social media ads such as photo ads, video ads, story ads with interesting contents will attract customers instantly. It is an effective way to achieve maximum visibility on social media. In another aspect, creating various social media campaigns has basically become one of the creative way to increase bank visibility. Especially, the meaningful social media campaigns might inspire customer to spread it largely and promote awareness of bank brand. Overall, regarding creating various advertising on social media to achieve customer expectation, participant expressed that having effective social media marketing strategies still a core value to deploy social media advertising. Additionally, one of social media marketing type is social media influencer which significantly impact to customers. Social media followers are interested in big name celebrities; therefore, many Vietnamese banks hire famous people to promote their products and services. Participants pointed that banks received many positive feedback and concerns towards their products when advertise by using influencers. Influencers can offer banks their audiences and high number of follower from their fan base which can support banks to increase their customer base and reach out more potential customers. Especially, young generation (Gen Y and Z) tend to be influenced by influencers. Understanding the role of that impact, many banks hired and educated influencers financial knowledge, provided them benefits to experience bank products which leads them to have deep insight and easily to promote products. Influencer marketing can be an effective strategy for banks in relation with actual engagement and also is an efficient choice to expand customer network. Indeed, in some studies which were mentioned in the literature review, many brands hire social media influencers to advertise their products and they believe that this factor will significantly encourage customer behavior. The inspiration of influencers such as celebrities or social media famous people will bring the trend towards customer buying intention. Vietnamese banks utilized posts and shares of influencers on their social media

pages to build up followers as well as engage social media users with the topic of specific products or services. Based on the reputation of influencers, the products and services will be more trustworthy to customers (Geysler, 2021). Participants also stated that customers tend to look for social media influencers opinions to support their decision making on choosing a specific bank services.

5.4. Strength of social media:

This theme of strength of social media regarding how social media bring benefits to banks. Participants reported that the relationship between banks and customer has been created stronger via social media. There are many activities has offered to customer on social media, it is not only a place to promote bank products and services. This is consistent with the purpose of using social media of banks, banks used social media to expand their services and to guides customers to experience their products *“We use social media platforms, particularly Facebook to approach more customers for example opening new account online, guiding customer making transaction online, offering promotions and new products/services”*. Indeed, benefits of social media towards maintaining and enhancing customer relationship is not only promotion attraction, it also brings added value from customer care and supports.

In another aspect, in this analysis, social media is a tool which bank can use to analyse customer behaviour. Participant pointed that their bank based on personal information and customer preferences on customer’s social media page to reach out and offer them appropriate services and products. Banks use social media as a filter tool to extract needed information, therefore the informative contents will be created to adapt customer expectation. In the fact, based upon customer online searching about property and house price, bank offers them mortgages and related projects which is suitable to their demands.

One of the main social media’ strength is to support banks to acquire young generation customers who tend to access social media more than other groups. Because these customers currently prefer to be active online more that go to bank branches. They found social media as a convenient and entertained online place to look for their needs. Hence, participants indicated that by providing attractive social media contents via images, video, other social ads and also rapid online services can help banks to retain and reach out more young customers. On the other hand, participants stated that social media contributed

to customer service on social media because interaction within social media users is quite prompt. Social media create an environment for customer to get supports from each other. This is understandable when the bank has to be more proactive with their posts and social advertisings on their social media page, it will attract more customer interaction. Therefore, it generates more supports for customers. Somehow, the customer dissatisfaction will be reduced because they probably receive responses instantly and they do not to wait for customer service centre.

Social media content is one of the engage tool that supports banks to be more competitive in the market. Participants expressed that social media equips banks a tool to spread information virally to customers. Through social media, banks create interesting and meaningful contents including videos, images, campaigns. This can help to offer customer deep insights about bank's products. Moreover, such tools are sources where customers are educated and engaged to use the bank's products and services. Especially, many banks use SEO campaign (search engine optimization) to boost their competitive ability on Google. SEO strategy contributes a vital role to brand's search visibility and Google ranking. According to participants, social media has been used to increase traffic in bank's website. Indeed, all the information and links in respect to bank's products have been shared across social platforms will affect to SEO such as increase bank's reputation, improve traffic and push bank to be more competitive in the market. Hence, banks utilise social media as a sharp weapon to boost their SEO strategy on Google.

These finding converge with the statement of Ahuja (2020) in the literature review, banks utilized social media as the practical marketing tool to implement their strategies to maximize the profit. Basically, people find the finance and banking information are always hard to absorb. Therefore, social media assist banks to engage banking product information to customers through online community. As the participants mentioned, social media created online community for customer to enable to share, discuss and interact to each other regarding financial information and banking products. This is consistent with literature review where the author stated that social media can strongly support banks to maintain relationship between banks and customers. Furthermore, promotional campaigns on social media with attractive content and very closed to customer enable to easily approach customers.

Indeed, this finding is consistent with the literature review, because it is not only banking and financial industry using influencer marketing to promote their products and services, but also influence marketing has been becoming a popular trend on social media. Social media influencers can be considered as celebrities or high follower people on various social media platforms. Indeed, in order to spread products on social media, many banks tend to engage financial experts who can inspired people by their experiences and financial knowledge in an attractive way on social media. According to Cocheo (2020), the fast way to build the trustworthy is to inspired customer by influencers when this group of people are well known and their reputation has been created before they jump into any projects to spread product information to customers.

As the influencer marketing is more popular and as mention in the above section, participants also expressed that those people have posting with influential followings can be invited to promote bank's products or services. Social media influencers who have high fan base and followers will support banks to amplified bank's products/services on social networks. Therefore, they confirmed that this factor is one of the social media tactics to connect banks with customers. Moreover, it helps to build more trust between banks and customer through honesty of influencers.

In overall, the findings are indicated that strengths of social media generate significantly to bank's marketing strategy. Banks has been utilised these factors to improve their social marketing and be more competitive in the market. The findings are consistent with some aspects of literature review which demonstrated the advantages of social media application in banking sector always maximise the effectiveness of marketing strategy and bring the best outcomes for any campaigns.

5.5. Challenges of social media:

Although social media are beneficial to banks in many aspects which were discussed in the previous section, this theme was directly covered the weakness of social media in banking sector.

Regarding *lack of human resource to support customer service* on social media, participant stated that due to the high volume of customer interaction on social media, the more employee need to be educated to support customer on social media. This is understandable that social media is not customer service centre where bank's employee just

communicate with one customer at one time. The supported responses on social media will be spread widely to many follower at once, hence the responses have to be more rapid. Especially bank's products are financial services which require employee has to be highly educated not only sales skills, it also be equipped good financial knowledge. Moreover, as the participant mentioned, their bank always want to satisfy customer by prompt responses and tend to approach customers for cross selling on social media, therefore improving employee skills and recruiting more employee to cover this field are important tasks for them. However, they also believe that this is not a big challenge for their bank.

Participants also raised their concern associated with the possibility of *security and privacy* towards customer personal information on social media. They claimed that eventhough banks want to improve their service more convenient on social media, security of social media remains as an issue. It is completely understandable for example Internet banking and mobile banking system are strickly control and managed by their bank IT, while social media is lack of security to compare with banking system. Therefore, participant demonstrated that they would never ask their customer make any banking activities on social media. However banks use social media platform to refers customers through landing pages to protect their information. In another aspect, privacy is one of the cause of customer approaching limitation. Social media is an open place where almost of user activities are exposed, meanwhile people are quite sensitive when looking for financial or banking service such as loan service. Customers tend to hesitate to interact with campaign relating to loan services, because they probably feel uncomfortable to public on social media. Indeed, these factors has significant affect to financial services, especially in banking sector where security and privacy are the most customer concerns. This finding is consistent with the research which mentioned in literature review, some of the banks allow customer to implement banking activities through social media because of convenience however, the security of privacy issues remains as a big obstacle. The social media policies does not guarantee to protect banking customer regarding the confidential customer information. Especially, the findings are converged with literature review to demonstrated that regarding some sensitive banking products such as personal loans or mortgages, customers usually avoid social media platform to interact due to their privacy issues. Therefore, it is slightly hard for banks to investigate customer preferences and approach to offer them appropriate products (Parusheva, 2017).

Due to the fast moving of social media, there are not only positive information or attractive campaigns spreading fast, but also negative contents still have viral potential. It might cause the bank reputation to be ruined or less trustworthy. In term of *negative contents on social media*, it is general matter to all industries. Participants pointed that with the huge amount of social media users, negative comments are unavoidable. Furthermore, negative feedbacks on social media tend to go viral very fast, participants said that it is hard to control what customers say on social media even there are policies of social platforms to manage in term of inappropriate contents. However, in order to control the risks from the negative information spread, banks also implement their own social media monitor tools which support them to instantly solve social media crisis. This finding totally consist with the research which mentioned in literature review. The product information is easily spread on social media platform. The customer experiences can be negative even banks have procedures to control their social media page. Therefore, monitoring the customer interaction on social media is remaining a challenge for banks (Albro, 2010).

Although the social media penetration has increased, participants stated that *“majority of our customer on social media is young age group (20-40 years old). Older age group still prefer to be approached by phone consultancy, advices from branches”* which means main customers interact on social media is young generation who stick with digital technologies and prefer to communicate online more than offline, meanwhile the old generation generally lacks technical proficiency or do not entertain themselves on social networks. Therefore, even though banks currently put their effort to be more creative and innovative on social media which probably target young generation, on another hand, banks still have to deploy their campaigns and products on other channel such as traditional advertising, direct mail or face to face. This finding is partly converged with the literature review. The young generation (generation Y) tend to engage more with campaigns and information of products on social media more than old generation. It supports businesses to improve their marketing strategy via customer contribution. This is a significant factor for a business or bank to raise brand awareness (Hruska and Maresova, 2020).

In conclusion, these findings were discussed that social media also can be disadvantage to banks in some aspects. It can be more challenging for banks to deliver a consistent customer satisfaction. However, banks are also focusing to find solutions to improve their social media channel regardless the challenges. Additionally, some points of

these findings are completely consistent with the literature review which demonstrated that Vietnamese banks are facing with general challenges in banking industry while employing social media as the marketing tool.

5.6. Future plans for social media in banking:

This theme expanded the questionnaire regarding further actions with social media strategy.

Regarding the future strategic plans to expand social media, participants pointed that banks intend to deploy their communication on different social media platform apart from Facebook or YouTube. There are several social media platforms such as Instagram, Tiktok, Twitter which will be considered to improve their advertising and marketing features. Each social platform has a purpose and unique audience, also financial services is considered as special products with many regulations which have made banks reluctant to employ social media platforms. However, banks understand their aims to approach more customer in different market segments as well as the social media trends are developing day by day with various social media platforms. The more social media channels to be expanded, the more coverage will be reached. Therefore, expanding their social media platform is one of the strategy in their future plan.

Diversifying social media advertisings and marketing campaigns on social media has become an essential marketing strategy to engage customers. It becomes a priority for banks who want to stay relevant. Participants mentioned that banks will have to focus to produce innovative campaigns by using a variety of strategies. In the fact, since the pandemic 2020, people stay at home more, it is the reason to make banks have to put more effort to connect with customer online. Hence, providing various campaigns with positive contents will attract more customers. Participant also expressed that impactful campaigns such as charity programs will inspire people and bring more value to community in general, it extremely captures customer attention to have more positive views towards their bank. Additionally, participants demonstrated that fresh contents will be more considered to make them more competitive.

In order to be more successful on social media, participants confirmed that bank will improve their customer service on their social media platforms. Their goal is to assure existing customers and potential customers that they are always active and responsive on

social media. Especially young generation customers mainly use social media to get support about financial services, banks will concentrate to innovate customer service tools on social media to deliver effective customer service.

5.7. Summary of interview analysis:

From the discussion so far, findings of this chapter have focused on opportunities and challenges of social media application impact on service delivery of the banks providing to customers. Under the interviewer perspectives, the opportunities of social media support banking system in general and marketing strategies in particular. Marketing communication has been developed by using social media in their marketing strategy. Participants examined the social media application enhance the bank perception and its reputation. In additions, increasing the loyalty of existing customers and attract new potential customers via benefits of social media tools such as analytic tools toward interaction of customers. With the developing country as Vietnam, social media in banking sector has been described as a very functional tool to boost their performance in the market. They utilize social media to approach many potential in different segments, especially young generation who are mostly addicted to online communities. Also, social media application provides banks to exploit more creative marketing content which traditional marketing have limitation of this field. Participants delivered their judgement about the development of social media which contribute significantly in customer decision making. Variety of social media marketing solutions enhances bank performance and their brand awareness. These are the key factors of social media application to reach out the potential customers and maintain customer relationship along with effective marketing strategies.

However, there still remains the challenges which mentioned by participants. These weaknesses factors have both indirectly and directly affect to the development of social media in banking sector. Participant stated that challenge factors are improving and being making efforts to control it as soon as possible. In this finding, regarding the challenges of social media, the security and privacy factor has been concerned the most. Because banking services is the typical sector and sensitive services while social media is an expose environment. It limited customer to search and look for product information. Along with this, banking system is the most secured to compare with other industry, therefore security

on social media is not enough to let banks have more interaction with customer if customers desire to investigate deeply about a specific banking services.

Finally, the discussion concerning the action in the future to utilize social media in the effective way would be indicated by participants. Focusing to diversify the creative content on social media is still the main duty for banks to influence customer behavior, it supports banks become more competitive in the market. Furthermore, expanding their social network has been considered to explore while some social media platform is emerging to attract more users. Obviously, the customer service also is being focused to enhance the responsive capabilities while interacting with customer on social media.

The main contribution of this study is that identify and demonstrate the objective of the topic from participant's perspectives and experiences regarding the impacts of social media towards banking sector and customer purchasing behavior. All the highlighted key factors have been described in depth so far.

5.8. Critical inflection of interviews:

Based on the literature of qualitative methodologies, thematic analysis was considered as an appropriate method to investigate the experiences and responses of participants regarding all aspects of social media in banking industry. This thematic analysis supports the researcher to be more flexible during the analysis process. Participant perspectives were analyzed in detail and gathered into specific topics of social media in banking sector. Because of the trustworthiness of the thematic technique, this tool assists the researcher to approach a rich, detailed and complex data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The purpose of this research was to utilize the thematic analysis to bring outcomes that emerged from the data collection provided by participants. During the data collection process, in order to achieve the responses from participants, the researcher did not reveal her knowledge and experiences toward the social media in banking sector to investigate participants. The background of the researcher was a banker in Vietnam and has understanding toward marketing in banking industry which means she has a sufficient understanding of some aspects of social media marketing in a bank. Because of the work experiences of the researcher in banking industry, it would be affected to her approaching the study and it can be a potential achievement for this study. However, the researched believe that regarding her pre-existing knowledge of marketing in banking industry did not

lead to any influences to the analysis regardless the researcher experiences somehow affect to interaction process with interviewers. The purpose of the analysis was still to perform the perspectives of interviewer marketing management level and those people directly work in social media marketing in Vietnam banks. Additionally, the thematic analysis drives the research to achieve a rich understanding from interviews to contribute appropriate results towards this study. During the interview process, sometimes the researcher used her pre-existing banking experiences to make the interview process smoother and to clarify the response from the interviewers. However, almost statements related to social media concepts which are quite popular, therefore the participants were prompt to explain and to clear their point of views. On the other hands, the researcher also made suggestion which were closed to participant's views to support them clarify their statement in the easy way. It also accelerates the interview process to make the participants feel more comfortable, hence, they would express all their knowledge and information to support this study.

Despite the issues regarding the pre-existing experiences and knowledge of researcher about social media marketing as well as marketing in banking sector, the thematic analysis was implemented to complete the study. The coding and the themes were classified into the appropriate sub-themes to effortlessly analyse the data. The data was relevant and suitable with the classification. In conclusion, the thematic analysis significantly contributes the in depth sight for this research findings in this situation of the study.

Chapter 6: Discussion and Conclusion

6.1. Discussion on the results of hypotheses:

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence factors of social media on banking sector and customer behaviours in choosing and using banking services in Vietnam. Although there are many studies regarding the impact of social media towards customer behaviour, the literature shows that there was no appropriate previous study related to impacts of social media in Vietnamese banking sector. Based on the findings, it is described that the majority of participants in the survey have a positive perspective with social media application in their daily life as well as in banking purposes. Impact of social media drives the customer views to facilitate them in banking activities. Regarding the demographical factors, there was not a clear impact show on the social media using and social media advertisings or other social media activities. Moreover, risks of social media also cause the customer satisfaction to carry on using social media for their banking activities. In order to recap the findings, all the research hypotheses will be presented and discussed here:

Hypothesis 1: Demographical factors are statistical significantly and positively related to social media in banking industry.

As reviewed in the literature, demographic factors significantly influence social media activities, particularly across different age groups. This plays a crucial role for businesses when considering the deployment of social media marketing strategies or selecting the appropriate social media platforms for banking activities. The younger generation tends to access social media more frequently and seeks specific information more actively compared to the older generation. Additionally, gender also impacts social media usage, as businesses can tailor their strategies to target specific customer groups based on these differences (Yakobi, 2016). Consequently, it is anticipated that there is a positive relationship between demographic factors and social media usage.

The study's analysed data supports this prediction, showing a notable correlation between age groups and factors such as time spent on social media and the use of social media for banking purposes. Indeed, the younger generation shows a higher concern for social media compared to other age groups. However, regarding the effectiveness of advertisements on social media, there is no significant correlation with demographic

factors, suggesting that all customer segments can be attracted by diverse social media advertisements.

Furthermore, the analysed data indicates no significant differences among age groups in using social media for selecting banking activities or the benefits it provides in customer engagement. This suggests that banks can utilize social media as a supportive tool to help all customers access banking services effortlessly, irrespective of demographic variation. In this case, the hypotheses 1 is therefore partially rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Social media are statistical significant to customer behaviour.

As highlighted in the literature review, Cho (2014) emphasized that businesses use social media networking to create a strong impression of their products or services on customers and to influence their purchasing behavior, regardless of the size of the business. Social media platforms also consider the online social community, enabling customers to access these sites for communication, connection, updates, searches, and purchases.

The research results align significantly with the studies reviewed in the literature. Most research participants agreed on the impact of social media on the behavior, reinforcing the idea that social media indeed enhances customer purchasing behavior. Many participants believed that product information spreads rapidly on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, which effectively engage customers. Marketing campaigns were identified as a crucial factor in attracting customers and influencing their behaviour. Other social media factors, such as providing opportunities for users to explore various brands when considering purchases and building value and trust between users and brands, were generally supported by participants. This demonstrates that social media significantly impacts customer purchasing behaviour, offering substantial benefits in choosing products or services. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Social media activities significantly contribute to marketing strategy in banking.

As discussed in the literature review, Sharma et al. (2021) found a strong association between social media marketing activities and customer purchasing intentions. The variety of social media platforms makes customers feel more prepared to purchase products and services. In the banking context, platforms like YouTube and Facebook allow financial

services to be presented in emotionally engaging and meaningful ways, making it possible to attract customers quickly and effectively, often surpassing the reach of conventional marketing methods (Schmidt, 2021). Therefore, this study expects to see a significant contribution of social media in the banking sector.

The study's findings support this expectation, with the majority of participants agreeing that social media factors influence their purchasing behaviours. Specifically, in the banking context, feedback from bank employees reconfirmed that social media significantly affects marketing strategies. These strategies include raising brand awareness, building relationships with existing and potential customers, reducing marketing costs, and attracting customers with diverse content. Social media's ability to rapidly spread information and engage users plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of these marketing efforts. This demonstrates the importance of integrating social media into the marketing strategies of banks to achieve various objectives. Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: Functional factors of social media help to approach customer attention and satisfaction.

Based on the literature reviews, banks can leverage social media too execute various aspects of their business plans, such as marketing campaigns, product development, sales acceleration, and customer service enhancement, all of which contribute to increased customer satisfaction (Micti and Kapoulas, 2012). Additionally, social media has created effective marketing strategies specifically tailored for the banking sector (Ahuja, 2020). Statistical findings indicate that the majority of customers are generally satisfied with their bank's social media presence in certain areas.

As mentioned in the literature review, social media usage in the Vietnamese banking sector is still developing, with banks continuously working to maximize its benefits to better satisfy their customers. Despite this, customers in Vietnam are still satisfied with how banks utilize social media. The functional aspects of social media have significantly contributed to customer satisfaction, meeting their expectations for banking services. Customers appreciate the high quality of interactive support provided by social media banking community. This area represents a critical factor for banks to focus on to further improve their social media strategies in the future. Consequently, the hypothesis that social media utilization enhances customer satisfaction in the Vietnamese banking sector is

accepted.

Hypothesis 5: Risk factors of social media lead to a statistically significant change in choosing banking services of customers.

As being reviewed in the literature, many challenges and risk factors are emerging in social media environment. It led the banks need to be aware while employing social media as the communication tool in their strategy because it directly impacts to customer satisfaction to carry on choosing their banking services. According to Voramontri and Klieb (2019), risks factors of social media does not only challenge banks, it also has significant impact on consumer behavior on choosing to stay with banks. Especially in Vietnamese banking sector where social media is still emergence channel for expanding banking network and approaching more potential customers. As the expected, the research study show that there was the significant correlation between customer satisfaction and risk factors of social media. In this case, the more risk of social media will affect to the customer satisfaction. Although the social media usage in banking have positive affect and being beneficial for customer while experiencing and seeking banking services, whereas the remaining risk factors such as security, privacy or trustfulness of banking social media still cause customer fear somehow. Therefore, it affects to customer behavior in choosing to stay with banks. In this case, this hypothesis is therefore accepted.

6.2. Conclusions and recommendations:

6.2.1. Introduction:

This thesis has provided a comprehensive investigation into the application of social media in businesses, with a specific focus on the banking industry. The importance of social media usage was examined to understand its impact on consumer behaviour. The successful integration of social media into marketing strategies has yielded effective outcomes, influencing consumer behaviour positively. This integration plays a crucial role in promoting banking products and enhancing the competitiveness of banks in the market. In other words, social media has proven to be a valuable marketing tool that helps banks achieve their marketing objectives and strategic goals.

Within the context of this thesis, the efficiency of social media in the banking industry was analysed to demonstrate its impact on consumer behaviour. By leveraging social media platforms as marketing channels, banks have deployed various opportunities to gain

insights into customer behaviour. Key factors of social media, such as viral content, customer interaction, social media influencers, and analytics tools, have supported banks in raising brand awareness, implementing marketing campaigns, increasing sales, and maintaining customer relationships. Consequently, the research outcomes confirmed that social media utilization offers a significant marketing solution for banks. This enables banks to refine their marketing strategies and better understand consumer behaviour. Furthermore, social media marketing activities have accelerated customer decision-making and enhanced the bank's reputation in the eyes of consumers.

The literature review in this research provided fundamental concepts of social media and technological developments that have shaped the social media environment. Various aspect of social media were discussed and examined, updating the understanding of consumer behaviour and perceptions related to purchasing products via social media. Previous studies were reviewed to explore the application of social media in business strategies aimed at meeting consumer satisfaction, promoting products, and raising brand awareness. These studies demonstrated the success of social media marketing in different business contexts, while also identifying existing opportunities and challenges.

Given the importance of the research question, a pragmatic approach was adopted to combine subjectivity in research with objectivity in data collection and analysis. Therefore, a mixed-method approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative methods, was employed. The pragmatist approach was deemed suitable for identifying the role of social media in the banking sector and its impact on consumer behaviour. This thesis has highlighted the advantages of the pragmatism paradigm, demonstrating that the effective integration of quantitative and qualitative methods provided comprehensive answers to the research questions and achieved the research objectives.

In order to achieve the research aims, the researcher arranged 9 interviews with key participants in Vietnamese banks through online interview due to the restriction of traveling during pandemic (Covid-19). 152 questionnaires were distributed to those people who mainly work in banks and financial institution to collect their opinion and views about social media. By employing questionnaires, the data collection and data analysis will develop research objective 1 (to explore the contribution of social media in Vietnamese banking sector) and also expand the research objective 2 (to examine the customer attitudes

towards the application of social media marketing). In order to analyse the collected data from interviews, the researcher will apply qualitative thematic analysis to analyse the data in the chapter 5. Qualitative thematic analysis will support the research to reach the objective 2 and 3 of the research which has focused to evaluate the opportunities and the challenges of social media application in Vietnamese banking sector. Moreover, it investigated the research participants' experience and perspective of social media in banking because those participants are working in marketing field in Vietnamese banks.

6.2.2. Summary of key findings:

❖ Findings from Questionnaires analysis:

In term of demographical social media, the findings has shown that demographic statistic contributed a significant impact on social media marketing. As the findings, the contribution of female participant is much higher than male which accounts for the majority of participant. This statistic indicated that the social media concerns of women is more than man which might cause the target of marketing strategy. Banks might consider to create social media marketing campaign which focus more on women's preferences and their demand. Along with gender factor, based on the findings, the majority of participant contribution for the questionnaire survey was young and middle generation. Therefore, it can be concluded that social media influences and plays a vital role to Gen Y and Gen Z compare with old generation (over 40 in age group). However, regarding the attraction of advertisement on social media, there is no significant correlation with demographics, hence, it has indicated that all customers should be attracted with diversified social media advertisements.

The findings also demonstrated that Vietnamese people tend to use social media to enhance various aspects of their daily lives, including entertainment, purchasing, communication, and information seeking. Viral advertisements on social media consistently capture attention, while user interactions and social media influencers significantly impact behaviour. Regarding purchasing products and services, the findings indicates that Vietnamese consumers prefer to spend more time researching and buying products on platforms like Facebook and Instagram. This demonstrates that social media interaction influences customer purchasing intentions.

The findings also revealed high consumer satisfaction with bank's social media efforts. With the increasing presence of social media in the Vietnamese banking sector, banks are currently focusing on enhancing their social media presence and activities to attract and satisfy customers. In conclusion, the research achieved its first objective of exploring the contribution of social media in the banking industry, as well as the second objective of examining consumer attitudes towards social media marketing. Additionally, the findings highlighted potential risks associated with social media use in choosing banking services. However, customers generally trust banks' social media channels, as their personal information is protected during interactions

❖ **Findings from Interview analysis:**

In general, the findings has demonstrated that the majority of the participants agree with the concept of social media impacts on their purchasing behaviours. Especially in banking context, based on the participant perspectives as known as bank employees, it reconfirmed that social media has become a essential tool in marketing strategies of banks. Functional factors of social media has supported banks to reach to all the marketing purpose such as raising brand awareness, expanding the relationship with existing customer and potential customers, reducing marketing costs and attracting customer with diversified contents. In addition, the findings have focused on indicating opportunities and challenges when applying social media to banking activities as well as to marketing strategies. Base on the participant's perspectives, the opportunities of social media support banking system in many aspect of marketing strategy, so that it facilitate the product delivered process to their consumer in the effective way. This findings also demonstrated that marketing communication has been significantly developed by utilising social media in the bank's marketing strategy because consumer behaviour was effectively investigated through bank's social media platforms. This leads to the practical outcome to accelerate customer decision making and purchasing. Additionally, benefits of social media analytic tools has supported bank to adjust appropriate marketing goals and plans, hence, it has increased the loyalty of existing customers and expand more potential customers. As a developing country, Vietnam banking sector has developed both retail banking and corporate banking, so social media has been described as a very practical tool to boost the banking performance as well as enhance their reputation in the competitive market. On the other hand, challenges of social media has till remained why banks deploy marketing campaign or utilise to raise

their brand awareness. Weaknesses factors have both indirectly and directly affect to the development of social media in banking sector. In this finding, in term of the challenges of social media, the security and privacy factor has been concerned the most. Because banking services is the typical sector and sensitive services while social media is an expose environment. It limited customer to search and look for product information. Along with this, banking system is the most secured to compare with other industry, therefore security on social media is not enough to let banks have more interaction with customer if customers desire to investigate deeply about a specific banking services. Understanding the risk of applying social media in promoting banking products, Vietnamese banks improving and making efforts to control it by their own policy and procedure as soon as possible to create a healthy online environment.

6.2.3. Limitation of the research:

There are some limitation of the research. Firstly, this research was carried out during the Pandemic Covid-19 which is the restriction for the researcher to travel back to Vietnam to implement interviews. It leads to the discussion of interview had to conduct via phone and email instead of in person meeting. Even though the interviews have complete, but some of answers seem to be too short and did not contain much details as expectation. This pandemic also affects to questionnaire distribution, because questionnaires was distributed only in banking environment, it cannot be appropriate to represent the whole banking product consumer who are working in different industries. The sample size is not big and participants working in banks has basically have more financial knowledge than others and understand the important of social media therefore it can bring the bias of respondents about the research topic.

Secondly, in the current situation of Vietnamese banking industry, the priority of banks is digital banking transformation to innovate the banking system and facilitate banking operation to reduce costs and improve competitiveness, therefore, digital banking channel would become the main platform for the bank to concentrate. Although social media is always utilised to deploy marketing campaigns and product release, many banks employed outsource agency to implement their social media marketing. Hence, the managing social media activities of banks sometimes are implemented by marketing

agency, it leads to the participant perspective were not have a deep insight in some aspects towards their social media marketing strategy.

Third, because banking products are always typical financial products which customer information need to be confidential, therefore, based on the Vietnamese people habit, Vietnamese banks are not able to utilised social media for transaction making or conduct as customer service. In the fact, Vietnamese people prefer to use social media for searching, interaction and looking for marketing campaigns, however, in term of providing private information on social media, they would not be confident. Hence, in order to protect customer, after approach them on social media, banks have to transfer them to the official customer service or call centre of banks to figure out customer problem if necessary. Overall, researcher has limited investigation all the functions of social media when applying in Vietnamese banking due to a typical industry and Vietnamese customer habit.

Finally, the last limitation of the research is from the bank policy. During the interviewing process, due the bank policy, even though all the participants has provide the honest and useful information, but they seem to not expose all the detail of social media operation in their banks. All the information concerning future plan or negative comments from consumer, participants did not provide in detail. In another aspect, Vietnamese banking industry is very competitive especially in retail banking where social media marketing has been applied to approach more customers, therefore, the social media marketing strategy of banks did not mentioned too much to forecast the successful of social media in a particular bank.

6.2.4. Recommendation of further research:

Although the trend of social media has wisely spread in Vietnam, the its application in banking industry still considered as not creative. There was not many studies investigating about social media towards customer service in banking. As said above, because banking is a typical industry which need to protect personal customer information, the social media application has not been completely utilised. In the future, if banks improve the security and privacy system, then link it to social media, thus, this can be more interesting for future research to re-examine the effectiveness of social media to banking sectors. Additionally, the development of social media in banking industry requires the supports of banking policy. The supportive policy enable to facilitate the application of

social media in banking. The adjustment of current regulation and operational procedures in Vietnamese banks will create the association between digital bank and social media which can generate new benefits for consumers. As a result, it is recommended for researchers to examine the potentially transformation of social media when the new policy adjustment has been conducted in the future.

Currently, Facebook is still a main platform to conduct banking activities and marketing promotions in Vietnam. Along with that, YouTube is another platform to support Facebook with viral video to raise brand awareness. In the meantime, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram and Tiktok are a trendy platform which many international financial institutions and banks utilised them in effectiveness way. During the research process, the researcher realized that Vietnamese banks has not diversified their social media platforms, therefore, if in the future, social media platforms are expanded wisely in banking system, it would be recommended for researchers to identify the new outcomes of social media in Vietnamese banking sector.

Moreover, due to the habit of using cash of many Vietnamese, especially it happens in old generation, these group of customer use social media for entertainment and purchasing other product online but they do not have concern towards banking products. Therefore, with the rapid technology innovation, banks will create appropriate contents and campaigns on social media to expand their market as well as to approach more customers. Based on this result, this can be another area for researchers to explore in success of social media in the future.

At the moment, Vietnamese banks utilise social media mainly into retail banking to promote retail banking products, raise brand awareness or release new banking products. However, corporate banking also should be considered to apply social media to develop products and associate with clients to reinforce banking capabilities. Hence, this can be become a significant field to be researched in the future.

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APPENDIX:

1. QUESTIONNAIRES :

Question 1:

What is your gender?

- Female (1)
- Male (2)

Question 2:

What is your age?

- 18 to 29 (1)
- 30 to 39 (2)
- 40 to 49 (3)
- 50 to older (4)

Question 3:

Are you using any kind of social media?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Prefer not to say (3)

Question 4:

If you are using social media, how long do you usually spend on this per day?

- Less than an hour (1)
- 1-3 hours (2)
- 3-5 hours (3)
- More than 5 hours (Your job relates to social media) (4)

Question 5:

Which social media platform do you think is more useful to purchase products/services?

- Facebook
- LinkedIn
- Twitter
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Other platforms

Question 6:

Are you currently employed in the financial sector?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Prefer not to say (3)

Social media influences human behaviour

Question 7: To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Statements	Strongly disagreed	Disagreed	Neither agreed or disagreed	Agreed	Strongly agreed
Social media creates communities that can influence human interactions.	1	2	3	4	5
People rely on social media to make a decision.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media inspires people to have a better life.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media provides more information and useful knowledge.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media platforms are where people enable express their experiences and opinions freely.					
Social media is addictive and an engaging tool that exists in the user's lives.	1	2	3	4	5

Social media influences human behaviour in purchasing

Question 8:

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Statements	Strongly disagreed	Disagreed	Neither agreed or disagreed	Agreed	Strongly agreed
Social media is a tool that significantly contributes to communication effectiveness.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media is a tool to improve the performance of marketing campaigns to attract users	1	2	3	4	5

Social media platforms enhance information spreading.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media builds value and trust between users and brands.	1	2	3	4	5
Social media creates opportunities for users to approach various brands while considering to purchase goods and services.	1	2	3	4	5

Question 9:

What kind of advertisement on social media impacts you towards considering a specific product/service?

- Reviews from users on the brand’s social media (1)
- Social Ads (2)
- Reviews of social media influencers (3)
- Shared posts of attractive contents and images of the product/service on social media (4)

Social media influences the banking industry

Question 10:

Do you usually use social media to search for information regarding banking activities?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Prefer not to say (3)

Question 11:

If you are using social media for searching information regarding banking activities, what activity would you tend to look for the most?

Customer service (1)

Marketing/Promotions (2)

Products/services researching (4)

Recruitment (5)

Question 12:

To what extent do you think banks use social media for the following purposes?

	Highly agree	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Highly disagree
Raising brand awareness	1	2	3	4	5
Expanding relationship with existing and potential customers	1	2	3	4	5
Reducing marketing and advertising costs	1	2	3	4	5
Attracting customers with diversified content.	1	2	3	4	5

Question 13:

If you are employed or currently working in a banking or financial institution, what activities do you think banks take as successful social media tactics to attract their customers?

- (12) Being visual on social media
- (13) Focusing on customer service
- (14) Inviting Influencers/Celebrities
- (15) Educating and providing financial advice to their customers/followers on social media
- (16) Engaging with interactive contents

Question 14:

Customer satisfaction with benefits from social media towards banking services

Rate if you are satisfied with your current banks as the following factors:

	Highly dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Highly satisfied
Customer experience gained through the bank's social media	1	2	3	4	5
High quality in interactive support	1	2	3	4	5

Customer expectations gained towards banking services	1	2	3	4	5
Information provided on social media platforms of the bank are supportive	1	2	3	4	5
Better and faster responses to compare with branch banking service	1	2	3	4	5

Question 15:

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Highly agree	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Highly disagree
Social media platform of banks is less trustworthy	1	2	3	4	5
Social media is not secure once customers provide information to get support	1	2	3	4	5
Social media might influence customer negatively in choosing banking service or being loyal	1	2	3	4	5

Question 16:

Based on your experience with social media towards banking services, how likely would you carry on using to choose banking products/services in the future?

- Scale: 1(not very intense) to 5 (very intense)

Question 17:

Would you mind writing some sentences about how you expect banks to improve their services on their social media platforms?

2. INTERVIEW QUESTIONS:

1. What is your job title?
2. What is your department in your bank/financial institution?
3. How long have you been working in your position?

Social media in the bank

4. What type of social media platform do your bank uses?
5. How do you think social media is enhancing your bank's customer experience in general? Would you be able to explain these points in more detail?
6. In your experience, how would you describe the customer's views about social media influences to them in banking services?
7. Do you think your bank is successful in meeting customer requirements through social media platforms? If yes, what did make you ensure that?
8. What impacts do you think social media has on a bank's profitability?
9. How do you think social media can help your bank capture and retain customers?
10. What is your general view about the development of social media within the bank in the last few years?
11. What do you think about your bank strategies to improve and expand social media in the near future?

